

Exploring Remote Research Supervision: Challenges and Opportunities

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M.A. Academic Practice

2021

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of information technologies combined with economic challenges in recent years has generated a need for universities to compete effectively for new sources of funding while also maintaining cost-effective and competitive operations. This has resulted in a significant rise in distance education programmes. The current COVID global pandemic has made the task of remote teaching and in particular remote postgraduate supervision more demanding. Remote supervision is in general under-researched field requiring empirical validation. Furthermore, although there are a number of supervision models, none have not been applied to remote supervision, so there are open questions concerning if and how they reflect the supervisor's experience of supervising research students remotely.

This study involved conducting a focus group involving academics at the Department of Computing, Dublin City University(DCU) engaged in remote (online) research supervision. The Focus group explored whether/how supervisory practices changed as campuses were closed during the Covid-19 pandemic. The purpose of the focus group is to generate data for reflexive thematic analysis, the aim being to capture knowledge for understanding and hypothesis generation for future research.

The results of reflective thematic analysis indicate that supervisors engaged in remote supervision report negative experiences in the context of i) providing students access to adequate research infrastructure ii) enabling student research enculturation iii) ensuring the development of students' critical thinking skills and vi) building a strong student supervisor relationship. The study makes a novel research contribution in that it validates and elaborates on the challenges of remote supervision as identified. Furthermore, the analysis underscores also how existing models of research supervision are impacted negatively by distance learning and will require adaptation to a remote context. Finally, the study provides a series of recommendations with respect to research gaps (challenges and opportunities) in remote supervision that require further exploration and validation.

Acknowledgements

A sincere thank you to all of the staff at School of Computing, Dublin City University (DCU) who participated in this study. It would not have been possible without your willing participation and cooperation. I am also extremely grateful to my heads of School, Prof Alan Smeaton and Prof Martin Crane and the Learning and Development Unit at DCU who agreed to financially support my studies.

I am extremely grateful to Dr. Jan Smith for the amazing support that she gave over the last year – providing structure and supporting material throughout the entire MA process, providing advice and thoughtful feedback. Her support and understanding over this last year is very much appreciated.

Thanks also to Dr Michelle Tooher, Dr Simon Warren, Dr Sharon Flynn and Dr. Iain MacLabhrainn and the rest of the CELT team past and present – for all your input and guidance and support over the last few years as I worked through the excellent PgCert and PgDip to get to this stage. I am very grateful for all the excellent work that you do and enjoyed the course so much. Thanks also to my peers throughout the PgCert, PgDip in particular Dr Deirdre McHugh who my was excellent partner for peer review in teaching and learning. I also want to thank my peers in the MA Community of Practice led wonderfully by Jan, who always made me feel part of the NUIG family while studying remotely pre and during Covid.

Finally, I would like to thank my family, children and especially my wife Alessandra for their patience, support and love during my studies.

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Chapter 1: Introducing Remote Supervision

1.1 Motivation

The rapid advancement of information technologies in recent years combined with the economic challenges has generated a global demand for universities to compete effectively for new sources of funding while also maintaining cost-effective and competitive operations. This has resulted in a significant rise in distance education programmes (Nasiri and Mafakheri, 2015; Andrew, 2012). Universities who provide distance learning and education programmes are also ideally placed to attract more part-time students in particular flexible opportunities for working professionals seeking to up-skill to maintain competitiveness in the job market, as well as inclusivity of educational access to people with disabilities.

The current COVID global pandemic has made the task of remote teaching and in particular remote postgraduate supervision more demanding. The typical supervision routine which would often have occurred in structured face to face manner has now been disrupted and aside from relying on their implicit leadership and management of supervisors, supervision must now be delivered in a more focused, limited and organized manner (Ghani, F. ,2020).

Although it is assumed that there are no differences between remote or campus based supervision, remote postgraduate supervision poses a number of challenges at the cultural, personal, intellectual and professional level with respect to 1) supervisor-supervisee interactions and 2) the content, progress and delivery of research activities and output (Nasiri and Mafakheri, 2015)

1.2 Aims & Objectives

The aim of this project is to explore the experience of academics, who are engaged in remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in the Department of Computing, Dublin City University(DC). Focus groups will be used to explore whether/how supervisory practices changed as campuses were closed during the Covid-19 pandemic. The purpose of

the focus group is to generate data for content analysis – specifically reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To goal is to gain knowledge for understanding and hypothesis generation for future research (Wallace and Wray, 2006, p. 90).

1.3 Personal Context and Academic Environment

While graduating masters and doctoral candidates is a departmental Key Performance Indicator (KPI) in their own right, achieving high quality publication output requires resources typically in the form of postgraduate research students, who usually expect to be funded for the duration of the postgraduate program, inclusive of course fees. Having both access to funding and postgraduate researchers does not guarantee high quality publications. It is no surprise then that good quality supervisory practice is the final catalyst to ensure success. With respect to the postgraduate supervision, I am currently acting as the primary supervisor for four postgraduate research students and have supervised over four postgraduate research students to successful completion. I also have a growing interest in the pedagogy of research supervision and I am particularly interested in learning more about concepts of research supervision pedagogy and methodologies (Lee, 2019; McCallin and Nayar, 2012)

1.4 Rationale for the study

The rationale is to understand the academic practice within the context of remote research supervision and to what extent it relates to the research/practice literature in the field. The goal is **not to** elicit knowledge at this time in order to affect any change in the field. So the aim is **not to elicit** knowledge for *critical evaluation* by taking a negative standpoint based on the data analysis from one focus group alone (Wallace and Wray, 2006, p. 90). Nor would the analysis sufficiently empirical to draw any concrete conclusions with respect to supervision practice with the field. In addition, attempting to evaluate supervision activities is too broad and out of scope given the time limits. However, the outcome of the focus group will have the goal for *knowledge as action* in order to inform efforts to potentially bring about improvement to the prevailing practice within the department (Wallace and Wray, 2006, p. 90). Furthermore, this type of inquiry is conservative involving

basic gap spotting and neglect spotting (Sandberg and Alvesson, 2011) with respect to supports available for academics or students engaged in remote supervision. It will not attempt to reject existing supervision practices or models, but I will make recommendations for future research based on gap and neglect spotting. Any critical stance would be inaccurate and not representative given the absence of a more rounded analysis containing additional qualitative and quantitative data such as first hand accounts, lecturer interviews and student evaluations.

1.5 Remote Supervision and Models of Research Supervision

Firstly, with respect to existing literature, there are number of models and conceptual frameworks for research supervision (See Section 2.2). In general, existing models are naturally generic in they tend not to focus on the specific needs of any discipline in particular science, engineering and technology for that matter. However, to my knowledge none have not been applied to the context of remote supervision, so there are open questions with respect to their robustness and fitness for purpose for modelling remote supervision and to what degree they reflect the supervisor's experience of supervising distance learning postgraduate research. Of course we must bear in mind, that the existing models were developed from studies involving supervisors (and students) engaged in full time campus based postgraduate research supervision.

Secondly, and most critically, remote supervision is an under researched and neglected area in general and while some of the challenges and research opportunities have been posited the literature, they have not been empirically validated, which is a significant research gap that this thesis in part attempts to address. Hence, given the challenges posed by the on-going Covid-19 pandemic globally and the move to emergency remote supervision of research degrees, this research is timely.

1.6 Research Questions

The aims of this thesis can be operationalized by the following **two** research questions:

- **RQ1:** *What are the challenges and opportunities experienced by academics engaged in the remote supervision of postgraduate research students?*
- **RQ2:** *How do supervisors engaged in remote supervision relate to existing models of Research supervision (specifically Lee's Concepts of Supervision, (2019) and Gatfield's Supervisory Management Grid, 2005)?*

1.7 Methodology

Focus groups are a form of group interview, which who discuss a topic provided by the researcher in order to yield a collective view. The goal of a focus group is to gather data (views and opinions, themes on challenges and opportunities) with respect to remote supervision for subsequent content analysis (Cousin, 2009), specifically Thematic Analysis (TA), which is an umbrella term for a cluster of approaches for analysing qualitative data that share a focus on identifying patterns of meaning or *themes* in qualitative data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The data will be automatically transcribed (and manually checked) from an online Focus Group consisting of academic staff members in the Department of Computing, Dublin City University who are engaged in remote postgraduate research supervision. Reflexive TA (See Section 3.3) as it is both theoretically flexible and emphasises the researcher's subjectivity (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Moreover it is a very accessible and relatively easy to learn and ideal for non social scientists such as myself who are engaging in educational research. Reflexive TA will be applied to the focus group data in order to capture and summarise themed patterns. The goal is to capture a thematic structure of knowledge, which represent research supervisors' current practice and experiences of remote supervision and if (and how) they relate to two existing supervision models (specifically Lee's Concepts of Supervision, (2019) and Gatfield's Supervisory Management Grid, (2005) *and* the challenges outlined in the literature (Nasiri and Mafakheri, 2015) (See Section 2.3 for critical review).

In summary, this is a *qualitative* study, as I am interested in acquiring more complex, substantive and richer layers of data as opposed to the only surface information that would be elicited by a quantitative questionnaire (Cohen et al, 2018, Chapter 23). Hence, the

methods are appropriate given the research goals, time and resources, and the nature of the data.

1.8 Structure of Thesis.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** critically analyses the relevant literature with respect research supervision pedagogy, including the models of research supervision most relevant to remote supervision. The chapter also analyses the existing albeit limited scholarship on remote supervision and concludes with an analysis of research gaps within the literature.
- **Chapter 3** describes in detail the methodology used in this study. It outlines my theoretical position and details the qualitative methods used. I outline the design of the focus group, recruitment and sampling strategies and study demands. In addition, I describe reflexive Thematic Analysis (TA) in detail and justify my choice (Braun and Clarke, 2006).
- **Chapter 4** presents the results of reflexive thematic analysis applied to data derived from the focus group. I present a thematic map, which provides an overview of our results. Furthermore, I provide a detailed analysis and illustrative narrative for each theme (sub theme and code). Finally, I offer a summary critical analysis of each theme and their interrelationships, while also engaging with the relevant literature.
- Finally, **Chapter 5** presents my final recommendations with respect to challenges and opportunities remote research supervision based on my analysis of the literature and the results of my reflexive thematic analysis. I outline the limitations of my study and revisit the research questions posed in this chapter, and conclude with recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review – Supervision Models and Remote Supervision

2.1 Introduction

In Chapter 1, I outlined the motivations for our study into remote research supervision as well as the challenges it poses at the various levels (cultural, personal, intellectual and professional) for 1) supervisor-supervisee interactions and 2) the content, progress and delivery of research activities and output (Nasiri and Mafakheri, 2015); challenges which are likely to be further exacerbated as result of the current COVID global pandemic (Ghani, F., 2020);. In this thesis chapter I provide i) a brief overview of research supervision pedagogy (Section 2.1), ii) analyse the literature within the scope of concepts and models of supervision (Section 2.2) as I am interested in how these frameworks relate to remote supervision and iii) examine the challenges of remote supervision (Section 2.3) as described in the existing scholarship for the purposes of critical reflection and engagement when reporting my results in Chapter 4.

2.1 Research Supervision – A Brief Overview

The *traditional model* of supervision involves a dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student and is concerned with preparing the student for independent research (McCallin and Nayar, 2012). It assumes the supervisor is the expert and the student is the apprentice who *learns by doing*. Although superficially highly structured involving regular meetings to discuss and document progress, upon closer examination the traditional model implies that supervisors engage in *mentoring, sponsoring, quality assurance* with respect to *progressing*

and *coaching* (McCallin and Nayar, 2012). The traditional model arguably demands for intelligent, self-directed and self-motivated students who have strong (possibly) innate capacity for independent research and thus require minimal input from their supervisors in order to progress. The Irish PhD, which was claimed to have first awarded by Trinity College Dublin in 1935 (Delany, 2008) is also based on the British single supervisory model is equivalent to the traditional model described above whereby the doctoral degree is pursued using an apprenticeship (learn by doing) model of training (Delany, 2008). A detailed literature review of research supervision is beyond the scope of this thesis, however Delany's (2008) analysis of the literature is a good start as it provides an historical overview of the introduction of research degree and the evolution of the ad hoc (traditional apprenticeship) model of research supervision within the Irish context. In addition it provides a good starting point with respect and analysis of the literature effective models of research supervision (up to around 2002) , whereby *effective* is defined by the criteria specified in Gatfield (2002) i.e. timely thesis submission, excellent supervisory reports, high engagement with supervision meetings.

McCallin and Nayar (2012) provide another excellent analysis of the literature concerning supervision pedagogy, and models of supervision. In particular the research context is discussed, whereby government funding agencies have begun to impact on how research student supervision. Although this occurs in a New Zealand context, there are clear parallels in this respect with the UK and Ireland with the advent of the SFI (Science Foundation Ireland)¹ Research centres,² IRC Postgraduate Awards³ and the recent centres for research training (CRT⁴) all of whom have cleared defined expectations with respect to completion times, reporting, publication and deliverable output, dissemination and research training (generic and specialist). It is often the case the students in receipt of government funding must complete "a structured PhD", which is aims to operationalize the skills statement. Coming back to McCallin and Nayar (2012), faculty challenges are also addressed and the impact of quality metrics (faculty credentials, publication records, supervision completions and grant award successes) on successful student completion and the clear need for *formal training* in research supervision.

¹ <https://www.sfi.ie/>

² <https://www.sfi.ie/sfi-research-centres/>

³ <https://research.ie/funding/goipg/>

⁴ <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/centres-research-training/>

In this respect, Pearson and Brew (2002) propose a course outline for a programme for flexible professional development programme for supervisors. Their proposal is based on a framework for supervision development which is underpinned by i) an analysis of the practice of supervision and teaching strategies so as mentoring, coaching, students as apprentices, *modelling* whereby the supervisor models a task for the student, *scaffolding* providing intermediate supports and cues for the student and *fading* – the subsequent removal of the aforementioned supports and ii) discussions and definitions of what constitute research training – the key generalist and specialist skills required by the “complete scientist”, (Pearson and Brew, 2002, p. 137) as well as an analysis of senior academics conceptions of research and scholarship (Pearson and Brew, 2002, pp. 144-145).

Finally, this literature in general has focused solely on i) the full time research postgraduate undertaking ii) a 4 year PhD traditional research focused degree. The “professional doctorate” which targets students entering employment in areas other than academia often in the areas such as health sciences, psychology, nursing, education, business and finance, engineering, the goal being develop graduates of have research capability and who can become “active contributors to the knowledge economy in the workplace “(McCallin and Nayar, 2012, p. 69). The professional doctorate contains a significant number of taught components and research projects are practice or work based. In addition, supervision may often occur or develop in a group. For a good discussion of the professional doctorate see (McCallin and Nayar, 2012) and for a more update to discussion of the future of doctoral degree in general in the 21st Century we refer the reader to (Porter, 2021). In addition, it should be noted that the supervision of part-time postgraduate research are not captured explicitly within this literature review and in under researched topic in the scholarship on general. Watts (2008) provides a good overview of the challenges of supervising part-time PhD students and discusses the benefits of a more student centred or pastoral supervision pedagogy for supporting the part-time PhD.

We move to the next section, in which I discuss concepts and models of supervision, deemed most relevant to our research questions.

2.2 Models and Frameworks of Research Supervision

There are number of models and conceptual frameworks for research supervision and historically they owe their origins to clinical/medical supervision and

counselling/psychotherapeutic practices (Gatfield, 2005, p. 312: Gurr, 2001, p. 83). In the following subsections we compare and contrast **four** models for research supervision: i) Lee's (2008) , concepts of supervision, ii) Halse and Malfroy's (2020) approach to reformulating doctoral supervision as professional work iii) Gatfield's (2005) supervisory management styles and iv) Kiley's (2009) model of the supervision experience via threshold concepts.

2.2.1 Lee's (2019) Conceptual Approaches to Research Supervision

In (Lee, 2008, 2019), the author describes a series of conceptual approaches to supervision: *functional, enculturation, critical thinking, emancipation and relationship development*.

I will describe briefly each of the above concepts in the next sections, however for a detailed discussion on each of the concepts, I refer the reader to Appendix F. The framework (See Figure 2.1) is underpinned by a series of interviews with academic supervisors reflect on the “what” and “why” of the experience of supervision.

	Functional	Enculturation	Critical Thinking	Emancipation	Relationship Development
Supervisors Activity	Rational progression through tasks	Gatekeeping Master to apprentice	Evaluation Challenge	Mentoring, supporting constructivism	Supervising by experience, developing a relationship
Supervisor's knowledge & skills	Directing, project management	Diagnosis of deficiencies, coaching	Argument, analysis	Facilitation, Reflection	Managing conflict Emotional intelligence
Possible student reaction	Organised Obedience	Role modelling, Apprenticeship	Constant inquiry, fight or flight	Personal growth, reframing	A good team member. Emotional intelligence

Figure 2.1 Lee's Framework for Concepts of Research Supervision, (Lee, 2008, p. 268)

Supervisors report problems along a dichotomy of i) tensions between the professional and personal self and ii) tensions with respect to student dependence/independence. We pay particular attention to this model of supervision, as it well known documented and highly cited in scholarship of research supervision.

The functional approach.

This approach which is directive, task orientated and concerned with project management, (Lee, 2019, pp. 1-18) The supervisor is concerned with “institutional procedures for quality assurance”, (p 31, Anne Lee, 2021) and ensures that the student has access to all necessary institutional information and study supports he/she requires for their doctoral journal.

Deadlines and assessment criteria are made clear and the role of supervisors and co-supervisors and the requirements for ethical research practice are made explicit.

The approach draws parallels with Gatfield’s (2005) *directive* supervisions style and a managerial approach (Vilkonis, 2002). There is an underlying theme of consistent structure being established early in the supervision process which would be both maintain itself also and the students progress. The author describes a series of stages which are concerned with recruiting, teaching and supervising research students (Lee, 2019, p. 42).

Enculturation

Here the supervisor is concerned with gatekeeping, diagnosing deficiencies and coaching the student on how to become a member of the research community providing with sense of belonging by contributing to department and/or research unit. This approach is frequently referenced within the context of an apprenticeship model, whereby the research student must acquire a significant amount of knowledge both professionally and interpersonal about the nature of academic life (Lee, 2019, p. 48). This knowledge is subtle and not explicitly taught, but it essential to learn if the student wishes to become a competent and skilled professional researcher. The academic/research team can support this by providing opportunities attend and/or lead research seminars, attend conferences, attend/co-organise workshops and undertake teaching assistance activities as well as undergraduate or even taught postgraduate co-supervision. The supervisor is much like a “family doctor” (Lee, 2019, p. 49), providing some specific knowledge or expertise but will also act as a *gatekeeper*, “choosing which gates to open”, which must be handled with care in the early stages of the student or researchers’ PhD lifecycle/research career.

Critical Thinking

The critical thinking approach is concerned with a constant inquiry, analysis, argumentation (Lee, 2008). It is concerned with i) beliefs about knowledge and ii) the ability to assess statements relative to those beliefs. It is also concerned with the ability to “define and

evaluate an argument” in manner which is appropriate to the discipline(s) in question (Lee, 2019, p. 70). Finally critical thinking involves developing the ability of a postgraduate research student to solve a problem in logical manner and reflect metacognitively on his/her performance. The supervisor in this context is concerned with developing in the student the ability to understand, critique and create an argument. The supervisor depersonalises (but does not disregard) the relationship with the student in order to “examine substantive thinking processes free from emotion (Lee, 2019, p. 70) – what are the arguments for an against? What are the gaps? What has been considered and what has been left out? Naturally the critical thinking approach makes excellent preparation for the viva defence (Wisker, 2005).

Emancipation

With respect to this approach the academic is seeks to empower the student to find their own direction and values and to apply them to their research. Supervisors are supportive and yet where appropriate will challenge the student but are cautious not to impose their own values/agenda (Lee, 2019, p. 95). Supervision meetings and group work involved the academic both providing and seeking information and subsequently seeking the student’s opinion. With respect to the emancipatory approach, a supervisor may allow a student to fail at a particular task if it may be extremely beneficial to the students learning. In this context the academic acts as a non directive mentor. Unlike enculturation, the emancipatory approach will not attempt to constrain the student within the discipline. Furthermore, personal development planning is strongly encouraged in this approach. Universities now expected to promote and ensure that students have access to personal development plans(PDPs) which tend to fall into three categories of i) learning, research and scholarship ii) employability, engagement and society and iii) personal and communication skill (Lee, 2019, p. 96).

Relationship Development

This approach to supervision is characterised by friendship and normally both the academic and student will typically anticipate and overt any unnecessary conflict (Lee, 2019, p. 110). Problems are resolved with the goodwill of both parties and non “overt rationalisation” will require expressing in order resolve a given problem or complete requested tasks. Although

boundaries shall be maintained, both academic supervisor and postgraduate student may introduce each other to friends and family (Lee, 2019, p. 111). Unsurprisingly, the quality of the relationship plays an important (if not the most important) role in determining student satisfaction (Harkin, 1998, Smith, 1997, Carson 1996). Likewise, poor relationships can result in poor completion rates (Taylor and Beasley, 2005, p. 69). Lee analyses the scholarship surrounding the relationship approach discussing in detail Aristotle’s notions of friendship, *friendship of utility* and his moral virtues of *courage, temperance, liberality, magnificence, friendliness and wittiness* (Lee, 2019, p. 111), as well as the need for positive student/supervisor relationship as evidenced by the qualitative work of Ives and Rowley (2005).

2.2.2 Investigating Supervisory Management Styles (Gatfield, 2005)

Gatfield’s (2005) supervisory management grid, (See Figure 2.2) contains **four** management styles placed between two high to low axes, one labelled “support” and “structure”. The four styles are i) **Laissez-faire** [low structure low support] – Supervisor is “non-directive” and not committed to high levels of personal interaction with limited levels of motivation and management provided to the student. The supervisors may “appear” uncaring and uninvolved (Gatfield, 2005, p. 317) ii) **Pastoral** [low structure high support] - The supervisor is concerned with the student’s welfare and provides information however the student is

Figure 2.2: Gatfield’s Supervisor Management Grid, (Gatfield, 2005, p.317)

responsible for their research project management and self-structure, so the supervisor is less task driven. iii) **Directional** [high structure low support] - The focus of supervision is the management and direction of the student's research project but with no provision of pastoral support. The supervisor maintains a close regular interactive relationship with the student but avoids non-task(personal) issues. iv) **Contractual** [high structure high support] - The supervisor is involved with the management of the student's research project and, if needed, provides pastoral support (Gatfield, 2005). The supervisor provides direction, and exercises good management skills and interpersonal relationships. This style is considered the most demanding for the supervisor's time.

It should be noted that although the supervisor may have a preferred style, it is influenced by the student's attitude and responses (Gatfield, 2005, p. 318). Likewise the supervisor, will move between a range styles at across stages in the PhD research project, in that the supervisor management grid is dynamic and changes over time (Gatfield, 2005, p. 222). Finally there is strong overlap with the Garfield's Supervision Grid and Lees Framework for Approaches to research supervision in Figure 2.1 (Lee, 2019, pp. 19)

2.2.3 Re-Theorizing doctoral supervision as professional work (Halse and Malfroy, 2010)

In (Halse and Malfroy, 2010) the authors reformulate doctoral supervision as "professional work" The model is informed by language, discourse and theory and based on empirical analyses, doctoral supervision is theorized as professional work that comprises five facets: i) the *learning alliance* which is the agreement between supervisor and student to work towards the common goal i.e. the production of a high quality doctorate. (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 84), ii) *habits of mind*, is described as a both a disposition and mode of behaviour, which involves the capacity to learn and reflect on the principles around making particular decision (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 85), iii) *scholarly expertise refers to* "theoretical knowledge acquired through reflection and thinking"(Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 86), iv) *technê*, is understood as craft knowledge, but it is "more than technical skills or instrumental practice" (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 87), and finally v) *contextual expertise*,

which is concerning with the possession of knowledge and understanding of the institutional and disciplinary context of doctoral education (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 87).

2.2. 4 Threshold concepts experienced by doctoral students and strategies for support Kiley (2009).

Kiley (2009) models the supervision experience from the doctoral students perspective using threshold concepts, which critical learning and development concepts whose threshold must be crossed and must retain the following characteristics of being: *transformative, integrative, irreversible, bounded and troublesome* (Meyer and Land, 2006). In (Kiley, 2009) a postgraduate research student may be in experience the ambiguous “liminal state” – the tension between knowing, not knowing whereby they i) feel *stuck*, feeling unproductive and unmotivated or ii) mimic at the surface level (mimicry) what their peers are doing. Understanding the key threshold concepts (examples include: *argument, thesis, theory, framework*), within the context of the journey of the postgraduate research journey, which reinforce a liminal state, can facilitate a learning transition (Kiley, 2009, pp 298-299). According to (Kiley, 2009) this can be achieved in collaborative group work via a community of learners/research culture i.e. journal clubs, seminars, writing retreats, reading key theses/dissertations and discussing with peers/supervisor.

2.3 Challenges in Remote Supervision

2.3.1 Remote Supervision in Brief

There area of distance or remote(online) supervision is effectively quite under researched and in fact the term itself does not appear to have concrete definition in the literature. Other terms include *e-supervision, telesupervision* the latter, which implies the use of video conferencing to supervise graduate studies (Sussex, 2008). Distance supervision can be delivered **asynchronously** exchange of materials by post, fax, email, and or shared audio/video files, and via shared project manager/content repositories such as Google Drive, Microsoft OneDrive, Basecamp), project wikis, micro blogging (Twitter for sharing publications) and or **synchronously** via video/conferencing (Zoom, Teams, Google Meet), live chat (Skype, Slack) and virtual learning environment (Blackboard, Moodle). If we return to providing definition of distance supervision, given that the research supervision

owes its origins to clinical and counselling supervision (Gatfield, 2005, p312)(Gurr, 2001, p. 83). Publications of remote/distance or “cyber” clinical supervision indicate the accepted definition of clinical supervision “applies to all modalities”, whether supervision is provided face-to-face or electronically using synchronous, or asynchronous methods (Nelson et al., 2010, p. 2). So if we take the traditional model of supervision, which involves a “dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student” which concerned with preparing the student for independent research. (McCallin and Nayar, 2012, p. 68), a first attempt would define distance/remote supervision as:

“ a dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student which occurs predominately electronically (usually online) using synchronous, or asynchronous methods and is concerned with preparing the student for independent research”

Unwin (2007), provides a rich list of postgraduate supervisor elements and tips on how to adapt them for distance delivery. Ghani, (2020) discusses strategies and highlights technologies for teaching, assessing and supervising graduate students online within the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. A good comprehensive historical overview of research supervision within the context of distance/remote learning is provided in (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). Moreover, the authors clearly state as evidenced by their analysis of the literature that is “widely assumed that there is no difference” between the requirements for completing and PhD/Research Master’s programme on campus or by distance. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1963) and reveals that there has been little exploration into the challenges, complexities and difficulties of conducting distance research degree programmes let alone the potential benefits to student and supervisor, which we explore in the section. Finally, although numerous universities have produced policy documents on what processes to follow in order to formally engage in remote supervision (i.e. forms, number of meetings online/face to face – every 6 months etc), they tend do not offer practical guidance remote supervision. However, the UK Council For Graduation does provide a very comprehensive guide, which is evidence based by the scholarship of distance learning and research supervision to our knowledge (Kumar et al. , 2020).

2.3.1 Remote Supervision, Challenges and Strategies (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015)

Nasri and Mafakheri (2015), provide an excellent overview of challenges with respect to remote or distance research supervision which include *lack of depth or delicacy*, as discussed in communication as result of distractions caused by the fast pace of technology changes and the need to explore the latest technology instead of focusing on the research. The dislocation effect results in the likelihood that this a lack of personal knowledge and hence rapport between student and supervisor and there is no opportunity for informal discussion with the possibility of decreased engagement and motivation on both sides. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). However, differences in computer (software or hardware) literacy can reinforce the effect of dislocation and the appetite for interaction (Sussex, 2008; Williams et al, 2011). The reduced appetite for interaction can be compounded by the challenge of *time differences*, if students/supervisors are in different countries/regions which may have an “imbalances” with respect to IT capacity. This can create a more serious challenge for part time students (often in the case of those enrolled in masters degrees) who are working professionals and have limited time to spend on resolving IT problems (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1964).

Supervisors may *experience increased workload* as they expected have high online availability. Furthermore, they must often act as institutional gatekeepers for the distance student which demands them to remain up to date with research degree requirements, ethics, university services (library facilities, funding opportunities, student services, counselling services, IT facilities, research seminars, postgraduate training), in order to be ready to provide “timely” guidance to students on pastoral and administrative matters (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965; Unwin, 2007).

As distance students, unlike campus students, do not have the opportunity to interact with other peers and colleagues, there is a risk that this *isolation* may result in ignorance, lack of focus and an *overdependence* on the supervisor on the student’s part, which may impact negatively on the students capacity to develop i) **critical thinking** skills and ii) their research independently (**emancipation**) (See Section 2.2.1) (Crossouard. 2008).

Remote supervision is also vulnerable to cultural misunderstanding, as it crosses geographical and cultural borders, which can result in misinterpretation, confusions and even conflicts with respect to race, gender and religion (**enculturation**, See Section 2.2.1) between the supervisor and the student (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965; Sussex, 2008, Wisker, 2007). The supervisor must be prepared to develop his/her awareness of cultural norms, difference, preconceptions and potential conflicting issues.

Distance postgraduate students coming from different cultures may have particular expectations with respect to supervision and models in the context of the student/teacher relationship. Students from some cultures may expect a collectivistic (teacher centred) relationship while others are used to a individualistic (student centred) relationship (Ventor, 2003).

A obvious challenge can results *technical barriers* with respect to communication tools with the need to use various asynchronous/synchronous communication tools due to the lack of face to face contact and it can be “delicate” task to find the “optimal blend” of communication channels (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966). This is critical to develop a rich **relationship** (See Section 2.2.1) between supervisor and supervisee as well as to ensure persistent and recoverable delivery of information between both parties(Fox, 2002). The collective use of such varied communication channels can suffer naturally from technical issues and limitations such as problems with: internet bandwidth, hardware limitations, accessing good quality web cameras, audio/video difficulties, memory requirements, data storage, remote access to hardware, and computer viruses and spyware (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966).

There may be *linguistic barriers* as a result of linguistic gap in either side from a lack of fluency, notwithstanding barriers in the content varying technical language standards with respective the discipline or research field such as Engineering (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965)

Finally *feedback systems may suffer* whereby student/supervisor tend to be distracted from each other as results of being in difference locations. Hence both parties may “forget” about mutual expectations and responsibilities. This may result in a decline in feedback frequency and quality. In addition, fewer interactions introduces the risk of

misinterpretation and varied expectations with respect to addressing feedback (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965)

Nasri and Mafakheri (p. 1966, 2015) discusses a number of potential strategies for addressing these challenges but they clearly state that there is limited evidence in the literature to support them. **Strategies** include:

- Hierarchical feedback systems (Unwin, 2007) from accepting track changes in documents for longer feedback, to audio file monologues to deliver opinionated feedback. Caution should be advised with track changes as students may accept the feedback thus eliminating constructive debate, hence a comment prompting dialogue and discussion (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966)
- Stricter deadlines with respect submission of progress reports and feedback on both sides (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967)
- Have an open debate with respect to expectation on “means, depth and timing” of supervisor- supervisee interactions and experiment with the various options (Andrews, 2012).
- Address lack of peer interaction and peer feedback by creating mailing lists for sharing research materials, use social media platforms to great a group research Facebook albeit internal access to virtual learning environment such Blackboard/Moodle with discussion boards may also be an option. The supervisor can organise virtual peer meetings and an annual local web based research conference is another option. International conferences are also occasions where face-to-face meetings can occur and they also provide the student with effective opportunity to acquire international contacts and collaborations thus reducing the reliance on the supervisor sides (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967). The supervisor can also identify quality research groups or labs at local university or research institutions so that the student will have the opportunity to gain additional peer feedback (Wisker, 2007).
- To address the lack of in-house training opportunities, dedicated pages should be created on the universities website or virtual learning environment(Moodle, Blackboard). It should include nduction, resource material, recorded seminars and training sessions. A dedicated virtual induction is recommended for distance

students (Unwin 2007; Wisker 2007). It should include a web-link, liver streaming seminar introducing the postgraduate research programme requirements, advice for students on any mandatory online courses to take (i.e. research ethics and integrity, intellection property management. Separate formal sessions can be organised to discuss issues such as research methods, diversity and cultural issues. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967).

- Finally, it is also recommended that course leader or tutor should be appointed to support the postgraduate distance learning programme in order to provide pastoral and administrative support to students, thus easing the administrative burden on supervisors (Paran et al. 2020)

2.4 Analytic Conclusions

In general we make the following observation with respect to research gaps concerning the literature and scholarship surrounding research supervision and remote research supervision:

- The models of supervision analysed in Section 2.2 in general do not appear to have been developed with distance/remote supervision in mind. Moreover they have not been applied to remote distance supervision so there is open question with respect to their robustness and fitness for purpose. In short this how do this models translate to online/distance learning space?
- Another question how “digitally aware” are these models? For instance what learning and communication technologies, asynchronous and synchronous teaching online activities map to Lee’s (2019) framework concepts of supervision and where? Hence a worthwhile exercise would involve conducting research into developing a *digitally annotated* model for research supervision.
- Another interesting research question is how well Lee’s (2019) concepts of supervision translate to the science, technology and engineering discipline. The model is general and rightly so and it may be worthwhile exercise to explore a methodology on how to instantiate a framework for specific disciplines thus ensuring better adoption.

- Supervision models and supervisor pedagogy in general tend to focus on a one-to-one ,face-to-face relationship between the supervisor and supervisee i.e. the full time campus based student pursuing a four year PhD Degree. The scholarship on supervision does not appear to differentiate between the PhD and the MSc by Research/MPhil degree and there appears to be an *implicit assumption* in the literature that the models, which apply to the PhD, apply also to the research masters. This also appears to be case for the **professional doctorate** (DPsych, EdD, EngD), which although they consist of a significant taught often contain group research projects/practica.
- Likewise the literature is lacking around the application of existing supervision models to **cohort/group supervision** of PhDs either face to face or remotely. This is particular the case with respect to the professional doctorates.
- There is less of focus in the literature at taught masters (Anderson et al., 2007, 2008) or undergraduate levels (Brew, 2010; Cullen, 2009)
- More research is required to explore the negative effect of distance learning in the context of remote supervision on the supervision process and the student with respect to Lee's (2019) concepts of **critical skills** and **emancipation** (student independence).
- Remote supervision is under in general researched and given the current Covid-19 pandemic this research is timely.
- Hierarchical feedback systems (Unwin, 2007) require more detailed exploration and empirical validation i.e. what processes/technologies work best, when and for which type of postgraduate student?

I have conducted detailed literature review of Research Supervision Pedagogy and Remote Supervision having compared and contrasted key models of research supervision (Section 2.2) and analysed what the scarce literature surrounding remote supervision, including the challenges and potential strategies to address (Section 2.3). Finally, I provided analytic conclusions and identified research gaps in the field which field directly into research questions. Lee's (2019) framework for research supervision is arguably the richest and well researched, however it is perhaps less accessible to the novice than Gatfield's (2005) supervisory grid which is more agile but perhaps less generalizable. Regardless both models are well aligned (Lee, 2019, p. 19) and more structured and suitable and better suited to

support reflective thematic analysis and our research methodology, which I move now to discuss in the next Chapter.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Position

This study is qualitative and *interpretivist*, as I am concerned with generating insights and understanding of a given context at given time and place (Cousin, 2009, Chapter 1). The research is *not positivist* in that I am not attempting to predict or measure human behaviours within this study. I do not attempt to make and firm claims; rather I attempt to interpret academics individual and collective experiences of remote supervision and the meaning they ascribe to them.

3.1.2 Ontological Position.

Ontology is the nature of reality (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988) and it is concerned with our basic beliefs of what a human is and the nature of reality. Reality (ontology) is interpretivist and is multiple and relative (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). Relativist ontology is the belief that reality is a finite subjective experience (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005)(Levers, 2013) Myr ontological stance within in the limits of this study is *nominalist* meaning reality is a projection of human imagination (Morgan and Smircich, 1980).

3.1.2 Epistemological Position.

Epistemology is concerned with about nature of knowledge and ways of coming to know, It is concerned with questions such as “How is it possible, if it is, for us to gain knowledge of the world?” (Hughes and Sharrock 1997). Epistemology concerned with “the nature, validity, and limits of inquiry” (Rosenau, 1992). It defines the nature of the relationship between the researcher(inquirer) and what counts as knowledge (Grant, 2021) and on what basis, we can make claims. My epistemological stance is *subjectivist*, as knowledge is created based on the personal and subjective views of the participants (Cousin, 2009, Chapter 1).

3.2 Methods

This study is qualitative as it involves analysing the data using Thematic Analysis (TA), which is an umbrella term for a cluster of approaches for analysing qualitative data that share a focus on identifying patterns of meaning or *themes* in qualitative data (Braun and Clarke,

2006). This study uses one approach to TA called *reflexive Thematic analysis* or reflexive TA (See Section 3.3) as it is both theoretically flexible and emphasises the researcher's subjectivity. Moreover it is a very accessible and relatively easy to learn and ideal for non social scientists such as myself who are engaging in educational research (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

I am interested in acquiring more complex, substantive and richer layers of data as opposed to the only surface information that may be elicited by a quantitative questionnaire. The content will be generated from data automatically transcribed (and manually checked) from an online Focus Group consisting of academic staff members in the Department of Computing, Dublin City University(DCU), who are engaged in postgraduate research supervision.

Reflexive TA will be applied to the data in order to capture and summarise themed patterns, generating a thematic structure of knowledge, which represents research supervisors' current practice and experiences of remote supervision and if (and how) they relate to existing supervision models and literature on remote supervision..

3.2.1 Focus Groups

Focus groups are a form of group interview, whereby participants discuss a topic provided by the researcher in order to yield a collective view. The goal of this Focus group is to gather data (views and opinions) about supervision frameworks and their experiences of remote supervision for subsequent content analysis. One focus group is appropriate in that I am concerned with the generation understanding and ideas, co-inquiry "sharing and comparing" and co-constructing knowledge. However, I am not attempting to generate theory or in this case new frameworks of research supervision, as this would require more data and time, which is outside the scope of the MA dissertation. However new observations and ideas may emerge and potentially new hypothesis may be generated for long term research.

3.2.2 Sample size

- Volunteers were drawn from the academic staff (of the Department of Computing at DCU), who supervise doctoral students in a form of teaching that was required to move online during the pandemic.
- The sample size ($n = 7$, 4 male, 3 female) was that of standard focus group (4-12 participants) academics (Cohen et, al, 2002, p. 436; Cousin, 2009, Chapter 4).
- The sampling method was purposeful and convenience based, drawing staff within the School of Computing – including a relatively equal number of both male/female participants.
- Academics were either permanent/contract staff at the levels:(Lecturer/Assistant Professor, Senior Lecturer/Associate Professor) with the exception of one Full Professor.
- Participants were engaged in doctoral supervision (either primary or secondary) but may or may not have graduated a PhD student.
- Supervisees of participants ranged from 1st -Final Year PhD students in Computing.

3.2.3 Recruitment

- Recruitment involved emailing staff members who are constrained to above criteria.
- Staff will be asked to recommend another colleague who was **not** on their supervision panel (Cohen et. al, 2002, p. 154). I attempted to constrain the criteria with to the academic rank by recruiting.
- Table 3.1 below outlines the number of students each academic is responsible for supervising. The table includes Taught Masters projects, which may include up to two students per project. Likewise undergraduate projects may include teams of up to five or six students. According to DCU Graduate Studies regulations, an academic can act as a supervisor or co-supervisor for up to maximum number of **ten** postgraduate research students at any one time (Graduate Studies, n.d.).

Participant	No of Full Time PhD Students	No. of Part-time PhD Students	No of Full Time Research MSC Students	No. of Part-time Research MSC Students	No. of Taught Masters projects (full time / part-time)	No. of undergraduat Projects (full-time/part-time)
Assistant Professor 1	2	0	0	0	2	14
Assistant Professor 2	3	0	0	0	3	4
Assistant Professor 3	6	0	0	0	11	0
Assistant Professor 4	6	0	0	0	4	4
Assistant Professor 5	7	0	0	0	6	4
Associate Professor 1	11	0	0	0	7	6
Full Professor 1	8	0	1	0	6	8
Total	43	0	1	0	39	40
Average	6	0	0	0	6	6

Figure 3.1. Supervision workload of Focus Group Participants

3.2.4 Study Demands

- Participants were to read the plain English Information Statement (See Appendix B) and sign the consent form digitally (See Appendix C).
- Participants were asked to join a password secure Zoom⁵ session hosted by this researcher.
- The Focus group was delivered in **two parts**:
Part 1: Duration 45 minutes followed be a 15 minute break
Part 2: Duration 45 minutes.
- **(Part 1)** The participants were provided an agenda whereby they will be asked engage in-group reflection with respect to remote supervision. Questions included *What Worked?, What did not work? Actionable Knowledge – What have you/we learnt? See Appendix D for more details.*

⁵ zoom.us

- **(Part 2)** In addition participants were asked to reflect on both Lee, (2019) and Gatfield's (2005) conceptual models of supervision and how it relates to their own supervision style (See Appendix D)
- The focus group was recorded on Zoom with consent from participants
- A transcript of the group was generated automatically in Zoom via the plugin otter.ai.

3.3 Ethical Issues related to project.

Below outlines the key ethical and data protection issues and related to the study and how they were addressed. For additional see Appendix B for the Ethics application of this thesis which was approved in January Semester 2 Academic Year 2020/2021

Research Integrity and Ethical Issues

- Focus group participants were reminded of the need for **confidentiality**.
- The information discussed in the group was **kept confidential**.
- The transcript was anonymised at source to ensure full confidentiality
- Participants had the right to withdraw prior to full anonymisation of the transcript.
- All participants were volunteers of equal academic rank, thus ensuring no conflicts of interest with respect to probation/promotion.
- The researcher had no line management responsibility of any potential participants to avoid issues of coercion.
- If a participant provides potential evidence of poor academic practice/research integrity than they were asked not to discuss the issue in the group.
- The participant will be advised confidentially/privately of the potential issue and to discuss the issue with the head of department or research integrity officer.
- If the themes within the group discussion inadvertently cause distress the participant was free to leave the group. The participant would have been debriefed separately and advised of Employee Assistance Services which are at their disposal at the university. No such incident occurred.
- Participants could withdraw from the focus group at anytime.

- The researcher ensured participants that the data or the department staff, university will not be misrepresented in the course of publishing the research as to cause harm (professionally or personally).

Data Protection Issues

- All **data was stored on secure cloud institutional** (DCU) repository. Data will not be stored on any standalone machine.
- The original Zoom recording and transcript will be retained until the dissertation is examined.
- Once this is done the Zoom recording will be destroyed.
- The original transcript was anonymised at source and will be kept data verification examination purposes but no longer than is necessary.
- The identity of participants has been **kept confidential**.

Ethical Note

Initially two Focus Groups were planned. The first group was intended as a pilot group involving the research convenor and senior academics, while the second group consisted only of assistant professors. However, as recruiting sufficient became difficult, it was necessary to merge both focus groups. Permission was sought individually and separately from each member in the second group to merge groups. In addition clarification was requested from the group as to whether having two senior academics and the research convenor in their group would create any conflict of interest and/or if they wished to subsequently withdraw. No conflicts were identified by any of the participants.

3.4 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

As mentioned earlier Thematic Analysis (TA) is a collection of approaches for analysing qualitative data which focus on identifying patterns of meaning or *themes* in qualitative data As stated by (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2012b) while there are different versions of TA which share some degree of theoretical flexibility, they can differ enormously in terms of both

underlying philosophy and procedures for producing themes. A detailed comparison of reflective thematic analysis with other forms of TA is outside the scope of this thesis and we refer the reader to Braun and Clarke, (2021a, 2021b) and Appendix H.

One of the advantages of the reflexive TA method outlined by is that it is theoretically-flexible; it can be used within different theoretical frameworks for quite different types of research questions. Furthermore, what is key in reflexive TA is that the theoretical position is made clear and that the researcher “acknowledge these decisions and recognise them as decisions” (Braun and Clarke, 2021). .

3.4.1 Different Orientations of Reflexive Thematic Analysis

As stated by (Braun and Clarke, 2006) Thematic Analysis can be approached in many difference ways and one the advantages of the authors reflexive approach is that all variations are possible, as long as the researcher’s chosen orientation is aligned to their research questions and that researcher both actively “decides” on their tailored version and makes it explicit when presenting their analysis. Table 3.2 below outlines the approaches.

Approach	Description
An inductive way	Coding and theme development are strongly linked to and directed by the content of the data (Patton 1990). The data may not be directly related to the specific questions asked to the participants. Coding in this context is not trying to fit into specific coding frame and is data-driven
A deductive way	Coding and theme development are directed by existing concepts or ideas in a theoretical or top down fashion. It is analyst driven as coding is tied to researchers theoretical interest and hence coding may be explicitly tied to a coding frame or research question (Braun and Clarke, 2021b)..
A semantic way	Coding and theme development reflect the explicit content of the data. Codes and themes are identified from the explicit surface meanings in the text. There is no attempt code beyond what the participant has said or written (<i>the latent way</i>) (Braun and Clarke, 2021b)..
A latent way	Coding and theme development report concepts and assumptions underpinning the data. It begins early in the analysis process to examine the “underlying ideas, assumptions, conceptualisations and ideologies “ that shape the semantic (surface) content.
A (critical) realist or essentialist way	Focuses on reporting an assumed reality evident in the data. The motivations, experience and meaning are

	theorised in a straightforward manner. The approach assumes a unidirectional relationship between, meaning and experience.
A constructionist way	Contrasts with the (critical) realist way in the meaning and experience are socially produced and reproduced. A constructionist framework cannot and does not focus on individual accounts but seeks to theorize the sociocultural contexts and structural conditions, which enable such individual accounts.

Table 3.2 Approaches to Reflective Thematic Analysis

Often inductive, semantic and (critical) realist approaches tend to be grouped together. This is also the case for the deductive, latent and constructionist approaches. However the authors clearly state in this separation is not always so rigid and nor should it be. As mentioned earlier, it is very important that the analysis and its output are theoretically coherent and consistent with the research questions and aligned approaches actively decided on by the researcher. Furthermore, the key to reflexive TA is that the researcher maintains a “critical lens” on themselves, thus they must be critically aware of the relationship of who they are as researchers and their research questions and theoretical choices. The reflective TA orientations adopted in this study:

- I. *Inductive as* although the analysis influenced by frameworks of supervision such as (Lee, 2007) (Lee, 2019) and (Gatfield 2005) , they do not impose and explicit coding frame (deductive).
- II. *Semantic* at the theme and coding development stage, although at the interpretation stage, I attempt to theorize the significance of patterns and their broader meanings and implications in relation to the scholarship of research supervision.
- III. *Critical realist* - this is the most appropriate stance given the amount of time and data samples available. I argue that one focus group is insufficient time and social interactions to construct a common shared meaning around remote supervision. Also I believe interesting insights and contrasting themes from individual participants could be lost if a *constructivist approach* were taken.

The researcher should proceed to engage in **six phases** of reflexive Thematic Analysis developed by Braun and Clarke (2006), once they have reached a decision concerning their particular approach to TA (as described above)

3.4.2 Six Phases of Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Phases 1: Familiarization

First and foremost the research must get to know their data or “immerse” themselves in order to get a thorough overview of the data. This involves reading through the dataset once prior to commencing coding, making notes and actively searching for initial hints of codes and potential patterns. This stage also involves transcribing the data; in this case the audio recording of the focus group on remote supervision. In the context of this research the transcription of the audio recording has been generated from Zoom via the Otter.AI service. However, despite advances in Artificial Intelligence driven speech-to-text tools, these services can be error prone and so the text must be verified manually against the audio recording and corrected for errors. The transcription provided in this thesis is minimal in that it provides an “orthographical verbatim account of all verbal utterances” (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Step 2: Coding

After the researcher has familiarised herself/himself with the data and notes any ideas, he/she should proceed to producing the initial codes from the data. Coding involves i) highlighting sections or text chunks from the data (usually phrases or sentences) and then ii) assigning simple labels or “codes” to describe the meaning of their content.

The example extract below is in part adapted from Caulfield (2020), which is based on interview data collected from conservative voters aged 50 and up about their perceptions of climate change

Coding qualitative data

Interview extract

Personally, I'm not sure. I think the climate is changing, I can't explain why or how. They say you should trust the experts, but who's to say they don't have their agenda? I'm not saying they're wrong, I'm just saying there's reasons to be sceptical of them. Scientists keep chopping and changing their facts – it used to be called global warming

Codes

- Uncertainty
- Acknowledgement of climate change
- Distrust of experts
- Changing terminology

Figure 3.1. Example of coding an interview extract.
The above is a modification of (Caulfield 2020)

In this extract, we've highlighted various phrases in different colours corresponding to different codes. Each code above describes the patterned idea or feeling expressed in that part of the text. In fact a code is the most basic unit (semantic unit in this case) of the raw data that can be assessed in meaningful way (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It is important to pay equal attention to each individual piece of data (data item). The researcher should code frequently, comprehensively, systematically and inclusively (keeping surrounding context). Codes can change and be refined, broken up and evolve. The process is flexible and organic. The researcher should conduct a few coding sweeps. The data should be at the end of this stage collated into groups of identified codes (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Phase 3: Generating for themes

Next the researcher inspects the codes created and collated in Step 2. He/she begins to sort the code into potential themes, which are patterns of meaning, which are distinctive yet, part of a whole (Braun and Clarke, 2018). In addition the researcher organises the collated coded extracts under themes. Codes may combine to form an overarching theme and visual aids such as tables, mind maps or hierarchical theme maps (Braun and Clarke, 2006) can support this process. Some initial codes may form core themes, others may form sub-themes or alternatively they may be discarded (Braun and Clarke, 2006) .

In Figure 3.1 (which is in part based on (Caulfield 2020)), one might combine codes into themes such as the following.

Turning codes into themes

Codes	Theme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty • Let experts decide • Alternative explanations 	Uncertainty
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing terminology • Distrust of scientists • Resentment toward experts • Fear of government control 	Distrust of experts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorrect facts • Misunderstanding of science • Biased media sources 	Misinformation

Figure 3.2 : Example of grouping code into themes. The above is a modification of (Caulfield 2020).

At this stage we are only concerned with developing a collection candidate themes and subthemes for review (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Indeed as advised in Braun and Clarke,(2018) certain candidate themes may not hold, may need to be refined, combined, separated or even discarded. The researcher should reflect on the relationship between themes and subthemes.

Phase 4: Reviewing themes

In this phase, the researcher conducts a review and refinement phases. The researcher asks whether to this theme is good? Is it rich? Does it say more than one thing? Are we missing anything? Are these themes really present in the data? What can we change to make our themes work better? What is the quality of this theme? What are the boundaries for this

theme? Again this stage may involve, splitting themes, combining themes, discarding themes.

For example, the data that “changing terminology” may fit better under the “uncertainty” theme rather than “distrust of experts,” since the data extract could be labelled with code *confusion*, not necessarily *Distrust of Experts*.

Finally, It is important to stay close to your data extracts but at the same time be willing to take a step back to take a broader view of the data. Ultimately, the researcher produces a final thematic map and a final list of themes.

Phase 5: Defining and naming themes

This involves thinking through the nuances specific to the themes identified; what are they are about? What is each theme specifically about? What is of interest about them and why? It should capture the key idea of what a theme is about? This might involve writing a mini-abstract of the theme to clarify its key idea and boundaries. In doing so this allows the researcher to produce a precise, “punchy” and easily understandable name for a theme.

In Figure 3.2 (which is in part based on (Caulfield, 2021) provided earlier “distrust of experts” could be better named for the theme is “distrust of authority” or “conspiracy thinking” based on broader analysis of code extracts related to this theme (Braun and Clarke, 2006;

Phase 6: Producing the report

This involves delivering an analytic commentary, describing each theme as well as illustrative data extracts. The researcher should finalise the order of the themes and select vivid and compelling examples and in addition the commentary should critically link and engage with the literature and also refer back to our research questions.

For the examples provided earlier, the report could argue that conspiracy thinking about climate change is more common among working class voters (Caulfield, 2021). The report might discuss the role of fake news plays in influencing the respondents’ perceptions. This should be supported by critical engagement with the literature.

3.5 Summary

In this chapter, I have described the overall research methodology starting with its theoretical, ontological and epistemological positioning in Section 3.1. I then described in detail the research methods corresponding to this positioning which involved i) recruiting academics the Department of Computing, DCU to participate in a focus group on the topic of remote supervision (Section 3.2 for the purpose of gathering data to conduct reflexive thematic analysis (Section 3.4 and 3.5). In addition, I have provided a detailed overview any ethical issues encountered in the design and execution of this methodology (Section 3.3). In the next chapter, I report on reflexive thematic analysis of the data generated from the focus group and interpret the results.

Chapter 4: Reflexive Thematic Analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of reflexive thematic analysis applied to data derived from the focus group described in Section 3.2.1. Recall, that the theoretical orientation for of this thematic analysis is *inductive, semantic and critical realist* (See Section 3.4). Section 4.1 presents a thematic map of which provides and overview of our results, while Section 4.2 provides a detailed analysis and illustrative narrative for each theme (sub theme and code). Finally Section 4.3 offers summary critical analysis of each theme and how they interrelate while also engaging with the relevant literature.

4.1 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

- In this section we provide detailed descriptions for each theme derived in our analysis. Figure 4.1 below provides a thematic map, which shows the **five** main themes developed from our analysis of supervisors' experiences (at the School of Computing DCU) of conducting remote supervision during the Covid-19 pandemic during the period beginning from the emergency move to teaching online in Semester 1 March 2020 until Semester 1 February 2021. The **five** themes are: *Concepts of Remote Supervision, Student-Wellbeing & Performance, Supervisor Wellbeing, Modalities of Research Supervision-Pros & Cons, Research Supervision Styles and Research Environment*

THEME

SUBTHEME

CODE

Figure 4.1: Thematic Map of Research Supervisors' Experiences of Remote Supervision

4.2 Descriptive Analysis of Themes

The following sections below provide shorted description of each theme, illustrated with excerpts from the data. The complete descriptions and analyses for each theme are available for inspection in Appendix G.

4.2.1 Theme: Concepts of Remote Supervision

Theme Name: Concepts of Remote Supervision

Description: This theme refers to the insights gleamed from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concepts of Supervision (2019) (Section 2.1 and how they translated to remote research supervision.

SubThemes: Research Enculturation, Critical Skills, Student-Supervisor Relationship, Structured-Functional, Emancipation

SubTheme Name: Research Enculturation

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleamed from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of research **Enculturation** (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision.

Codes: *serendipity-spontaneity, conference-attendance-networking, research-placement-internship, online-group-meetings, physical-lab-experience, peer-support/peer-le, career-development*

Code: : serendipity-spontaneity

This code is concerned with what supervisors experience as the absences of chance (office door, water cooler), serendipitous or spontaneous meetings with students and which are common when conducting campus based research and supervision. Examples from participants include:

"often rely on kind of chance you know chance ad hoc interactions"

"students knew they had to give a quick update on what they've been doing"

"a chance for them to grab me if they had those quick questions"

students were able to reach "out for whatever problem",

"spontaneous chats like in the hallwayI find would more important for like the building up a rapport with the student"

"you would have been sparking ideas, and I would have pulled that pieces of paper and coloured pens,"

"maybe just discuss about some new technique"

Code: conference-attendance-networking

This code is concerned with the loss of physical conference attendance (as a result of Covid) and networking as part of research enculturation of research students.

One supervisor mentioned that as a result of Covid-19 restrictions "conference travel" is not happening at the moment and I think "that is affecting PhD students," especially those who are just finishing up"

Although students can attend conference online the supervisor argues that they are not the equivalent.

"they're going to conferences online and the networking opportunities just aren't the same there".

Regardless of Covid-19 for the remote student to be properly enculturated he/she would benefit from attending conferences physically at the same time as their supervisor to avail of introductions and networking opportunities.

Code: group-meetings.

This code is concerned with the discussions arising about how to organise online video conference group with research students in order to facilitate research enculturation. Negative experiences of supervisors include:

"the group meeting is moved to fortnightly because we found people just finding it to much in the group meeting"

and

"we've got it online we've had to move it to be fairly structured because we just found people weren't coming and you can't do that ourselves and kind of grabbing free at the door, we lost that."

With respect conducting group meetings to practice presentation talks and discuss the methodologies and technologies, the same supervisor found that:

"attendance really dropped off, so we said it's too hard to keep up with everybody else's stuff and they found it really annoying and boring"

Another supervisor modified their group meeting structure in response to a student's feedback Which i.e. "one of my students and I really appreciate itYou know that it was just too hard to

concentrate for that long, and we should just do status updatesthen leave the discussion to the end,which is something that we never did in the face to face”.

“they were kind of waiting for their turn,they ended up just not like it wasn't very pleasant experience.... having to wait like an hour”.

Another supervisor agreed i.e. I think you're right ...there is a bit of a i'm waiting for my turn that's the only time I have to be doing stuff and then the camera goes off.....”

The supervisor’s experience of online group meetings was positive for managing research student cohorts online i.e. “I have seven students and some of them are supervised and they still attend the meetings actually” The supervisor also indicated that the group meeting fostered collaboration between students i.e. one to one meetings between my students and that might not have happened if it wasn't for that:

Another senior academic described how they “have a weekly group meeting which is far more relaxed, we can have a journal club , more often than not breaks downthings go different directions right and everyone has a cup of tea”.

The supervisor does not attend the group meeting every second week as this meeting is facilitated by a senior PhD who is a mature student and is “brilliant ... she's just really organized very social very smart and she's kind of created the energy in that group”.

The outcome of this discussion is that enculturation of research students could be facilitated well by allowing senior researcher students/postdoctoral research to organise a less formal research group (See theme: Modalities of Supervision under *online-interaction* for a related discussion).

The academics in the group recognised the value of this i.e. it's a good idea, I think I might try something similar...” but that it was “critical is, as you say you can really switched on senior PhD or a postdoc who can help who's not the professor.

Code: lab-experience-physical-lab-placement

The code is concerned with the overall importance of the physical lab experience and its role in the research enculturation of the postgraduate student and how is this is missing in remote supervision. It links closely the theme of **Research Infrastructure** (access-to-lab).

One supervisor felt “ he **lab experience is too ...important to be removed**, out of the PhD and it can be feasible for some short period, but it shouldn't be the normal way”

Another agreed the stating the loss of the ability of the research student being able to observe and model off the supervisor as well as senior colleagues/PhDs and socialise with colleagues as a result of distance learning at the postgraduate research level.

I'd agree with that, I think we've talked about the lack of spontaneity and that kind of **serendipitous discoveries at the coffee machine** or over lunch or then that's **where that enculturation** stuff, I think, not just **from observing your supervisor**, but also from **discussing stuff with your peers or gaining experience from ones** who are.., a year or two ahead of you....if we were **to move to solely remote supervision**, **apprenticeship/enculturation would** be more difficult,

One supervisor felt that enculturation was not possible online:

I think the **enculturation point is totally missing in zoom** , like, I **cannot see any way that you can do this kind of role modelling apprenticeship.**

As a workaround some supervisors place the remote student in a laboratory (and even earn credits) where they have existing collaborations, which appears to be a useful solution to fostering enculturation :

“any of **my students that are abroad**... I've **put them in other universities labs abroad**..”

“just find some **university advisor right, ... an internship there....get some credits**”

“just stick her in some lab nearby”

Code: peer-support-peer-led

This code captures supervisors discussions around the impact of conducting postgraduate research students remotely on peer support in the context of research enculturation.

One supervisor comments how the benefits of a face to face research group meeting and how it fostered peer support.

The supervisor “...set up the group **meeting because one of my other students will be able to**

answer their questions, better than I could, because there will be ... something related to an experimental detail that I just couldn't I couldn't help them

The supervisor described the benefits of continuing group supervision online because:

“for the students... to help each other, and I think that's particularly important am at the moment because we're not seeing each other..... that's been really helpful so used to be obviously face to face but and we kept it going and i'm really glad that we that we just”

One supervisor agreed in the context of online research group that was peer-led and or led by a senior PhD Researcher and has not generated peer support activities:

“So that seems to work and then I also encourage them now to meet in pairs and I don't force it I just have encouraged thattry and take away from spoke model, so you don't need to come to me to talk to her.

SubTheme Name: Student-Supervisor Relationship

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of Relationship (2019) ((See Section 2.2.1))and how it translates to remote research supervision. The subtheme is with the challenges surrounding boundaries and the rapport between student and supervisor and the effect of the lack-of physical context on their student supervisor relationship

Codes: *rapport-relationship, boundaries-of-supervision, lack-of-physical-context*

Code: rapport-relationship

Description: This code is captures the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to the impact of remote supervision on their relationship or rapport with students.

Supervisors in general feel something is missing:

“because you don't have that personal interaction that feels like and everything has to be very formally done and discussed in the meeting it's just lacking”

“I feel a little bit disconnected”

“but I feel like there's something missing out”

They also find it strange that there are some students that they have never met and do not have

“some level of personal knowledge about the student”. They find it a

“It can be a bit strange”

“....that I never met so it's weird.”

One supervisor misses not being “able to have a few minutes, with a student each day” as was the case with campus based supervision.

Another supervisor felt that the relationship had become directorial and task orientated:

“less of a conversation like you'd have one, you know you're walking over to coffee and a lot more about here, where the tasks last week”

One supervisor states that remote supervision demands being more involved in the supervisee's issues regardless of whether the supervisor is comfortable or not with the situation.

“You know that may mean that you have to listen to them for a bit talking about whatever problem they may have”

“I think that's part and parcel of where we are now it's it's it's something I would prefer not to get involved in...”

This links into the code *boundaries-of-supervision* .

One supervisor is able to compensate for this by sharing mobile contact details with students which helps to foster *sponteniety-serenditpy* in the relationship.

“They ring me anytime and that's how we've kind of evolved to working but, and that gives us that spontaneity “

Code: boundaries –of-supervision

Description: This code captures the uncertainty created for supervisors by remote supervision in relation to the what are the appropriate boundaries of supervision. Supervisors are for example unsure how to manage the blurring of boundaries in the supervision relationship as result of supervising online and demanded to act as institutional gatekeepers for student wellbeing and moving what they feel is beyond their role of academic supervisor:

“The the level of separation between you, as a supervisor and the students has changed I know there's there's discussions about how much a supervisor should be you know ..be knowledgeable or be invested or involved in your your students life outside of the PhD”

“Others say that you, you should be on kind of dinner conversation level with your students”

“I've had to deal with stuff over the last year, which has really been quite personal knowledge for some of my studentsbervements to deal with Covidwho've had all this stuff

One supervisor expressed concern as to being unsure as to what was expected of them formally

“this wasn't my role, I was just meant to be helping you get through this (PhD Programme)

“Should it be should not be?”

Another supervisor made valid point the in some situations regardless of the supervisor preference that some involvement in non-PhD issues are unavoidable:

“I don't really know... have an answer to what like how much you should get involved in that or whether we you find out these things and kind of ARE involved”.

Code: loss-of-physical-context

Description

This code captures supervisors’ explicit frustrations cause by the lack physical contextual information as result of remote supervision and how this impacts the supervision relationship. For example many supervisor discussed their concerns for student health and theirs inability to assess the situation remotely.

“I have no other insights other than seeing an email to in the morning to judgment call on their sleeping patterns”

when you're working remotely you don't have the usual physical cues

While with campus based supervision:

“You can just get a sense of what's going on from the everyday” interactions in the lab.

“all those cues are gonethe ecological.... the context for your everyday is gone”

“and just as a lot, I cant see if I only have zoom and”

“you know what id be expecting to see (the student) every day and just be able to monitor the situation in some way, “

SubTheme Name: Critical Skills

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleamed from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee’s Concept of Critical Skills (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision.

Codes: *discussion-feedback, brainstorming-critical-thinking*

Code: *discussion-feedback*

Description: This code is with the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to providing feedback for example:

“tried to do is to have them, for example, to write down things, because then I can keep on that some **feedback but it's much more limited**”

Another supervisor commented:

“i've **given my answer back and then the following week** you find that they've **completely misunderstood you**.... i'm **finding this a lot projects**”

There was a general consensus that is was difficult to have discussions with students online i.e.

“think everyone's exactly right **it's it's just really hard to to have discussions on zoom** as as we're discovering it in this focus group right”

“there is less opportunity for talking actually out new things”

“Just that **doesn't happen**, **it becomes very much I can what have you done last week, what are you gonna do next week, so the critical discussion and critical issues is just not prioritized** in in that kind of a time slot that we have so **that's that's particularly tough**”

Code: *brainstorming-critical-thinking*

Description: This code is captures the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to effectively conceptualising and brainstorming about a research problem with a student online (as form of critical thinking) contrast to face to face supervision. For example “**is more critical thinking like brainstorming and find zoom terrible like I am struggling so** much”

“i **would love to have a whiteboard I know there is a (virtual) whiteboard but it's just brutal like it doesn't work**, I found the same thing with my masters students sometimes they lack some knowledge, so I tried to explain it **and just doesn't work like** you need some support

That is just frustrating.

Another supervisor mentioned in relation to trying different devices for brainstorming with little success:

“i've tried, a **number of different devices have a one of these pen things** that goes on a pad but

“again it's : clunky difficult to write with and frustrating actually”

Again this was supported by the supervisor who commented at the beginning above in that they felt unable to “to helpstudents to scope out things like you know, to have them reasoning like when they're hitting a wall it's very hard to have them navigate possible solutions, soeverything must go through some sort of (online) structure.

SubTheme Name: *Functional-Structured*

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of Functional supervision (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision. The subtheme is concerned with the experiences of supervisors with having to apply more structures to their supervision style as result of the move to online/remote supervision.

Codes: structured-planning, meeting-minutes-note-taking

Code: *structured-planning*

Description: This code captures supervisors experience of applying more structures and project planning to their supervision style as result of move to remote supervision.

Supervisors discussed how they had been applying more structures and using synchronous online collaborative documents(Google Docs), project dashboards to track progress, and scheduled Zoom (video conferencing meeting)

“I think it sounds like we're all doing someGoogle Doc..”

For some supervisors, research activities are broken down into tasks.

“like a task that might be something likelook into approaches for this or find.....very much as tasks, you know, read the paper least, learn these technologies”

One supervisor maintained that more structure was a side effect of remote supervision:

“So if they're not actually seeing them on a day to day basismeans that you have to have ...more slight more hands on approach when it comes to actually supervising”

One supervisor commented on how the organic experience of the PhD was not becoming too project managed as a result of supervision and so this a negative:

....like an organic spread them where they come back to you with their own ideas to do their own research, now I feel like having that as like an itemized task - it feels like it's lending more towards project manager, even the students' research and getting up to speed or reading the

papers”.

Finally, one supervisor commented that although supervisors could be more structured it did not automatically mean that they need to be directorial or task orientated. Hence the creation of this code in contrast to *deliberate-directorial* under the theme of **Supervision-Styles** i.e.

“Moving to that **high structure in terms of meetings doesn't change or necessarily change your style** of supervision”

Another supervisor confirmed this:

“It shouldn't affect my it **doesn't change my personality now for sure** yeah. “

Code: meeting-minutes-note-taking

Description: This code captures supervisors' experience of encouraging students to take efficient notes in order to reduce cognitive overload. Students are often asked by supervisors to use a collaborative document editor such as Google docs to:

“**leave a comment...., but I make a point that they shouldn't be long,**

“**wrap it up a...100 words it's a quick stream of consciousness,** just that we have **some continuity** as we're going along “

“so I'm trying to encourage them to even if **it's just three points that we discussed actions** they are **going to take**”

Another supervisor mentioned that this approach

“**is a lifesaver to know what we discussed last time just even to jog or memories** and bring us back on to the same points”

Other tools are discussed such as used software code repositories (gitlab) or hyperlinks to Google Slides i.e.

“I have this co student and she's using git lab and **doing a magnificent job of having this wonderful rolling set of notes**”

“use **Google slides so that means that I've got a link that I go to for meetings,** I can see, they put their **results in they've got bullet points as to what they're working on**”.

Code: Emancipation

Description: This code refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of Emancipation (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision. There is little data on this concept hence it does not warrant the level of a subtheme.

Supervisors are not too concerned with the emancipation would supported by the distance but also supported by being part of an online research group (enculturation):

"I mean it could be easier to be emancipated if it's all remote"

"I'd say the emancipation, supported by the enculturation and being part of a group"

Another supervisor demonstrated concerns that current students may not fully understand the nature of the PhD in that it requires research independence and the ability to think creatively i.e.:

The supervisor felt that the existing group was a "cohort of students who have not really learned in my view, what the doctorate is"

The supervisor felt that "students should have that sort of imagination side of things I'm a little bit concerned might be stifling that a little"

4.2.2 Theme: Student-Wellbeing-performance

Theme Name: *Student-Wellbeing-performance*

Description: This theme refers to impact of conducting remote research and learning on student wellbeing in terms of mental health (isolation experienced by students), the progress of students in relation to their studies and their overall experience.

Codes: *student-mental-health, student-progress, student-isolation*

Code: : *student-mental-health,*

Description: This code captures the effect of distance learning on student mental health *from the perspective of the supervisor*. For instance one supervisor states in relation to students in the final year of their research degree i.e. one or two of them are writing up they've just shut themselves off, and you can see the the the impact on their mental health. The supervisor wonders if there is "psychological damage to overdoing the online presence". However as the same time the participant commented that perhaps "we over estimating the impact on students who are more savy on social media- are far more used to the principle of connecting online" and "this a terrible situation are we just making something a little worse than it actually is, "...

So there may be different perceptions across different generations (See *code:online-interaction*).

Another supervisor describes the concerns raised by a student's parents i.e. his parents were **actually quite worried about** him and they wanted him to leave Ireland". On a positive note the student organised an internship in the home country which the supervisor felt **"was a really good idea"** and **"when that happened like there's just no question that and I wasn't going to dissuade him from going"**

"he's still in COUNTRY and meeting him once a fortnight and it's going fine and i'm really, really glad that he left ..."

Many of the participants raised the problem of being unable to assess the mental health of the postgraduate within a remote context which would not be in issue in physical context and cues (links to *code: to loss-of-physical-context*) i.e. "

"I find that this disconnect makes it very difficult like I don't know when I land into a zoom meeting and I haven't seen the students in the week I don't have any context about their their mental state, things I would have noticed as well in the past, like if you notice that the studentvery consistently turning off at their desk at nine o'clock.....and I also don't know in the way that to present themselves, maybe they're putting on their happy SMILEY face"

It is also difficult for supervisors to know or assess when **"you should be intervening or not, when all you have is" the student "putting on a good face"**.

Code: : student-performance

Description: This code captures the effect of distance learning on student performance from the perspective of the supervisor. There was some concern on the progress of students raised for instance one supervisor felt **"I suppose it's slowing things up a little bit.....you're concerned about the progress"** and that students have a **"tendency if they don't see you in the office to actually forget that they have to try and push themselves a little further forward.** The supervisor argued with on campus supervision **"if they if they see you every day they feel they should do something"** while with remote supervision the supervisor felt **"if you don't meet them regularly.... that can be that gap between the supervision and their response"**. In addition the supervisor mentioned that in one case that it was stressful for one student to make progress **"persevere we're trying to get his work done** and get across the line, so you can get back to back home to see his family... its tough **....spent a month in isolation** in a small apartment.

Another supervisor commented how it very difficult assess the students progress when supervising remotely on the students may “go through the motions but Im not sure what's going on it on in between, and I suspect there's problems”

Code: : *student-supervisor-isolation*

Description: This code capture the experience of isolation from result research postgraduates (and in some cases supervisors) engaged in distance learning *from the perspective of the supervisor*. Although it links heavily with *student-mental-health*, we assign the topic a separate code as it is quite prominent.

One supervisor’s perspective on student isolation was that students are “ really suffering” and “that student earlierwas really suffering right loneliness was the big issue right....”

“the loneliness thing I fully agree” as confirmed

With respect to the supervisor’s experience of supervision one supervisor felt “ there's a bit more of a of a disconnect” and in some cases that there is “incredibly low support and (we are) not meeting them at all”

Many supervisors found it strange that they have not physically ever met some of their supervisees

“one i've never ever met in person he moved to Dublin”

“other (supervisors) got students they've they've never actually met.

This is less of a concern about students with whom the supervisor has had an existing campus based supervisor-supervisee relationship, whereby remote supervision in this context has had less of a negative effect i.e.

“the others are ones that i've had two or three years for them to get to know my style ...do people feel that's made a difference”

4.2.3 Theme: Supervisor Wellbeing

Theme Name: *Supervisor Wellbeing*

Description: This theme refers to impact of remote supervision on supervisor wellbeing in terms of general confidence, the effect of workload on wellbeing. It also attempts to capture burdens on the

supervisor as a result of remote supervision.

Codes: *supervisor-confidence-motivation, supervisor workload-burden,*

Code: *supervisor- confidence-motivation*

Description: This code captures the effect of remote supervision on supervisor confidence and motivation. For instance one supervisor felt uncomfortable and unsure with having to advice students and whether or not to travel to Ireland or on topic, which they felt, was outside their remit. Although this was a direct result of Covid this could have broader implications with respect to remote supervision and expectations from supervisors i.e. "I **found weird I** am having to give students advice on stuff like this **and I am like I don't know.** Should I shouldn't come to Ireland and, ...I don't want to encourage you to travel when maybe it's going to be a problem and, but if I don't encourage you to travel now, you might have to pay for me to quarantine in three weeks time"

The same supervisor expressed concerns about whether remote supervision would become more mainstream i.e. is it **the new norm, which we are going to have** PhDs and master's students online. As results for the move to online/remote supervision the supervisor "made **a conscious effort to say I'm backing off** with the number of students are going to have during this whole (online) process" and also "**could have taken on more students**" but had felt unsure i.e. "because I'm **a little bit nervous**"

Code: *supervisor workload-burden*

Description: In this context, refers to discussions around the challenges related to postgraduate supervision workload i.e. the number of postgraduate (taught and research) students they are required to manage i.e. "you have so many projects going on" "**20 people I mean every day and I don't know what I've said to**".

In addition this code captures the burden on supervisors' wellbeing created by both existing workload and the impact of remote supervision with respect to i) no having enough time i.e. **haven't got time to** meet all seven of them in the week, which does happen" ii) meeting students at unusual times i.e. one supervision mentions meetings in **weird times which I wouldn't normally not do....Like very late, maybe quite early**" and another supervisor "when I was meeting her(the student) at that point, it **was it was late in the day for me**", which is a result of time zone differences.

On supervisor raises concerns around their own wellbeing in relation to workload i.e. "I'm finding all

of it **bit of a struggle**” and another raising the negative effects on all parties of continuous video conferencing for conducting remote supervision i.e. kind of given them ...**open ended zoom slots.**
....just really conscious of zoom's tiring”

4.2.4 Theme: Modalities of Supervision (Pros and Cons)

Theme Name: Modalities of Supervision (Pros and Cons)

Description: This theme refers to the observations arising in the data in relation to the various modalities and types of research supervision i.e. face to face of campus based supervision, remote and or distance supervision typically 100% online as well as a mix of both (blended). It also includes co-supervision as form of remote supervision which maybe cross-institutional and supervision of part-time students.

Codes: *blended delivery, online- interaction, face-to-face, remote-co-supervision, part-time-phd*

Code: *online-interaction.*

Description and Analysis:

The discussions associated with this code centred around online interaction as a form of supervision. There have been positive experiences with respect to synchronously communicating with students via chat often using a tool call Slack i.e. “ I love the fact that some of your having **you know conversations between students and slack**” and “they just chat with each other and they used to it and that for them is the same as meeting at the water cooler”. This is usually in the context of research group interaction or supervision of research groups remotely. Other experiences have been negative where a supervisor offers students to “**contact me on Skype we have a slack** but sometimes you just don't seem to bring up issues until the next meeting” and the students will “drop things into the **slack** but one or two PhDs I co supervise they wont are waiting” until the next video meeting. Other supervisor also agreed the students may be “scared” to reach out online resulting in little interaction i.e. “we didn't **have that much interaction**”.

Supervisors also mentioned the impact of different time zones and technical difficulties encountered when interacting online. Examples included “**connection is not working....terrible**” and the output on the screen “**hanging heavy over the keyboard** having **some technical difficulty**”:

Finally some supervisors indicated the issue may be with them and for “Digitally native” younger

students socialising and working online may be quite normal in that “ they are attracted - that's how that is increasingly **how they interact in the way, independent of covid**” and “ for **digital natives**” remote supervision and online interaction “is **nothing that unusual**”. Supervisors agreed that it may be the case that they are “seeing the world through the lens” of their “**own (online) experiences**” and that they should not “**overplay ...the role of Zoom**”

Code: *blended-delivery.*

Description and Analysis:

The justification for this code as it does highly the issue of attempting to replicate the conditions the research environment (particular in the context of Covid) where the university wishes to have research students partly based on campus (blended) and remotely. However this naturally could generalise to blended postgraduate research programmes (post-Covid) The universities “**week on week off traffic light system**” presents challenges in that you “can't then have the **same setup in both places**, because **you can't move stuff back and forth**”. For example one supervisor described how one student “took his (computer) tower home on the bus last March, because he knew that there was going to be **issues withtrying to ...manage it remotely**. But that means if he **wants to be week on week off what's he supposed to do.....** carries his kit (desktop computer) back and forth every other week”. Hence a blended research programme would need to factor in

Code: *face-to-face interaction.*

Description and Analysis:

This code captures some of the practical difficulties supervisors are experiencing as result of the absence face-to-face interaction as a by-product of remote supervision. For example “problems that they have at the end of the week.... could have been resolved throughout the week” if a student had dropped into to their supervisor’s office briefly. “**You gotta be at the door and quickly solve the problem, so we lost that completely**” Online interaction appears to inhibit the approachability of the supervision and supervisors experience this as a loss i.e. **missing** that type of **... day to day interaction** just a **three four or five minute conversation**, how are you getting on?” One supervisor indicated that face to face meetings despite their length were “**absolutely fine**” and “**energizing**”.

Code: *remote-co-supervision*

Description and Analysis:

Although mentioned briefly, this code is included provides interesting insights into the benefits of remote cross site co-supervision whereby it is “actually a really great foundation for **our future supervisions**, because we've got this understanding of how to **supervise remotely**”. Another supervisor mentions that in their co-supervision arrangement that they “have the **same experience** actually” and “it **makes no difference at** all, like I have kind of forgotten that the supervisor is in another university”. The first supervisor mentions some minor concern about how the dynamic may change once on-campus study resumes i.e. “because **we're all interacting in the same way**, so it's going to be **interesting to see** when we hopefully return to regularly scheduled programming” and “where potentially there'll be one dialled in to a weekly meeting or I'll be the one dialling into a weekly meeting and **we won't be equal anymore** will it change?” There is a hint here from the supervisor that the power dynamic may be change in perhaps a negative way but this is speculative, requiring more research.

Code: *part-time-phd*

Description and Analysis:

Although mentioned briefly, this code is included provides interesting insights into the quite strong negative perceptions of two supervisors of part time doctoral supervision (face-to-face or remotely) i.e. I feel a little bit like **part time PhDs in computinghugely risky**... even in four years, some of the stuff that my (full-time) guys are doing is out of date”. Another supervisor strongly agreed in that “**part time PHDs are a nightmare!**I **don't entertain them at all, so I kind of zoned out** to everybody, **part time PHD** and I don't know I've done it before I took nine years - **never fuckin again not me**”. Both supervisors agreed the a part time PhD was manageable if the research topic was fundamental .i.e. “the **only way to do it is you** have to **pick a topic that's absolutely fundamental**.... **no way you'll** do can have any applied computing science right or AIsomething deeply mathematical”

4.2.5 Theme: Supervision Styles

Theme Name: Supervision Styles

Description: This theme refers to impact of remote supervision with respect to different supervision management styles. The codes are in part influenced by Gatfield's (2005) supervision management grid. Management styles include i) a deliberate or directorial style ii) a more apprenticeship/pastoral style. In addition, this theme explores the impact of remote supervision on the flexibility of supervision delivery and on supervisor capacity to switch supervision styles (Gatfield ,2005) dynamically throughout the course of the student's PhD.

Codes: *apprenticeship-style, directorial-deliberate, dynamic-flexible-supervision*

Code: *apprenticeship-style*

Description and Analysis:

This code captures the concept of an apprenticeship/mentor/coach/pastoral style model to supervision. I also subsumes under it the *laisser-faire and pastoral styles or low structure and low direction* forms of research supervision (Gatfield ,2005). The code is mentioned typically when supervisors are discussing the supervision style prior to the emergency move to online/remote supervision. Typically with respect to traditional face to face supervision, academics were sometimes *laisser-faire* “relying on **ad hoc** relying on all these (face to face) interactions for just figuring stuff out, which is life, you know that's **improvisational** thing” “or a lot on kind of **winging it**”.

. Prior to the move to remote supervision the some supervisors’ expectations of the postgraduate researcher “was to go from undergrad to completely ...**sink or swim - you know Sparta**you know surviving is - it can be shocking”. So students were expected to adhere to the traditional apprenticeship style model be highly motivated, take initiative and work independently. Supervisors do not view themselves as line managers or directorial but a mentor/coach i.e. “we'll call it a **pastoral model** to some degree right,” and “you've signed up to do a marathonand I’m **your coach not your boss** right”.

Codes: *directorial-deliberate*

Description and Analysis:

This code captures the experience that supervisors are becoming more deliberate and even directorial in the communications and tasks setting since the move to remote supervising . For instance one supervisor will now “ **cut to the chase** I had to be **way more deliberate** and ain't that if I just say it” and while another commented “I do find that, as I said, it is 100% **more deliberate**”. Another example of the change in student-supervisor interaction with respect to verbal communication “like I’d probably change up the way I speak a little better.....might start asking them probing questions. Another example is the need to be deliberate with respect to the time allotted for a supervision meeting i.e. even the conversation that we have now is **very much project and a targeted thing** because, unfortunately, what I can see it's very much that that is **my hour**, so we need **to get as much into that** as possible”.

Another example of directorial where a supervisor tries to enforce structure on remote working hours with research students i.e. like I've **given out to** one or two students before when I'd see like you know they send an email at two in the morning and giving them a **good bit of a talk on** burnout and how **you need to get off** that now.”.

Codes: *dynamic-flexible-supervision*

Description and Analysis:

This code describes the overall impact on the flexibility expected from supervisors as well any barriers raised by remote supervision to the supervisor's ability to adapt supervision management styles to the student's needs. In the context remote supervision can mean an increase in flexibility for both the supervisor and student. Working online does offer advantages to the supervisor with respect to an increase of communication options i.e. I think there is much more **flexibility**” and “ I have a student, for example, **that has children so for her it's actually easier, sometimes to zoom to organize a quick meeting ...just out of the blue.** However, this may depend at what stage the student is in their PhD “but she's **also a fourth year student.** ...assume she's **more willing,** you know, **to reach out to me at every time** Like she she reached out via **whatsapp whatsoever,** **I think, for first year student will be much different”.**

However this may mean the supervisor is required to organise a supervision session outside regular hours if a student has to “set **up a shift** with her husband” “is working a night” , the supervisor will need **to fix**” a particular supervision late night slot.

Regardless of their experiences either (positive or negative) supervisors also feel strongly that remote supervision should **not be “the standard ...the normal way of operating... not for a PhD.**

Interestingly, another supervisor felt that imposing structures did not necessarily lead to a more deliberate or directorial supervision style in that “the (supervision) meeting that **the naturehasn't changed** in that way” . A supervisor “can have this meeting that happens **regularly** but **within the meeting** you **don't have to become like hardcore project manager**”. The supervisor is “**not really straight jacketed**” by Zoom and that it that it does “**not necessarily change your supervisory style**” and that it was “still very possible to have that sort **of pastoral approach**” with a series of structured meeting.

This above also resulted in the need to distinguish between the *deliberate*-directorial supervision style and the concept of *functional-structured* (Theme: Concepts of Supervision) supervision, which

was not necessarily directive when generating codes.

4.2.5 Theme: Research Environment

Theme Name: Research Environment

Description: This theme refers to challenges, which arise in remote research supervision within the context of accessing the research environment – physical and/or virtual. It may be the campus access to the research centre/university environment including, the research lab space, desk space, learning space, seminar rooms as well as equipment in computer labs, labs for electronic engineering, science lab for experiments. It may include remote access to servers and datasets or take home access to hardware or materials, data or equipment that would otherwise normally reside on (in) campus. This theme also refers to challenges and issues surrounding institutional support for supervisors and research students as well as legal-finance challenges that may be inadvertently caused by the move remote supervision/research study.

Codes: *access-to-materials-data, access-to-lab-equipment, home-access-to-equipment, legal-financial-issues, student-learning-space*

Code: access-to-materials-data

Description and Analysis: This code concerned with the challenges surrounding access large datasets and or data critical for experiments. It may apply to other research materials i.e chemicals. Some students /supervisors going to “enormous negotiations” with a third party collaborator and are required to sign a non disclosure agreement and evidence that the data stored securely off campus “we could sign a contract saying that we made every effort to ensure not only was this dataset not stored on Internet cable computer, but it was physically prevented from being accessed”. “ we ended up actually purchasing this guy's safe, which is presumably under his bed”. Sensitive third party data access would not be an issue with campus based research and supervision the data would under physically restricted access” and it “wouldn't be a problem”.

Code: access-to-lab-equipment

Description and Analysis:

This code concerned with the challenges surrounding research students gaining access to the research lab on campus. This is usually in the context of gaining access to high performing hardware such machines with graphic processing unit(GPU) needed for building complex learning

models and this negative impacts this has on the students research i.e. “whole sway the PhDs that just can't happen without physical access to your expensive infrastructure and even for ours that the gpu's”. Although remote access to servers with GPUs was made available to research students and work progressed “and the remote access - look it works”, there is the sense that this suboptimal and “we're trying to muddle through and figure out ways to rearrange their plans and put stuff off, but at certain points, they need to be in there” Although in the context of this research study the focus in students of computer science, the doctoral thesis are interdisciplinary such as combining data science and chemistry or mechanical engineering i.e. “mixing chemicals and then using the bio printer and you know building devices to desalinate water”. These students require laboratory access to complete their experiments which is challenging for both student and supervisor i.e. “two of my co supervision are in Mech Eng and they need physical access to a lab”

Code: home-access-to-equipment

Description and Analysis:

This code concerned with the challenges surrounding research students having or retaining access to campus equipment for remote work i.e. laptops and computer hardware, monitors and graphic processing unit(GPU)s at home and the challenges surrounding this. In particular one participant highlighted the impressive response by department “ I was so impressed at how well the school and university in general responded last March, when they basically said take your computer home take your screen home if you need to take a taxi just do what you need to do, which I was so impressed they did that”. However, on the negative side it adds additional burden on the supervisor “ had to drop piece of equipment off to the student’s housethe student was also not been able to come and have a place at the university”. In addition there are issues for students concerning the heat electricity generated from powerful hardware that is being housed in a small unventilated space and the potential negative impact on the health of the student and the maintenance of specialist university hardware in improper conditions i.e. we've sent them home with the gpu machines - that's noisy , heat electricitysomeone who's in what a three by three room and eating, sleeping, working” and “the room isn't properly controlled for temperature and stuff like that

Code: legal-financial-issues,

Description and Analysis:

This code captures any legal and financial complexities surrounding research students residing outside of the country while also being registered for full time campus based attendance and in

receipt of scholarship. In addition supervisors raise concerns i.e. "it's such a complicated question because the University has certain things it wants to try and do, but there are others that are related to tax issues visa issues". In some cases supervisors are critical of the university expectation that off-campus students should reside in the country i.e. "It's been a little bit short sighted". PhDs students in receipt of a tax-free fellowship in Ireland must reside in the country in order "get a social security number you have to be here and have a bank accounts to get a bank account, you have to have a residential address in Ireland". Supervisors are faced with the conundrum of paying a stipend to a student who is not yet resident which not part of the regular procedure i.e. "technically, we can probably pay them, but do we really want to start paying them when they haven't come, yet what if they drop out".

Code student-learning-space

Description and Analysis:

This code describes the challenges surrounding whether research students have optimal or suboptimal learning spaces in which to conduct their research and studies. In some positive cases the student may "actually have their own space and maybe they have a desk" while for other students it is negative whereby, "you can very clearly hear that they are living in a very noisy household and there is a lot of distraction, and things going on" and that his has "definitely proven difficult for some students". Another example highlights this clearly that "some students may be in a situation where they have a space in their house where they can workthe ones that could be living with family in a very disruptive environment". The same participant notes that with campus based study that "all of those problems didn't exist because you had your space where you were you had your work, and that was kind of it, so the muddying of those waters.". Here the blurring of work life boundaries is also hinted. In addition, a submit optimal learning space may have a negative impact on student health i.e. "have physical issues because of having to work in a non optimum bedroom"

4.3 Critical Summative Analysis

In this section we over brief critical analysis connecting and summarising the key points of our thematic analysis:

- With respect the Lee's concepts of research, (2019), it appears that the concepts for Critical Skills (**theme: Concepts of Supervision**) and enculturation, relationship are impacted quite negatively by remote supervision– (sub themes: **Research Enculturation, Student Supervisor Relationship, Critical Skills**)
- **Research Enculturation** appears to be affected the most by online learning i.e. research group meetings, lab experience, loss of physical context, research opportunities lost as result of the absence of serendipity although some valuable solutions are suggested notably research lab placement and student led online meetings.
- Academics engaged in remote supervision experience a loss of rapport with their students and express an uncertainty of their role with respect to the management of personal student matters (**See subtheme: Student Supervisor Relationship**).
- The challenges posed by online interaction and in particular the lack of physical context (*code:online-interaction* and *code:lack-of-physical-context*) appear to cause frustration and strain to the student supervisor relationship (**See subtheme: Student Supervisor Relationship**).
- Supervisors experience a loss of chance opportunities as a result of no longer being campus based (*code: serendipity-spontaneity*). These impacts negatively on students due to the loss of opportunities for problem solving skills, creativity, collaboration and peer support within the research group/supervision process.
- The theme of **Research Environment** for remote supervision is a strong theme and one, which sufficiently dealt within in literature of research supervision models or remote supervision, although lab placements and are mentioned in (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). Of course this indicates the additional demands remote supervision places on the supervisor to act as an institutional gatekeeper for lab access as well as access to materials and equipment which is an additional burden.

- Supervisor's experience of difficulty in assessing student mental health and performance remotes. Isolation as result of distance learner plays significant role in the decline of student mental health (*code:student-mental-health, code: student-isolation*, **theme: Student Welfare and Performance**)
- Furthermore student mental health and the experience of isolation by distance learning postgraduate students are not tackled in the existing literature on remote supervision (theme: **Student Welfare and Performance**) as well the provision for explicit support and training for the supervisor. Although the restrictions caused by Covid-19 are logically a factor it does mean that there are certain non-Covid contexts where these difficulties would arise.
- Remote supervision may naturally lead to a more highly structured (code: **(subtheme:Structured-Functional)** form of supervision (**theme:Research Supervisor Styles**), however this does not mean that supervisors need to take a directorial (*code:deliberate-directorial*) approach, although there is some discussion in the data on how too much project management may impacts the independent nature of postgraduate (PhD) research
- Supervisors do not explicitly think **Emancipation** (*code:emancipation*) is being impacted by remote supervision although despite the concerns raised over the student deficits in the development of independent critical thinking (**subtheme: Critical Skills**) which is mentioned in (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015) as well as their potential poor understanding of the independent nature of the PhD degree.
- Supervisors (in Computer Science) felt that critical thinking activities with students i.e. brain-storming, critical discussion and (misunderstandings) feedback were significantly negatively affected by the limitations of working online as well as existing online tools (missing whiteboard and physical interaction) **subtheme: Critical Skills**. This relates also to the challenges surrounding providing effective feedback in the literature (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015).
- Supervisors do experience an increase on workload as a result of the demands of remote supervision place on the supervisor to act as an intuitional gatekeeper, which is stressful for the supervisor (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). The additional burdens placed on supervisors by remote supervisor have caused some academics to be more

hesitant to take on more supervisees (codes: *supervisor-confidence-motivation*, *supervisor workload-burden*)(**theme: Supervisor Wellbeing**)

- Some supervisors are repelled by part-time PhD supervision, which naturally has implications for postgraduate research degrees by distance, and a follow up study would be interesting. The negative reaction recorded may also explain the lack of research on part-time supervision in general. Perhaps academics do not see part-time doctorates as productive for their research metrics but this is speculative (*code:part-time-phd*)

We now conclude the chapter on reflexive thematic analysis. Having first provided a rich and thick description of each theme with illustrated example, we then provided a critical summative analysis. We move now to the final chapter in the thesis, which presents our recommendation for future research opportunities based on the results above.

Chapter 5: Recommendations and Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents our final recommendations with respect to challenges and opportunities remote research supervision based on my analysis for the literature (Chapter 2) and the results of my qualitative study into the experiences of supervisors engaged in remote supervision (Chapter 4). I also outline the limitations of the study (Section 4.1), respond to the research questions posed in Chapter 1 (Section 4.2) and conclude with recommendations for future research.

5.2 Limitations

- This research is exploratory and is constrained within the boundaries of the MA dissertation. I am not attempting to test a hypothesis. One focus group is appropriate as this research is concerned with the generation understanding and ideas, potentially new hypothesis may be generated for long term research.
- The reflexive thematic analysis presented in Chapter 4 does not attempt to generate new theory or model for remote research supervision. Nevertheless it does identify research gaps in existing model that require further investigation and validation.
- The sample size is representative at the department level however naturally one cannot generalise to a broader population. However, the account provided in reflexive thematic analysis has sufficient reproducibility, depth and richness that the themes can be i) verified in the literature and or ii) potential validated in similar studies (focus groups, interviews, quantitative surveys) culminating in a potential case study (Cousin, 2009, Chapter 8).
- Finally, it is effectively impossible to decouple the factors surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic from our data. While on side, the pandemic creates very strict conditions for observing the experience of supervisors for remote supervision, any negative experiences may be intensified by the challenges of the COVID-19. Nevertheless, it

does not mean that the themes presented in our analysis would not generalise to other supervisors' experience of remote supervision at a less intensified level.

5.3 Research Questions Revisited

Based on my analysis in Chapter 4, I can now provide a preliminary answers to our research questions bearing in mind the limitations of the study :

- **RQ1:** What are the challenges and opportunities experienced by academics engaged in remote supervision of postgraduate research students?

Answer: Based on our initial analysis, supervisors engaged in remote supervision report negative experiences and challenges with respect to i) providing students with access adequate research infrastructure and ii) opportunities for research enculturation (lab experience) iii) ensuring the development of critical thinking skills and vi) building a strong student supervisor relationship. In addition they report a negative impact of online interaction on the student supervisor relationship and experience increased burden and experience uncertainty around the boundaries of their role with respect to student welfare. Finally some supervisors report being unsure, whether they can dynamically alter supervision styles within the constraints of online/remote delivery of a research degree programme. Some benefits are reported however with respect improvements in efficiency with respect to organisation of peer led online group meetings, feedback and progress as a result of the high structure demanded by remote supervision.

- **RQ2:** How do supervisors engaged in remote supervision relate to models of supervision (specifically Lee's Concepts of Supervision, (2019) and Gatfield's Supervisory Management Grid, 2005).

Answer: Based on our initial analysis, with respect Lee's Concepts of Supervision (2019), the concepts **Enculturation** (in particular) , **Critical Skills** and **Relationship** (Section 2.3) appear to be impacted significantly in a negative way by remote

supervision. Notably, the model does not adequately address the importance of access to research infrastructure under the concept of **Enculturation**. Supervisors experience a higher degree of **Functional** approach to supervision when working remotely with research students. With respect to Gatfield's Supervisory Management Grid, (2005), supervisors report a shift to **directorial style** as result of remote supervision but others argue that although supervising remotely demands more from structure from the supervisor, this does not necessarily have to lead to change in supervision style. Finally some supervisors were concerned about whether working remotely/online impeded their ability to move between styles (**pastoral, laissez-faire**), feeling that online interaction was a constraining influence in their supervision style.

5.3 Recommendations and Future work

Based on my findings in Chapter 4 and our analysis of the literature (Chapter 2) I can make the following recommendations with respect to future research opportunities and challenges, bearing in mind that the recommendations are preliminary and the additional empirical validation is needed.

- With respect the Lee's Framework for research supervision, (2019), it appears that the concepts for **Critical Skills, Enculturation, Relationship** (Section 2.3) are impacted quite negatively by remote supervision and how to adapt the model better to remote supervision is an open research **challenge** and it provides **opportunity** to update the model.
- **Research Enculturation** appears to be negatively **challenged** the most by online/remote learning. The data indicates the supervisors attempt to circumvent the lack of lab experience by organising a research placement in the student's country of residence as well as peer led online group meetings. Lab placement is suggested also in the literature (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015) . However enabling

remote enculturation is a research challenge, which has likely been underestimated, and it presents an **opportunity** for further study.

- Academics engaged in remote supervision experience a loss of rapport with their students and express an uncertainty of their role with respect to the management of personal student matters. In barriers posed by online interaction and in particular the lack of physical context *appear* to strain the student supervisor relationship. This challenge of managing the student supervisor relationship remotely does not appear to explicitly tackled in the literature, which presents an **opportunity** for further study with respect good online technologies and methods to
- Supervisors experience a loss of chance (serendipitous and spontaneous) opportunities as a result of no longer being campus based. This impacts negatively on opportunities for problem solving, creativity and collaboration between student and supervisor as well as peer support within the research group. More research is needed (**opportunity**) into experimenting with online tools that foster more spontaneous collaboration and how can this **challenge** be tackled in distance learning context.
- The theme of **Research Infrastructure** in remote supervision is a strong theme and one, which is not sufficiently dealt within in literature of research supervision models or remote supervision. This **challenge** poses additional demands on the supervisor to act as an institutional gatekeeper (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015) of access to materials and equipment as well lab access. More research needs to be conducted into best international practice supporting research infrastructure for distance learning research postgraduate i.e. tackling issues such as lab , equipment or materials access within a remote context or blended setting as well as the legal /financial issues surrounding registered full time postgraduate students who are studying and residing outside of the host country (**opportunity**)
- Supervisor's experience of difficulty in assessing student mental health and performance remotes. Isolation as result of distance learning is likely to plays significant role in the decline of student mental health. This is **challenging** for supervisors who in a remote context must act as institutional gatekeeper to the support services offered by the unversity (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). There is an

opportunity for additional research to address supervisors needs (support or additional mental health awareness training, helping skills)

- Remote supervision risks to constrain supervision into a more highly structured even directorial supervision (Gatfield, 2005). This can prove **challenging** for the supervisor seeking to ensure the emancipation and eventual production of independent researchers at the end of the PhD process. There is an **opportunity** to conduct research into guidelines for supervisors on how and when to dynamically adapt their supervision management styles in a remote/online context.
- Critical thinking activities with students i.e. brain-storming, critical discussion and (misunderstandings) feedback were negatively **challenged** by the limitations of working online as well as existing online tools (missing whiteboard and physical interaction. This relates also to the challenges surrounding providing effective hierarchal feedback in the literature (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). There is an **opportunity** to conduct research into guidelines for the effective use online tools for critical skills development, note taking and effective feedback.
- More research is required into assessing the impact of increased workload as a result of remote supervision (**opportunity**)
- Part-time research supervision and group supervision either remotely or face-to-face are under-researched. In particular there may be hesitancy on the behalf of academics to engage in supervision of part time students, which presents an **opportunity** for further research.

References

- Anderson, C., Day, K., & McLaughlin, P. (2007). Mastering the dissertation: Lecturers' representations of the purposes and processes of master's level dissertation supervision.
- Anderson, C., Day, K., & McLaughlin, P. (2008). Student perspectives on the dissertation process in a Masters degree concerned with professional practice. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 30, 33-49. doi:10.1080/01580370701841531
- Andrew, M. (2012). Supervising doctorates at a distance: three trans-Tasman stories. *Quality Assurance in Education*.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2018, June) An introduction to thematic analysis, Guest Lecture, University of the West of England [Video] Youtube
Retrieved 26th August 2021 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5zFcC10vOVY>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021a). Can I use TA? Should I use TA? Should I not use TA? Comparing reflexive thematic analysis and other pattern-based qualitative analytic approaches. *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 21(1), 37-47.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021b, June) An introduction to reflexive thematic analysis, School of Psychology, University of Auckland,
<https://www.psych.auckland.ac.nz/en/about/thematic-analysis.html>
- Brew, A. (2010). Enhancing undergraduate engagement through research inquiry. (Research Report). Retrieved from the Australian Learning Teaching Council website
- Carson, B. H. (1996). Thirty years of stories: The professor's place in student memories. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 28(6), 11-17.
- Caulfield, J (2020, August 26) How to do thematic analysis? Retrived from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
- Charmaz, K. 2002. "Qualitative interviewing and grounded theory analysis". In *Handbook of interview research: context and method*, Edited by: Gubrium, J. F. and Holstein, J. A. 675–94. Sage. [\[Google Scholar\]](#)
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th). Routledge.
- Cousin, G. (2009). *Researching learning in higher education: An introduction to contemporary methods and approaches*. Routledge.
- Cullen, S. (2009). Resource guide to dissertation supervision on taught undergraduate and postgraduate

- Crossouard, B., 2008. Developing alternative models of doctoral supervision with online formative assessment. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 30(1), pp.51-67.
- Delany, D. (2008). A review of the literature on effective PhD supervision. *Trinity College, Dublin, Centre for Academic Practice and Student Learning (CAPSL)*.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Sage.
- Donald, J. G. (2002). *Learning To Think: Disciplinary Perspectives. The Jossey-Bass Higher and Adult Education Series*. Jossey-Bass, Inc., 989 Market St., San Francisco, CA 94103.
- Franke, A., & Arvidsson, B. (2011). Research supervisors' different ways of experiencing supervision of doctoral students. *Studies in Higher Education*, 36(1), 7-19.
- Ghani, F., & CMP, B. (2020). Remote teaching and supervision of graduate scholars in the unprecedented and testing times. *J Pak Dent Assoc*, 29.
- Gatfield, T. (2005). An investigation into PhD supervisory management styles: Development of a dynamic conceptual model and its managerial implications. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 27(3), 311-325.
- Ghani, F., & CMP, B. (2020). Remote teaching and supervision of graduate scholars in the unprecedented and testing times. *J Pak Dent Assoc*, 29.
- Graduate Studies, Dublin City University . (n.d.). *Graduate Research Guide, 2020-2021*
<https://www.dcu.ie/sites/default/files/2020-10/graduate-research-guide-2020-21.pdf>
- Grant, B. M., & Giddings, L. S. (2002). Making sense of methodologies: A paradigm framework for the novice researcher. *Contemporary nurse*, 13(1), 10-28.
- Gurr, G. M. (2001). Negotiating the "Rackety Bridge"—a dynamic model for aligning supervisory style with research student development. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 20(1), 81-92.
- Haberstroh, S., & Duffey, T. (2011). Face-to-face supervision of online counselors: Supervisor perspectives. Retrieved from http://counselingoutfitters.com/vistas/vistas11/Article_66.pdf
- Halse, C., & Malfroy, J. (2010). Rethorizing doctoral supervision as professional work. *Studies in Higher education*, 35(1), 79-92.
- Hudson, L.A. and Ozanne, J.L., 1988. Alternative ways of seeking knowledge in consumer research. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(4), pp.508-521.
- Kiley, M. (2009). Identifying threshold concepts and proposing strategies to support doctoral candidates. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 46(3), 293-304.
- Wisker, G. (2012). *The good supervisor: Supervising postgraduate and undergraduate research for doctoral theses and dissertations*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Hughes, John and Sharrock, Wes (1997), *The Philosophy of Social Research*, 3rd edition, Pearson: Essex.
- Kumar, S., Kumar, V. & Taylor, S. (2020) *A Guide to Online Supervision*. UK Council for Graduate

- Education. Retrieved from <http://www.ukcge.ac.uk/media/download.aspx?Mediald=2268>
- Meyer, J., & Land, R. (2006). *Overcoming barriers to student understanding: Threshold concepts and troublesome knowledge*. Routledge.
- Lee, A. (2008). How are doctoral students supervised? Concepts of doctoral research supervision. *Studies in higher education*, 33(3), 267-281.
- Lee, A. (2019). *Successful research supervision: Advising students doing research*. Routledge.
- Levers, M.-J. D. (2013). Philosophical Paradigms, Grounded Theory, and Perspectives on Emergence. *SAGE Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244013517243>
- Paran, A., Hyland, F., & Bentall, C. (2010). The Research Element in Masters' Degrees in Distance Education: Literature Review and Mapping Survey.
- Pidgeon, N., & Henwood, K. (1997a). Using grounded theory in psychological research. In N. Hayes (Ed.), *Doing qualitative analysis in psychology* (pp. 245- 273). Hove, UK: Psychology Press
- Pearson, M., & Brew, A. (2002). Research training and supervision development. *Studies in Higher education*, 27(2), 135-150.
- Porter, S. (2021). Doctoral reform for the 21st century. In *The Future of Doctoral Research* (pp. 28-39). Routledge.
- Morgan, G., & Smircich, L. (1980). The case for qualitative research. *Academy of management review*, 5(4), 491-500.
- McCallin, A., & Nayar, S. (2012). Postgraduate research supervision: A critical review of current practice. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 17(1), 63-74.
- Rosenau, Rose (1992), *Post-modernism and the Social Sciences. Insights, Inroads, and Intrusions*, Princeton
- Sandberg, J. and Alvesson, M., 2011. Ways of constructing research questions: gap-spotting or problematization?. *Organization*, 18(1), pp.23-44.
- Smith, B. M. (1997). *Lecturing to large groups*. SEDA.
- Smith, J. A. and Osborn, M. 2003. "Interpretative phenomenological analysis". In *Qualitative psychology: a practical guide to methods*, Edited by: Smith, J. A. Sage. [\[Google Scholar\]](#)
- Sturgeon, N. (2019, July). *Why governments should prioritize well-being*. [Video]. TED Conferences.
- Sussex, R. (2008). Technological options in supervising remote research students. *Higher Education*, 55(1), 121-137.
- Swartz, R. J., & Perkins, D. N. (2016). *Teaching thinking: Issues and approaches*. Routledge.
- Taylor, S., & Beasley, N. (2005). *A handbook for doctoral supervisors*. Routledge.

Venter, K. (2003). Coping with isolation: The role of culture in adult distance learners' use of surrogates. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 18(3), 271-287

Vilkinas, T. (2002). The PhD process: the supervisor as manager. *Education+ Training*.

Wallace M, Wray A. Critical Reading and Writing for Postgraduates. London: Sage Study Skills, 2006, 92.

Wisker, G. 2007. "Supervising Postgraduate: Internationally, and at a Distance." In *Connections: Sharing the Learning Space*, edited by P. Wilcox, H. Jones, M. Sumner and E. Berrington, 23–28. Brighton, UK: Falmer Press

Wisker, G. (2012). *The good supervisor: Supervising postgraduate and undergraduate research for doctoral theses and dissertations*. Macmillan International Higher Education.

Unwin, T. (2007). Reflections on supervising distance-based PhD students. *Royal Holloway, University of London*. [www. gg. rhul. ac. uk/ict4d/distance-based% 20PhDs. pdf](http://www.gg.rhul.ac.uk/ict4d/distance-based%20PhDs.pdf).

Appendix A: Application for Ethical Approval

Application for Ethical Approval

Name:	Brian Davis
Email address:	b.davis1@nuigalway.ie
Project title:	Emerging themes in remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in Computing during COVID-19
Brief summary of the project: (please use plain English)	The aim of this project is to explore the experience of academics who engaged in remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in the Department of Computing, Dublin City University. Focus groups will be used to explore whether/how supervisory practices changed as campuses were closed. This research is being conducted by Dr Brian Davis, a student of the MA in Academic Practice at the Centre for Excellence in Learning & Teaching (CELT), NUI Galway.
Participant information: (include sample size, recruitment methods, study demands)	<p>Sample size</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volunteers will be drawn from the academic staff of the Department of Computing at DCU who supervise doctoral students in a form of teaching that was required to move online during the pandemic. • The sample size is that of standard focus group (4-12 participants) academics (page 436 of [1] and chapter 4 of [2]) • The sampling method will be purposeful/convenience based and drawn staff within the School of Computing – ideally an equal number of both male/female participants. • Academics will be permanent/contract staff who are at the early-mid career level (Lecturer/Assistant Professor). • Participants must be involved in doctoral supervision but may or may not have graduated a PhD student. • Supervisees of participants will range from 1st -Final Year PhD students in Computing. <p>Recruitment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment will involve emailing staff members who are constrained to above criteria. • The school research convener/head of department may be contacted as to acquire a list of primary supervisors who are at early/mid-career level grade and are currently supervising PhD students.

	<p>Study Demands</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants will be asked to read the plain English Information Statement and sign the consent form digitally. • Participants will be asked to join a password secure Zoom⁶ session hosted by Dr Davis. • The Focus group duration will be occur in two parts Part 1: Duration 45 minutes followed be a 15 minute break Part 2: Duration 45 minutes. • (Part 1)The participants will be provided an agenda whereby they will be asked engage in group reflection with respect to distance supervision. <i>What Worked?, What did not work? Actionable Knowledge – What have you/we learnt?</i> • (Part 2)In addition participants may be asked to reflect on Anne Lee [2] models of supervision and how it relates to their own supervision style (See Table 1 Appendix C) • The focus group will be recorded on Zoom with consent from participants • A transcript of the group will be generated automatically in Zoom.
<p>How will informed consent be obtained: (attach your participant information sheet/consent form)</p>	<p>A participant information sheet and consent form will be emailed to eligible staff at least one week in advance of the focus group. Those who volunteer will be asked to complete and electronically sign and return the consent form. See Appendix A</p>
<p>Ethical issues related to the project: (address confidentiality, anonymity, withdrawal etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus group participants will be reminded of the need for confidentiality. • The information discussed in the group will be kept confidential. There is little perceived risk, but any sensitive information or topics will be managed by the researcher outside of the focus group, and this will be communicated to all participants in advance. • Once the focus group has been transcribed – participants will be asked to review it for accuracy. • Once satisfied with the content of the transcript it will be anonymised at source to ensure full confidentiality • Participants will have the right to withdraw prior to full anonymisation of the transcript. • All participants will be volunteers of equal academic rank, thus ensuring no conflicts of interest with respect to probation/promotion. The researcher has no line management responsibility for any potential participants to avoid issues of coercion. • If a participant provides potential evidence of poor academic

⁶ zoom.us

	<p>practice/research integrity than they will asked not to discuss the issue in the group. The participant will be advised confidentially/privately of the potential issue and to discuss the issue with the head of department or research integrity officer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the themes within the group discussion inadvertently cause distress the participant is free to leave the group. The participant will be debriefed separately and advised of Employee Assistance Services which are at their disposal at the university. • Participants may withdraw from the focus group at anytime. • Participants will be provided with a summary of content analysis (thesis chapter) for review. • The researcher will ensure that the data or the department staff, university will not be misrepresented in the course of publishing the research as to cause harm (professionally or personally)
<p>Data protection/ security issues: (state how data will be secured, confidentiality maintained etc)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All data will stored on secure cloud institutional (DCU) repository. Data will not be stored on any standalone machine. • The original Zoom recording and transcript will be retained until the dissertation is examined. • Once this is done the Zoom recording will be destroyed. • The original transcript will be anonymised at source. • The original transcript (anonymised) will be kept data verification examination purposes but no longer than is necessary. • The identity of participants will be kept confidential. • Focus group participants will be reminded of the need for confidentiality.
<p>Signed (student):</p>	<p>I have discussed all relevant ethical issues with my supervisor and agree to be bound by the BERA and ethical guidelines, as well as the ethical guidelines Association of Internet Researchers</p> <p><i>Brian Davis</i></p>
<p>Signed (tutor):</p>	
<p>Date:</p>	<p>24th August 2020</p>

Please append supporting documentation as necessary, such as:

- Participant information sheet
- Consent form
- Recruitment materials (ads/flyers/other communications)
- Interview schedules/survey instruments
- Other (if appropriate)

ATTEMPT

28/10/20 00:24

40.00 /0

Submission

[Application-for-Ethical Approval-BrianDavis-MA
-Version-Final.docx](#)

Comments

BRIAN DAVIS

28/10/20 00:24

Dear Jan, Please find my final Ethics application submission. Many thanks for your feedback. Kind Regards Brian

Feedback to Learner

11/11/20 15:18

Sent to School of Ed, 4/11/20.

Approved 11/11/20.

Saved As Artefact

OK

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Participant Information Sheet

Project Title

Exploring remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in Computing during COVID-19

You are invited to take part in this research project that aims to explore the experience of academics supervising doctoral students remotely in the School of Computing, Dublin City University, during COVID-19 global pandemic

Participation is **voluntary**; you do not need to take part and, even if you agree to take part, you can withdraw from the study at any time with no negative effects for you. Please read this sheet carefully so that you know what you are being asked to do, and feel free to ask any questions you wish before deciding whether to go ahead or not.

Research purpose

In this project, I am interested in finding out about approaches to supervision online (by distance), any emerging issues (challenges, opportunities) for academics engaging in doctoral research supervision. The findings of the research will be shared with the participants.

Inclusion criteria:

DCU Academic staff in Computing (contract/permanent) at the grade of Assistant/Associate professor who are currently acting as a primary supervisor to a doctoral student (Any Year)

Exclusion criteria:

Academic staff in management role (Assistant Head/Associate Dean) of the rank hire than Professor

Academic staff who may participate in any probation review/promotion boards within the department.

Academic staff who jointly (co-) supervise students with an academic staff member who has already agreed to participate in the study

Your involvement

To do this, I am asking volunteers to join as a group in a secure Zoom video meeting at [date/time TBD]. Your involvement should take no longer than [120 minutes including 15 minutes break after 45 minutes].

Benefits

The benefits of taking part in this project include increased knowledge of the theory/practice of research supervision as well as any new insights/approaches/methods on how to improve their supervision practice based on shared agreed outcomes derived from moderated group reflection and discussion.

Risks

The risks associated with this project are negligible to staff. If staff inadvertently experience any stress disclosing information about their supervision experience during COVID-19 they are free to leave the group meeting. They will be advised of the appropriate support services available to employees in a follow-on private meeting.

What next?

Thank you for taking the time to read this information. If you would like any further information, please contact b.davis1@nuigalway.ie. If you wish to take part in this research, please complete and sign ⁷the consent form supplied and return it by post or electronically to:

Dr Brian Davis

School of Computing

L2.26

McNulty Building

Dublin City University |

Glasnevin

Dublin 9

Email: brian.davis@dcu.ie

If you would like to speak to an independent person about this research project, please contact:

Dr Jan Smith, Programme Co-ordinator, Postgraduate Diploma/MA in Academic Practice,
jan.smith@nuigalway.ie

⁷ A scanned signature or digital signature is acceptable.

Template – Recruitment Letter/Email

(Date)

Re: Exploring remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in Computing during COVID-19 – Invitation to participate.

Dear: (Name)

I am writing to let you know about an opportunity to participate in a voluntary research study

This study is being conducted by me, Dr Brian Davis at the Centre for Excellence in Learning and Teaching at NUI Galway.

Research purpose

In this project, I am interested in finding out about approaches to supervision online (by distance), any emerging issues (challenges, opportunities) for academics engaging in doctoral research supervision. The findings of the research will be shared with the participants.

Participation is **voluntary**; you do not need to take part and, even if you agree to take part, you can withdraw from the study at any time with no negative effects for you. Please read the attached Plain English Language statement carefully so that you know what you are being asked to do, and feel free to ask any questions you wish before deciding whether to go ahead or not.

Inclusion criteria:

DCU Academic staff in Computing (contract/permanent) at the grade of Assistant/Associate professor who are currently acting as a primary supervisor to a doctoral student (Any Year)

Exclusion criteria:

Academic staff in management role (Assistant Head/Associate Dean) of the rank hire than Professor

Academic staff who may participate in any probation review/promotion boards within the department.

Academic staff who jointly (co-) supervise students with an academic staff member who has already agreed to participate in the study.

Your involvement

To do this, I am asking volunteers to join as a group in a secure Zoom video meeting at [date/time TBD]. Your involvement should take no longer than [120 minutes including 15 minutes break after 45 minutes]. You must sign and return the attached consent form if you wish to participate in this study. The meeting will be recorded. Volunteers who are uncomfortable with being recorded will be unable to continue to participate the study.

Benefits

The benefits of taking part in this project include increased knowledge of the theory/practice of research supervision as well as any new insights/approaches/methods on how to improve their supervision practice based on shared agreed outcomes derived from moderated group reflection and discussion.

Risks

The risks associated with this project are negligible to staff. If staff inadvertently experience any stress disclosing information about their supervision experience during COVID-19 they are free to leave the group meeting. They will be advised of the appropriate support services available to employees in a follow-on private meeting.

If you would like additional information about this study, please contact me at **b.davis1@nuigalway.ie**

Brian Davis

Assistant Professor, School of Computing

Appendix C: Consent Form (Focus Group)

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM (STAFF)

Consent Form to participate in an Online (Video Meeting) Focus Group for the research project:

Exploring remote (online) research supervision of doctoral students in Computing during COVID-19

I have read the information provided for this project and have been given the opportunity to ask any further questions.

- Please tick:**
- I consent to take part in this study:
- I consent to audio/video recording using online video conferencing
- I consent to a anonymised transcript of the above being retained confidentially secure for the duration of the research project.
- If you would like to:
- hear about the outcome of this study:
 - ask further questions:

Contact the researcher at b.davis1@nuigalway.ie

Thank you for consenting to take part in this study. Please sign below, and a copy of this form will be supplied to you.

Signed (research participant): _____ Date: _____

Signed (researcher): _____ Date: _____

If you would like to speak to an independent person about this research project, please contact:

Dr Jan Smith, Programme Co-ordinator, Postgraduate Diploma/MA in Academic Practice,
jan.smith@nuigalway.ie, tel: 091 49 3481

Appendix D: Focus Group Materials

Activity 1: Reflection Exercise on your experience of Remote Supervision of Postgraduate Research Students

- *What is working well in the context of your current supervisory practice?*
Use the space below to gather some notes:

- *What are the challenges you are experiencing in the context of your current supervisory practice?*
Use the space below to gather some notes:

- *In what way(s) does remote supervision differ from on-campus supervision for you?*

Use the space below to gather some notes:

- *Actionable Knowledge – What have you learnt?*

Use the space below to gather some notes:

Activity 2: Frameworks of Research Supervision

There are number of models and conceptual frameworks for research supervision. Simply put they attempt model styles or approaches to research supervision. Two well known frameworks for research supervision are described. It is important to note there is no standard framework or model for supervision. Hence the approaches below are not authoritative or a *one size fits all!*

1. Anne Lee's conceptual approaches to supervision

Anne Lee [1], (see Table 1) describes a series of conceptual approaches to supervision: i) **functional**, which is directive, task orientated and concerned with project management, **enculturation**, which is concerned with gatekeeping, diagnosing deficiencies and coaching the student on how to become a member of the research community, iii) **critical thinking** which is concerned with a constant inquiry, analysis, argumentation, iv) **emancipation, which supports** constructivism⁸, reflection, personal development and growth and finally v) **relationship development** which is concerned with the development of the supervisor-supervisee relationship and emotional intelligence. Different

⁸ **Constructivism** is the theory that says learners construct knowledge rather than just passively take in information. As people experience the world and reflect upon those experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into their pre-existing knowledge (schemas).

approaches may be applied at different stages and/or combined depending on the individual student needs.

Concept of research supervision held by supervisor	Most prominent activity needed (Supervisor)	Knowledge and skills needed (Supervisor)	Possible student reaction
Functional	Rational movement through tasks	Directing, Project management	Organised Obedience Logical
Enculturation	Gatekeeping To communities, collaborations and networking – introductions to people/ exemplars of high-quality work.	Diagnosis of deficiencies to be remedied. Coaching	Apprenticeship, Role modelling
Critical thinking	Evaluation Challenge Enquiry based	Argument (gently Socratic) or constructive controversy, analysis, synthesis	Constant inquiry/ fight or flight
Emancipation	Mentoring (non-judgemental advisor) Supporting student in constructing knowledge	Facilitation Analysis and reflection	Personal growth Reframing (redefining)knowledge.
Relationship Development Qualities	Supervising according to own experience, Developing a relationship/team	Emotional intelligence. A range of experiences to draw upon	Emotional intelligence Personal awareness

Table 1 Conceptual approaches to Supervision (extracted from [1])

2. Terry Gatfield’s supervisory management grid

Gatfield’s [2] supervisory management grid (See Figure 2), contains **four** management styles placed between two high to low axes, one labelled “support” and “structure”. The four styles are i) **Laissez-faire** [low structure, low support] – Supervisor is “non-directive” and not committed to high levels of personal interaction ii) **Pastoral** [low structure, high support] - The supervisor is concerned with the student’s welfare and provides information, however the student is responsible for their research project management and self-

structure iii) **Directional** [high structure, low support] - The focus of supervision is the management and direction of the student's research project but with no provision of pastoral support and iv) **Contractual** [high structure, high support] - The supervisor is involved with the management of the student's research project and, if needed, provides pastoral support [10].

Gatfield's model is that it places supervisors and students on a spectrum, using descriptors to identify what he refers to as "preferred operating styles." This means that although a supervisor might have a propensity toward one particular style over another, it allows for movement between styles as necessary. Individuals may find themselves on different parts of the spectrum at different times during the degree or supervision process. For instance, a supervisor may allow the student lots of flexibility early in the doctoral program as the student tries to identify a suitable topic (more pastoral), but may become more directive and contractual as the student is actively pursuing the project. Later in the program, the supervisor again may become less directive or prescriptive as the student begins thesis write-up.

Gatfield stresses that **none of the four styles should be considered inherently undesirable or wrong.** He argues that supervision strategies are only ineffective if they do not match the needs and expectations of the supervisor and student.

Figure 1 Gatfield's supervisory management grid (extracted from [2])

Activity 2a: Reflection on Anne Lees’ Conceptual Framework for Supervision.

Take a few moments to study Table 1 above. How does Lee’s framework for supervision relate to your supervision practice? Please be aware there is no right or wrong answer!

Use the space below to gather some notes:

Activity 2b: Reflection on Garfield’s supervisory management grid

Take a few moments to study Figure 1 above. How does Gatfield’s supervisory management grid relate to your supervision practice? Please be aware there is no right or wrong answer! Use the space below to gather some notes:

References

[1] Lee, A. M. "Developing effective supervisors: Concepts of research supervision." South African Journal of Higher Education 21.4 (2007): 680-693.

[2] Gatfield, T., 2005. An investigation into PhD supervisory management styles: Development of a dynamic conceptual model and its managerial implications. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 27(3), pp.311-325.

Appendix E: Anonymous Survey on Supervisor Workload

Short Questionnaire - Survey on Remote Supervision - Brian Davis

In this project, I am interested in finding out about approaches to supervision online (by distance), any emerging issues (challenges, opportunities) for academics engaging in doctoral research supervision. The findings of the research will be shared with the participants.

***Required**

What is your job title?

- Assistant Professor/Lecturer
- Associate Professor/Senior Lecturer
- Professor/Full Professor

How many full time PhD (including Phd Track) student do you supervise/co-supervise? Please enter a number. *

Your answer _____

How many part time PhD (including Phd Track) students do you supervise/co-supervise? Please enter a number. *

Your answer _____

How many full time masters by research students do you supervise/co-supervise? Please enter a number.

Your answer _____

How many part time masters by research students do you supervise/co-supervise? Please enter a number.

Your answer _____

How many Taught Masters projects (full time / part-time) do you currently supervise - Note projects can include a (practicum pairs or one individual student). The question measures projects only -i.e. 1 project = 2 students 1 (MCM practicum pair) or 1 project = 1 Part-time MCM student

Your answer _____

How many undergraduate projects (full time / part-time) do you currently supervise - Note projects can imply a (team project or 1 individual student project). The question measures projects only i.e 1 project = 1 3rd year team project or 1 final year student

Your answer _____

Submit

 Page 1 of 1

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

Appendix F: Extended Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

In Chapter 1, I outlined the motivations for our study into remote research supervision as well as the challenges it poses at the various levels (cultural, personal, intellectual and professional) for 1) supervisor-supervisee interactions and 2) the content, progress and delivery of research activities and output (Nasiri and Mafakheri, 2015); challenges which are likely to be further exacerbated as result of the current COVID global pandemic (Ghani, F., 2020);. In this thesis chapter I provide i) a brief overview of research supervision pedagogy (Section 2.1), ii) analyse the literature within the scope of concepts and models of supervision (Section 2.2) as I am interested in how these frameworks relate to remote supervision and iii) examine the challenges of remote supervision (Section 2.3) as described in the existing scholarship for the purposes of critical reflection and engagement when reporting my results in Chapter 4.

2.1 Research Supervision – A Brief Overview

The *traditional model* of supervision involves a dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student and is concerned with preparing the student for independent research (McCallin and Nayar, 2012). It assumes the supervisor is the expert and the student is the apprentice who *learns by doing*. Although superficially highly structured involving regular meetings to discuss and document progress, upon closer examination the traditional model implies that supervisors engage in *mentoring, sponsoring, quality assurance* with respect to *progressing* and *coaching* (McCallin and Nayar, 2012). The traditional model arguably demands for intelligent, self-directed and self-motivated students who have strong (possibly) innate capacity for independent research and thus require minimal input from their supervisors in order to progress. The Irish PhD, which was claimed to have first awarded by Trinity College Dublin in 1935 (Delany, 2008) is also based on the British single supervisory model is

equivalent to the traditional model described above whereby the doctoral degree is pursued using an apprenticeship (learn by doing) model of training (Delany, 2008). A detailed literature review of research supervision is beyond the scope of this thesis, however Delany's (2008) analysis of the literature is a good start as it provides an historical overview of the introduction of research degree and the evolution of the ad hoc (traditional apprenticeship) model of research supervision within the Irish context. In addition it provides a good starting point with respect and analysis of the literature effective models of research supervision (up to around 2002) , whereby *effective* is defined by the criteria specified in Gatfield (2002) i.e. timely thesis submission, excellent supervisory reports, high engagement with supervision meetings.

McCallin and Nayar (2012) provide another excellent analysis of the literature concerning supervision pedagogy, and models of supervision. In particular the research context is discussed, whereby government funding agencies have begun to impact on how research student supervision. Although this occurs in a New Zealand context, there are clear parallels in this respect with the UK and Ireland with the advent of the SFI (Science Foundation Ireland)⁹ Research centres,¹⁰ IRC Postgraduate Awards¹¹ and the recent centres for research training (CRT¹²) all of whom have cleared defined expectations with respect to completion times, reporting, publication and deliverable output, dissemination and research training (generic and specialist). It is often the case the students in receipt of government funding must complete "a structured PhD", which aims to operationalize the skills statement. Coming back to McCallin and Nayar (2012), faculty challenges are also addressed and the impact of quality metrics (faculty credentials, publication records, supervision completions and grant award successes) on successful student completion and the clear need for *formal training* in research supervision.

In this respect, Pearson and Brew (2002) propose a course outline for a programme for flexible professional development programme for supervisors. Their proposal is based on a framework for supervision development which is underpinned by i) an analysis of the practice of supervision and teaching strategies so as mentoring, coaching, students as apprentices, *modelling* whereby the supervisor models a task for the student, *scaffolding*

⁹ <https://www.sfi.ie/>

¹⁰ <https://www.sfi.ie/sfi-research-centres/>

¹¹ <https://research.ie/funding/goipg/>

¹² <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/centres-research-training/>

providing intermediate supports and cues for the student and *fading* – the subsequent removal of the aforementioned supports and ii) discussions and definitions of what constitute research training – the key generalist and specialist skills required by the “complete scientist”, (Pearson and Brew, 2002, p. 137) as well as an analysis of senior academics conceptions of research and scholarship (Pearson and Brew, 2002, pp. 144-145).

In Franke and Avridsson, (2011), the authors explore the different ways in which research supervisors experience supervision their doctoral students. The results indicated two supervision structures i) *research practice orientated* whereby the supervisor transfers a research tradition, mediates best research practices and experiences a double role both of project manager and supervisor and any conflicts this raises (Franke and Avridsson, 2011, pp 12-13), and ii) *research relation orientated* where the supervisor is not the subject matter expert but rather oversees the transfer of knowledge concerning research skills and their *learning* and guarantees the scientific quality of the work and monitors all stages of the PhD. The supervisor creates the *right conditions* for the student to form and solve the problems of their thesis work via dialogue with the supervisor. In some cases the supervisor may feel they “fall short” if assigned a doctoral student that is outside their area of competence (Franke and Avridsson, 2011, pp 14-15).

Finally, scope of this literature review and the literature of supervision pedagogy in general focus on i) the full time research postgraduate undertaking ii) a 4 year PhD traditional research focused degree. The “professional doctorate” which targets students entering employment in areas other than academia often in the areas such as health sciences, psychology, nursing, education, business and finance, engineering, the goal being develop graduates of have research capability and who can become “active contributors to the knowledge economy in the workplace” (McCallin and Nayar, 2012, p. 69). The professional doctorate contains a significant number of taught components and research projects are practice or work based. In addition, supervision may often occur or develop in a group. For a good discussion of the professional doctorate see (McCallin and Nayar, 2012) and for a more update to discussion of the future of doctoral degree in general in the 21st Century we refer the reader to (Porter, 2021). In addition, it should be noted that the supervision of part-time postgraduate research are not captured explicitly within this literature review and is under researched topic in the scholarship on general. Watts (2008) provides a good overview of the challenges of supervising part-time PhD students and

discusses the benefits of a more student centred or pastoral supervision pedagogy for supporting the part-time PhD.

We move to the next section, in which I discuss concepts and models of supervision, deemed most relevant to our research questions.

2.2 Models and Frameworks of Research Supervision

There are number of models and conceptual frameworks for research supervision and historically they owe their origins to clinical/medical supervision and counselling/psychotherapeutic practices (Gatfield, 2005, p. 312: Gurr, 2001, p. 83). In the following subsections we compare and contrast **four** models for research supervision: i) Lee's (2008) , concepts of supervision, ii) Halse and Malfroy's (2020) approach to reformulating doctoral supervision as professional work iii) Gatfield's (2005) supervisory management styles and iv) Kiley's (2009) model of the supervision experience via threshold concepts.

2.2.1 Lee's (2019) Conceptual Approaches to Research Supervision

In (Lee, 2008, 2019), the author describes a series of conceptual approaches to supervision: *functional, enculturation, critical thinking, emancipation and relationship development*. The framework (See Figure 2.1) is underpinned by a series of interviews with academic

supervisors reflect on the “what” and “why” of the experience of supervision.

	Functional	Enculturation	Critical Thinking	Emancipation	Relationship Development
Supervisors Activity	Rational progression through tasks	Gatekeeping Master to apprentice	Evaluation Challenge	Mentoring, supporting constructivism	Supervising by experience, developing a relationship
Supervisor’s knowledge & skills	Directing, project management	Diagnosis of deficiencies, coaching	Argument, analysis	Facilitation, Reflection	Managing conflict Emotional intelligence
Possible student reaction	Organised Obedience	Role modelling, Apprenticeship	Constant inquiry, fight or flight	Personal growth, reframing	A good team member. Emotional intelligence

Figure 2.1 Lee’s Framework for Concepts of Research Supervision, (Lee, 2008, p. 268)

Supervisors report problems along a dichotomy of i) tensions between the professional and personal self and ii) tensions with respect to student dependence/independence. We pay particular attention to this model of supervision, as it well known documented and highly cited in scholarship of research supervision.

The functional approach.

This approach which is directive, task orientated and concerned with project management, (Lee, 2019,pp. 1-18) The supervisor is concerned with “institutional procedures for quality assurance”, (p 31, Anne Lee, 2021) and ensures that the student has access to all necessary institutional information and study supports he/she requires for their doctoral journal.

Deadlines and assessment criteria are made clear and the role of supervisors and co-supervisors and the requirements for ethical research practice are made explicit.

The approach draws parallels with Gatfield’s (2005) *directive* supervisions style and a managerial approach (Vilkonis, 2002). There is an underlying theme of consistent structure being established early in the supervision process which would be both maintain itself also and the students progress. The author describes a series of stages which are concerned with

recruiting, teaching and supervising research students (Lee, 2019, p. 42). Suggestions for operationalizing the functional approach include: i) ensuring funds and resources are available and in place ii) actively recruiting and interviewing candidate postgraduate students, which may include team interviews, exercises, samples of written work iii) organisation of induction, enrolling students in graduate induction programmes, induction checklist which includes key contacts, resources, thereby encouraging the student to participate in the research subculture. This also includes introducing students to academic life i.e. journal clubs, coffee meetings, teaching assistantship. This would involve the creation, maintenance and updating (with respect to institutional procedures) of research supervisors handbook at the department/research unit iii) facilitate a discussion around (co-) supervisors'/student roles and expectations, means of communication iv) research plan (including GANT charts, tasks, milestones and deliverables, log books), personal career development plan, organisation of technical and/or graduate skills modules whether they are mandatory as part of structured programme or necessary to correct any deficits. Training courses may include: research methods, best research practice, library training for conducting a literature search and other research skills, academic writing, ethics and research integrity training, Intellectual property management, project management, statistical methods iv) Records of meetings should be maintained and shared with all parties which can include briefly information about subjects discussed, objectives achieved and agreed to be met before the next meeting v) Attend or organise regular department, institutional meetings/seminars so that students can present their work to peers, staff and other visiting researchers vi) enabling feedback mechanisms, this may involve writing exercises such as paper sections, writing up reports on experiments, literature reviews in order to help students reach the level appropriate for the PhD. vii) Finally, there is the arrangement, management of progress reviews (internal) and at the Departmental/Faculty level. This will include organisation and management of the MPhil/Masters to PhD track transfer report as well as eventual thesis submission, internal/external examiner appointment and preparing the student for their Viva Voce exam. With respect to ensuring quality of the research outputs, supervisors are suggested to benchmark against recognised norms in their field and introduce assessment criteria early on in the doctoral training process as well their continued reference (Lee, 2019, p. 46).

Enculturation

Here the supervisor is concerned with gatekeeping, diagnosing deficiencies and coaching the student on how to become a member of the research community providing with sense of belonging by contributing to department and/or research unit . This approach is frequently referenced within the context of an apprenticeship model, whereby the research student must acquire a significant amount of knowledge both professionally and interpersonal about the nature of academic life (Lee, 2019, p. 48). This knowledge is subtle and not explicitly taught, but it essential to learn if the student wishes to become a competent and skilled professional researcher. The academic/research team can support this by providing opportunities attend and/or lead research seminars, attend conferences, attend/co-organise workshops and undertake teaching assistance activities as well as undergraduate or even taught postgraduate co-supervision. The supervisor is much like a “family doctor” (Lee, 2019, p. 49), providing some specific knowledge or expertise but will also act as a *gatekeeper*, “choosing which gates to open”, which must be handled with care in the early stages of the student or researchers’ PhD lifecycle/research career. It must be stated that the supervisor wields significant power as a gatekeeper (Lee, 2019, p. 49). Within the context of enculturation, the PhD is about becoming a member of the academic discipline/community (Leonard, 2001, p. 98) and as such the supervisor who is orientated to this approach should give clear direction to the student with respect to “academic and behavioural matter” which is akin to apprentice/master role (Lee, 2019, p. 49). As pointed out by Lee (2019), there are similarities with respect to enculturation methods across various disciplines. Suggestions for socialising students into a discipline include: i) allowing students to organise and invite guest speakers to seminars, ii) organise solo students into teams, iii) create a list of essential readings and key academics biographies with the discipline iv) encourage teaching activities with masters and undergraduate students as form of study v) organising students to present to colleagues within and outside their discipline vi) journal clubs and reading groups which encourage students to share knowledge and engage in critical analysis and reflection (Lee, 2019, p. 58). The enculturation of international research students raising different challenges as such students may have come from different undergraduate learning environments which may have less emphasis for instance on critical skills thinking and group discussion and more an

emphasis on memorising facts and texts (Lee, 2019, p. 59). For instance engaging a critical discourse and even disagreeing with the academic supervisor may be considered culturally inappropriate and may resist in engaging in co-inquiry and fear failure as well critique (either as a recipient or as an agent) (Lee, 2019, pp. 60-61). The supervisor must be cautious not to conflate intelligence with the above cultural issues. Supervisors must be mindful of cultural stereotypes and should seek to uncover any stereotypes that they may hold (Lee, 2019, p. 63). There may be a strong need from international postgraduate research students for the supervisor to engage in functional approach involving mutually “acceptable expectations” (Lee, 2019, p. 63). To avoid too much overhead with respect to supervision time, the supervisor can adopt a team approach with the support of postdoctoral researchers/senior PhD students. Suggestions to academics improving the supervision process with respect to international students include i) arranging additional induction programmes, ii) having a clear discussion of what the supervisors means by “supervisions”, “referencing”, “independent work and research”, auditing language, computing and research skills iii) having awareness of available support services, i.e. counselling, language, international, health and library services and who to contact iv) providing examples of quality research and the expected standards v) being sensitive to differences, cultural, religious and education etiquette. This may involve having a sensitive exchange of information with the student about timekeeping, gender relationships and body language v) providing encourage to take initiative with respect to academic writing and ensuring to allocate concrete time to provide clear and directive feedback v) and finally providing clear and concrete verbal and written guidance of the process and procedures of the postgraduate degrees (Lee, 2019, p. 63)

Critical Thinking

The critical thinking approach is concerned with a constant inquiry, analysis, argumentation (Lee, 2008). It is concerned with i) beliefs about knowledge and ii) the ability to assess statements relative to those beliefs. It is also concerned with the ability to “define and evaluate an argument” in manner which is appropriate to the discipline(s) in question (Lee, 2019, p. 70). Finally critical thinking involves developing the ability of a postgraduate research student to solve a problem in logical manner and reflect metacognitively on his/her

performance. The supervisor in this context is concerned with developing in the student the ability to understand, critique and create an argument. The supervisor depersonalises (but does not disregard) the relationship with the student in order to “examine substantive thinking processes free from emotion (Lee, 2019, p. 70) – what are the arguments for an against? What are the gaps? What has been considered and what has been left out? Naturally the critical thinking approach makes excellent preparation for the viva defence (Wikser, 2005). A “gentler Socratic method” proposed by Jackson (2001) proposes a more co-operative co-inquiry between student/supervisor and accepts that there is no correct answer (Lee, 2019, p. 73) Other approaches include: i) dialectically thinking which involves examining the strengths and weaknesses for a topic and putting differing points of view in competition with each other similar to debating ii) and dialogical thinking which involves examining and synthesising a series of propositions and investigating a topic from differing perspectives and frames of reference (Lee, 2019, p. 73) iii) constructive controversy /inquiry which involves reaching an initial position, being challenged and becoming uncertain around a topic, actively searching for more information and reconceptualising one’s knowledge in an attempt to resolve uncertainly and finally the production of new and refined conclusion (Lee, 2019, p.73; Johnson 2001). Regardless of the approach, Lee (2012, pp74-76) provides a series of tools that the academic supervisor can leverage to develop the critical thinking skills of postgraduates, which are grounded in **six** key components of critical thinking as identified by (Donald, 2002) across several disciplines across the fields Humanities, Science and Engineering. The six components are i) **Description**, which involves defining the problem, hypothesis, research gap, question, or the questioning of established “fact” or what is unknown based on the literature review ii) **Selection**, which is essentially the review of the literature and state of the art and development of the transferable skill of judging what is *important*, iii) **Representation**, which involves having a command of the key symbols and concepts in a discipline. Having a command of scientific and mathematical symbols and concepts is an example of this, iv) **Inference** which involves making an hypothesis about their findings. An idea is formulated about *what is going in?* Analyses are linked to and/or combined to generate outcomes. Inference may be: a) *deductive*, which involves using symbolic (propositional) logic, including logical connectives and quantification or b) *inductive*, based on data sampling, generalisation of outcomes using statistical techniques, probability, analysis of cause and chance and invocation of the scientific

method, iv) Synthesis, whereby the student must “stand back from the entire picture” and identify emerging themes and/or gaps in knowledge, where is data missing? Or where does data not fit theory? (Swartz and Perkins, 2016), v) **Testing Validity** requires the research student to demonstrate proof of the validity of their findings and the mechanism for testing will vary across disciplines, for example, examiners will test for *coherence* in the humanities, *consistency* in Physics, *reliability over time* as well the *principle of falsification* with respect to a given hypothesis in that it has been rigorously testing for rejection. Furthermore, findings can also be validated by *empirical evidence*, although this does not answer subsequent questions concerning causes and antecedents. *Triangulation* is also another method employed in the social sciences, where different research methods are invoked to analyse a phenomena, the results of which are compared with to test for the same result.

In the context of the approach to research supervision, Lee also engages significantly with the scholarship surrounding epistemology, ontology and how knowledge emerges in different disciplines and we refer to the reader to this section for more details (2012, pp 81-89). Key issues include the nature of knowledge as being: provisional or absolute, created and constructed, constrained by procedures with respect to its emergence, hidden, risky and personally transforming and different across different contexts and cultures (Lee, 2019, p. 82). Notably, Lee, (2019, p. 86) contrasts Cox’s (2008) integration of three cognitive structural development theorists with King and Kitchener’s seven stages of beliefs about knowledge and reasoning (1994) into a table concerning academics’ *knowing* concerning student beliefs about knowledge. In addition, Lee provides useful self-assessment questionnaires for academics to establish both the students’ beliefs and their own concerning knowledge (2019, p. 87).

In addition Lee describes how *threshold concepts* are another way of looking at how students master knowledge (2019, p. 87); such concepts are considered critical to understanding a discipline and have the following **five** characteristics of being: transformative, integrative, irreversible, bounded and troublesome (Meyer and Land, 2006). We will discuss threshold concepts in the context of research supervision later in Section 2.2.4. Lee also discusses problem solving and its role in critical skills thinking (2012, p. 87). Problem solving can be linked to project planning, planning and management skills. Lee (2019) describes an iterative problem solving procedure based on Swartz and Perkins (1990)

and Coverdale, (1990) which is based on three key stages: i) *description* of the problem, ii) *investigation* – eliciting information and dialectic examination, generating options, and iii) finally *implementation*, what needs to be done, what resources are needed and what is the plan of action and mechanisms of review?

Finally, Lee's treatment of the *critical thinking* approach provides an in-depth discussion around the metacognition (and reflection) in the context of the research student, observing, reflecting and directing their thinking. Reflection is concerned with the thinking process as described by John Dewey (1933) used by people when faced with questions of controversy or doubt in the face of challenges with respect to their current understanding or solution. "Reflective judgement is the end goal of good thinking" and involves producing a judgement or a solution that brings closure to a problem, (Dewey, 1933), (Lee, 2019, p. 89). Reflective learning, by providing intellectual and affective activities, enables learners to explore their experiences and thus leads to new understandings and appreciations with respect to a problem (Boud et al, 1985, p. 19), (Lee, 2019, pp.89). For a more comprehensive overview of reflection as an aid to learning, Moons (2000) evaluation of the work of Schon (1991) and Brookfield (1995). Schon describes a reflective practitioner as being "open to discovery" and a scholar that seeks discovery by "reviewing and reflecting on the actions" (Lee, 2019, p. 89). Brookfield promotes self reflection in the form of requesting teachers to engage students in self-evaluation whereby at least students can demonstrate that they are learning despite negative perceptions to the contrary on behalf of the teacher (1995), (Lee, 2019, p. 89). Lee discusses briefly several models of reflection, (2012, p. 90) notably one dynamic model of reflection which involves a continuous loop of three stages i) identifying and reflecting on experience (individually or with others), ii) comparing with other theorists' views and iii) creating/evolving new theory (Lee, 2019, p. 91). The conceptual model is underpinned by peer discussion (social constructivism) linked to the literature and constructivism, whereby the student must build their own understanding. Schon's (1991) notion of reflective practitioner involves two sorts of professional reflection: i) reflection on action that occurs after the event ii) reflection-in-action whereby professionals engage in reflective conversations with practical situations, constantly framing and reframing a problem as the research student works through it, thereby outlining their solutions and interpretations (Claderhead & Gates, 1993, p. 1). Cowan (2008) takes this model further by extending it for *reflection for action*, in that *between* each

stage, different reflecting skills are required (Lee, 2019, p. 91). Finally, Lee cites Moon (2000, 2004) in that the ability to reflect may depend on maturity (2012, p. 91). Examples include: showing evidence of internal dialogue and self-questioning, taking into account the views and motives of others, recognition how prior experiences can interact with their own behaviour, show clear evidence of standing back from an event, the ability to split off the reflective process from what *they* want to learn, demonstrate recognition that their personal frame of reference can change as result of their emotional state it was written, the acquisition of new information and the review of new ideas and the effect of the passage of time (Lee, 2019, p. 91) (Moon, 2004, p. 209). Moon recommends maintaining a reflective diary as a mechanism for focusing our own professional development (2000). In addition reflective diaries are a form of evidence for increasing demands for continued professional development (Lee, 2019, p. 91). To that end Lee provides a range of reflective questions in order to help students summarise their metacognitive skills (2017, p. 93).

Emancipation

With respect to this approach the academic is seeks to empower the student to find their own direction and values and to apply them to their research. Supervisors are supportive and yet where appropriate will challenge the student but are cautious not to impose their own values/agenda (Lee, 2019, p. 95). Supervision meetings and group work involved the academic both providing and seeking information and subsequently seeking the student's opinion. With respect to the emancipatory approach, a supervisor may allow a student to fail at a particular task if it may be extremely beneficial to the students learning. In this context the academic acts as a non directive mentor. Unlike enculturation, the emancipatory approach will not attempt to constrain the student within the discipline. Furthermore, personal development planning is strongly encouraged in this approach. Universities now expected to promote and ensure that students have access to personal development plans(PDPs) which tend to fall into three categories of i) learning, research and scholarship ii) employability, engagement and society and iii) personal and communication skill (Lee, 2019, p. 96). According to Lee, (2019, p. 96). The emancipatory approach can be viewed as form of Enquiry based learning (EBL), which engages the teacher initially as a guide and later as a collaborator. Students are encouraged to actively design questions, research and construct knowledge. While it includes leveraging research and

study skills, it also offers opportunities for creativity. EBL equips students with transferable skills of enquiry. It enables them to work trans-discipline/multi-discipline issues of constructed knowledge, ethical dimensions and enhances engagement (Lee, 2019, p. 97). In EBL, the teacher facilitates learning by establishing target learning outcomes, providing triggers for learning while the students collectively examine the problem, conduct the research, collate the results and examine the outcome with respect to their learning. The teacher acts a facilitator creating the necessary conditions by which the task can be carried out. Lee engages in further details with respect to the scholarship of Enquiry based learning (EBL) as mechanism for operationalizing emancipation of the research student. She contrasts i) problem based learning, whereby the academic sets the problem and the process and the student group solves the tasks with ii) EBL which is a holistic process facilitated by the academic whereby the learner and academic both collaboratively solve the problem and as well iii) action learning where learners define the problem and academic insures equal opportunity and fairness for all members. Lee also provides for serious of self assessment questions for the academic when facilitating inquiry based learning concerning issues such as ground rules, assessment of group learning, progress monitoring, safety conditions, facilitating discussion, collaborative development of assessment criteria (2012, p. 101). In addition, Lee (2019) discusses briefly the role of facilitation skills including psychosocial models of group functioning an group relationships, one notable example being the Rogerian model (Rogers, 1983) which involves six roles for the facilitator which i) set the initial mood of the group ii) elicit/clarify the roles of individuals and the group iii) be a flexible resource iv) respond to intellection and emotional needs from the group, disclose personal experience and work to recognise and accept their own limitations (2012, p101-102).

Lee also provides a detailed treatment of the scholarship the *supervisor as mentor*. Lee stress the journey conception (Brew, 2001) and the relationship to mentoring and emancipation and again how the importance of the student journeying from the known and discovering and testing knowledge as highlighted as well as the importance of empathy as the maintaining a level of awareness of the level of directivity and influence the supervisor teacher has over the student (Rogers 1967, pp. 276-277). Type and roles of mentors are discussed, whereby a **primary mentor** provides a more profound experience – moving

somewhat towards the *relationship* concept of supervision. The mentor is effectively a non-judgemental advisor there is wealth of literature available for further reading (Lee, 2006,2007). While the strength of the primary mentorship is to provide acceptance and confirmation that the mentee is worthwhile, seeking to empower him/her a **secondary mentor** takes on a business like or functional role, providing career advice, coaching for particular skills and assist with work based problems. A student needs to ask him/herself what do I want to learn before every meeting with an emancipatory supervisor (mentor) in short what motivates them? (Herman and Mandell,2004). The goal is to disorientate the student with such questions of personal and research motivations in many ways in order to increase their self-efficacy and the emancipatory supervisor (mentor) must take care to “hold the space” for the student, (Zimmerman, Bandura and Martinez- Pons, 1992). Students should be allowed to fail as if they only ever succeed with ease there is no room to develop resilience, “emerging stronger through adversity” (Lee, 2019, p. 106)(Bandura, 1994). Lee also discusses the limits of mentoring and warns of toxic mentoring when a mentor is untrained or lacks self-awareness with respect to their own limitations. Likewise the role may be limited or unsuitable if the supervisor is also a line manager a pure mentorship role must be entered into voluntarily by both parties in order to have profound learning experience (on both sides) (Lee, 2019, p. 107). While mentee’s may benefit the most from the mentoring relationship, mentors can connect and reflect on their own experiences and feelings, experience a sense a “parental pride” and become more effective academics (Lee, 2019, p. 107). Mentoring relationships may end organically i.e. at the end of a research degree programme. An unaware mentor may “cling on” so it is important to regularly review the mentoring relationship and decide on when the formal relationship might end and or evolve into a collaboration/friendship for instance (Lee, 2019, p. 107). The emancipatory approach (including mentorship) is fundamentally transformative as it transforms or reframes the way in which the student approaches their world (“meaning perspective or shared definition of a situation”) in a different and more positive way (Lee, 2019, p. 107).

Relationship Development

This approach to supervision is characterised by friendship and normally both the academic and student will typically anticipate and avert any unnecessary conflict (Lee, 2019, p. 110).

Problems are resolved with the goodwill of both parties and non “overt rationalisation” will require expressing on order resolve a given problem or complete requested tasks. Although boundaries shall be maintained both academic supervisor and postgraduate student may introduce each other to friends and family (Lee, 2019, p. 111). Unsurprisingly, the quality of the relationship plays an important (if not the most important) role in determining student satisfaction (Harkin, 1998, Smith, 1997, Carson 1996). Likewise, poor relationships can result in poor completion rates (Taylor and Beasley, 2005, p. 69). Lee analyses the scholarship surrounding the relationship approach discussing in detail Aristotle’s notions of friendship, *friendship of utility* and his moral virtues of *courage, temperance, liberality, magnificence, friendliness and wittiness* (Lee, 2019, p. 111), as well as the need for positive student/supervisor relationship as evidenced by the qualitative work of Ives and Rowley (2005), the notion of a “working alliance” or productive alliance focused on shared goal/task (Clarkson, 1995) as well as the role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and flexibility in successful completion of postgraduate supervision (Wisker et al, 2003a, 2003b). The four type of EI include: i) perceiving and expressing emotion, ii) understanding emotion, iii) using emotion to facilitate thought and iv) managing emotion in self and others. Conflict management is also discussed in the context of the literature of organisational psychology and coaching. Harrison describes four different ways of managing conflict depending on the context one can apply *avoidance, compromise, compete, accommodate or collaborate* (2002). Hockney recommends explicit contracts should be agreed between student and supervisor and that this an often neglected approach (1996). Moreover the differences in power (as the relationship cannot be an equal), boundaries and limits of confidentiality should be explicitly discussed between student/supervisor(Hawkins, 2006). Friendship at early stage in the supervisory relationship may cause difficulties but after several years of working closely together, it may be unavoidable and in some cases lifelong friendships may develop. However, other academics may experience rejection when this does not transpire (Lee, 2019, p114-115). Academics operating in the relationship dimension are comfortable sharing their own experience and are aware of the appropriate level of self disclosure and are often altruistic with respect to their students and driven by desire to inform, inspire and share and want “more than just a PhD student” in that “they remain in touch” (Lee, 2019, p. 116). Lee discusses also not all academic operating in this dimension have such a sense of responsibility for the personal lives of their students but are nevertheless happy to cross

that boundary if required given that intellectual well being depends on physical and psychological well being (Lee, 2019, p. 117). Lee also discusses the ingredients of creating a healthy relationships (similar to the therapeutic alliance between a psychotherapist and a client) such as the supervisor being helpful, supporting, facilitative and enabling a perception that both academic and student are bonding positively as a team (Grenyer, 2002). Moreover, a proper induction is considered key to creating a positive working alliance/relationship. Lee (2019, pp. 118-120) outlines a skeleton induction programme for postgraduate students (masters and doctoral levels) which can be delivered at group level. Topics include research methods, critical thinking skills, academic and student roles, library skills, academic writing skills, referencing and recoding keeping, expectations concerning feedback and mechanisms for requesting feedback, establishing expectations from supervision, group social event for network building, introduction to academic and administrative teams, student services. Students should be encouraged to use common room , personal desks and equipment so that they feel part of the academic tribe. They should be provided with learning/collaboration spaces to interact and socialise via self led learning groups which may involve studying key papers/journals or even inviting a guest speaker. Lee provides several suggestions to help students overcome isolation and establish their own network which include: small peer groups which self organise and meet regularly, co-leading staff/student departmental research seminars, inviting other academics/students to discuss their work, journal club, student conferences, university outreach and engagement (2019, p. 122). Lee also provides extremely useful checklists for helping students to i) manage their own finances (2019, p. 125) i.e. fees, travel and material costs, stipend/salary realistic, mitigation of delays, writing up as they proceed? and ii) frame their own research proposal (2019, p. 126) i.e. motivations, access to data/participants, ethics, competency of supervision, time, cost, achievable. Finally, Lee provides a rich discussion around i) supporting students through departmental/research unit reorganisations and any distress this may cause. As reorganisation a part of academic life and many postgraduates are aspiring academic, Lee recommends not to pretend that such difficulties commonly experienced by staff are non-existent (2019, p. 127). In addition, Lee strongly encourages supervisors to explore different cultural values within the context of international students especially when their may be cultural desire to prefer harmony over honesty (2019, p. 128). Different cultural values can be explained and

explored and both academic and student can learning enormously from each other thus leading to richer student/supervisor relationship. Lee also recommends various codes of ethical practice including that of the British Psychological Society Code of Conduct (BPS, 2008), (2019, p. 128). Lee also identifies “degenerate” patterns in student/supervisor relations which include: i) intellectual gain in order to enhance their own reputation and claim authorship for little or no contribution ii) commercial gain from the student’s research via invention disclosure of funding bids iii) the obvious problems of sexual gain iv) and the legitimate but sometimes ambiguous nature of friendship gain whereby there is abuse of power or an emotional need by the supervisor which oppressing the student and what courses of action should be taken by the student), (2019, p. 129). Furthermore, Lee advises on the ending of the supervisory relationship i.e. summarise the supervision journey, celebrate, have a conversation on expectations, regular or occasional contact, collaborations (2019, p. 130). Finally, Lee provides a useful self-assessment questionnaire which academic need to ask themselves concerning issues of boundaries that they will or will not cross, availability for non academic matters, levels of support, individual or in-group meetings when and where, avoiding favouritism (2019, p. 131). .

2.2.2 Investigating Supervisory Management Styles (Gatfield, 2005)

Gatfield’s (2005) supervisory management grid, (See Figure 2.2) contains **four** management

Gatfield (2005) p 317

Figure 2.2: Gatfield’s Supervisor Management Grid, (Gatfield, 2005, p.317)

styles placed between two high to low axes, one labelled “support” and “structure”. The four styles are i) **Laissez-faire** [low structure low support] – Supervisor is “non-directive” and not committed to high levels of personal interaction with limited levels of motivation and management provided to the student. The supervisors may “appear” uncaring and uninvolved (Gatfield, 2005, p. 317) ii) **Pastoral** [low structure high support] - The supervisor is concerned with the student’s welfare and provides information however the student is responsible for their research project management and self-structure, so the supervisor is less task driven. The student may have low personal management skills but avails of all support facilities provided by the supervisor iii) **Directional** [high structure low support] - The focus of supervision is the management and direction of the student’s research project but with no provision of pastoral support. The student is highly self-motivated and takes advantage of the structures put in place by the supervisor i.e. project goals, task and deliverable planning and timely completion. The student works independently on own initiative without the need to leverage institutional support. The supervisor maintains a close regular interactive relationship with the student but avoids non-task(personal) issues. iv) **Contractual** [high structure high support] - The supervisor is involved with the management of the student’s research project and, if needed, provides pastoral support (Gatfield, 2005). The supervisor provides direction, and exercises good management skills and interpersonal relationships. The student is again highly motivated, capable of taking direction while also very capable of acting on his or her own initiative. This style is considered the most demanding for the supervisor’s time.

It should be noted that although the supervisor may have a preferred style, it is influenced by the student’s attitude and responses (Gatfield, 2005, p. 318). Likewise the supervisor, will move between a range styles at across stages in the PhD research project, in that the supervisor management grid is dynamic and changes over time (Gatfield, 2005, p. 222). Finally there is strong overlap with the Garfield’s Supervision Grid and Lees Framework for Approaches to research supervision in Figure 1 (Lee, 2019, pp.)

2.2.3 Re-Theorizing doctoral supervision as professional work (Halse and Malfroy, 2010)

In (Halse and Malfroy, 2010) the authors reformulate doctoral supervision as “professional work” The model is informed by language, discourse and theory and based on empirical analyses, doctoral supervision is theorized as professional work that comprises five facets: i) the *learning alliance* which is the agreement between supervisor and student to work towards the common goal i.e. the production of a high quality doctorate. It is a *learning contract* between the supervisor and student, and is equivalent to the ‘therapeutic alliance’ between a patient/client and clinician/patient within the psychotherapeutic/medical context (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 84), ii) *habits of mind*, is described as a both a disposition and mode of behaviour, which involves the capacity to learn and reflect on the principles around making particular decision and how to judge when to apply these same principles for unforeseen or unfamiliar situations in an ethical manner (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 85), iii) *scholarly expertise refers to* “theoretical knowledge acquired through reflection and thinking”. Moreover the doctoral supervisors interviewed in their study all considered that a “deep substantive knowledge of their discipline or specialization was essential for supervising doctoral students” (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 86), iv) *technê*, is understood as craft knowledge, but it is “more than technical skills or instrumental practice”. It is the use of expert knowledge to create, produce –a (possibly new) artefact into existence or accomplish a particular objective, and most importantly to document and account of what has been produced (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 87), and finally v) *contextual expertise*, which is concerning with the possession of knowledge and understanding of the institutional and disciplinary context (or contemporary climate) of doctorate and doctoral education (Halse and Malfroy, 2010, p. 87).

2.2. 4 Threshold concepts experienced by doctoral students and strategies for support Kiley (2009).

Kiley (2009) models the supervision experience from the doctoral students perspective using threshold concepts, which critical learning and development concepts whose threshold must be crossed and must retain the following characteristics of being: *transformative, integrative, irreversible, bounded and troublesome* (Meyer and Land, 2006). In (Kiley, 2009) a postgraduate research student may be in experience the ambiguous “liminal state” – the tension between knowing, not knowing whereby they i) feel *stuck*,

feeling unproductive and unmotivated or ii) mimic at the surface level (mimicry) what their peers are doing. Understanding the key threshold concepts (examples include: *argument, thesis, theory, framework*), within the context of the journey of the postgraduate research journey, which reinforce a liminal state, can facilitate a learning transition (Kiley, 2009, pp 298-299). According to (Kiley, 2009) this can be achieved in collaborative group work via a community of learners/research culture i.e. journal clubs, seminars, writing retreats, reading key theses/dissertations and discussing with peers/supervisor. Other activities include allowing students to control and modify the intensity by which they engage in research tasks i.e. designing small mini assignments which contribute to research plan such summarise, discuss and critique a key paper, reproduce a key experiment/application of theory and discuss. All of the above can assist the student to become *unstuck*.

2.3 Challenges in Remote Supervision

2.3.1 Remote Supervision in Brief

There area of distance or remote(online) supervision is effectively quite under researched and in fact the term itself does not appear to have concrete definition in the literature. Other terms include *e-supervision, telesupervision* the latter, which implies the use of video conferencing to supervise graduate studies (Sussex, 2008). Distance supervision can be delivered **asynchronously** exchange of materials by post, fax, email, and or shared audio/video files, and via shared project manager/content repositories such as Google Drive, Microsoft OneDrive, Basecamp), project wikis, micro blogging (Twitter for sharing publications) and or **synchronously** via video/conferencing (Zoom, Teams, Google Meet), live chat (Skype, Slack) and virtual learning environment (Blackboard, Moodle). If we return to providing definition of distance supervision, given that the research supervision owes its origins to clinical and counselling supervision (Gatfield, 2005, p312)(Gurr, 2001, p. 83) . Publications of remote/distance or “cyber” clinical supervision indicate the accepted definition of clinical supervision “applies to all modalities”, whether supervision is provided face-to-face or electronically using synchronous, or asynchronous methods (Nelson et al., 2010, p. 2). So if we take the traditional model of supervision, which involves a “dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student” which concerned with preparing the

student for independent research. (McCallin and Nayar, 2012, p. 68), a first attempt would define distance/remote supervision as:

“ a dyadic relationship between a supervisor and student which occurs predominately electronically (usually online) using synchronous, or asynchronous methods and is concerned with preparing the student for independent research”

Unwin (2007), provides a rich list of postgraduate supervisor elements and tips on how to adapt them for distance delivery. Ghani, (2020) discusses strategies and highlights technologies for teaching, assessing and supervising graduate students online within the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. A good comprehensive historical overview of research supervision within the context of distance/remote learning is provided in (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). Moreover, the authors clearly state as evidenced by their analysis of the literature that is “widely assumed that there is no difference” between the requirements for completing and PhD/Research Master’s programme on campus or by distance. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1963) and reveals that there has been little exploration into the challenges, complexities and difficulties of conducting distance research degree programmes let alone the potential benefits to student and supervisor, which we explore in the section. Finally, although numerous universities have produced policy documents on what processes to follow in order to formally engage in remote supervision (i.e. forms, number of meetings online/face to face – every 6 months etc), they tend do not offer practical guidance remote supervision. However, the UK Council For Graduation does provide a very comprehensive guide, which is evidence based by the scholarship of distance learning and research supervision to our knowledge (Kumar et al. , 2020).

2.3.1 Remote Supervision, Challenges and Strategies (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015)

Nasri and Mafakheri (2015), provide an excellent overview of challenges with respect to remote or distance research supervision which include *lack of depth or delicacy*, as discussed in communication as result of distractions caused by the fast pace of technology changes and the need to explore the latest technology instead of focusing on the research. The dislocation effect results in the likelihood that this a lack of personal knowledge and

hence rapport between student and supervisor and there is no opportunity for informal discussion with the possibility of decreased engagement and motivation on both sides. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015). However, differences in computer (software or hardware) literacy can reinforce the effect of dislocation and the appetite for interaction (Sussex, 2008; Williams et al, 2011). The reduced appetite for interaction can be compounded by the challenge of *time differences*, if students/supervisors are in different countries/regions which may have an “imbalances” with respect to IT capacity. This can create a more serious challenge for part time students (often in the case of those enrolled in masters degrees) who are working professionals and have limited time to spend on resolving IT problems (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1964).

Supervisors may *experience increased workload* as they expected have high online availability. Furthermore, they must often act as institutional gatekeepers for the distance student which demands them to remain up to date with research degree requirements, ethics, university services (library facilities, funding opportunities, student services, counselling services, IT facilities, research seminars, postgraduate training. This is necessity as the institutional gatekeeper in order to be ready to provide “timely” guidance to students on pastoral and administrative matters (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965; Unwin, 2007). Furthermore in order the ensure flawless and constant communication, the supervisor may have to work closely with IT services.

As distance students, unlike campus students, do not have the opportunity to interact with other peers and colleagues, there is a risk that this *isolation* may result in ignorance, lack of focus and an *overdependence* on the supervisor on the student’s part, which may impact negatively on the students capacity to develop i) **critical thinking** skills and ii) their research independently (**emancipation**) (See Section 2.2.1) (Crossouard. 2008).

Remote supervision is also vulnerable to cultural misunderstanding, as it crosses geographical and cultural borders, which can result in misinterpretation, confusions and even conflicts with respect to race, gender and religion (**enculturation**, See Section 2.2.1) between the supervisor and the student (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965; Sussex, 2008, Wisker, 2007). The supervisor must be prepared to develop his/her awareness of cultural norms, difference, preconceptions and potential conflicting issues.

Distance postgraduate students coming from different cultures may have particular expectations with respect to supervision and models in the context of the student/teacher relationship. Students from some cultures may expect a collectivistic (teacher centred) relationship while others are used to a individualistic (student centred) relationship (Ventor, 2003).

A obvious challenge can results *technical barriers* with respect to communication tools with the need to use various asynchronous/synchronous communication tools due to the lack of face to face contact and it can be “delicate” task to find the “optimal blend” of communication channels (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966). This is critical to develop a rich **relationship** (See Section 2.2.1) between supervisor and supervisee as well as to ensure persistent and recoverable delivery of information between both parties(Fox, 2002). The collective use of such varied communication channels can suffer naturally from technical issues and limitations such as problems with: internet bandwidth, hardware limitations, accessing good quality web cameras, audio/video difficulties, memory requirements, data storage, remote access to hardware, and computer viruses and spyware (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966).

There may be *linguistic barriers* as a result of linguistic gap in either side from a lack of fluency, notwithstanding barriers in the content varying technical language standards with respective the discipline or research field such as Engineering (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965)

Finally *feedback systems may suffer* whereby student/supervisor tend to be distracted from each other as results of being in difference locations. Hence both parties may “forget” about mutual expectations and responsibilities. This may result in a decline in feedback frequency and quality. In addition, fewer interactions introduces the risk of misinterpretation and varied expectations with respect to addressing feedback (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1965)

Nasri and Mafakheri (p. 1966, 2015) discusses a number of potential strategies for addressing these challenges but they clearly state that there is limited evidence in the literature to support them. **Strategies** include:

- Hierarchical feedback systems (Unwin, 2007) from accepting track changes in documents for longer feedback, to audio file monologues to deliver opinionated feedback. Caution should be advised with track changes as students may accept the feedback thus eliminating constructive debate, hence a comment prompting dialogue and discussion (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1966)
- Stricter deadlines with respect submission of progress reports and feedback on both sides (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967)
- Have an open debate with respect to expectation on “means, depth and timing” of supervisor- supervisee interactions and experiment with the various options (Andrews, 2012).
- Address lack of peer interaction and peer feedback by creating mailing lists for sharing research materials, use social media platforms to great a group research Facebook albeit internal access to virtual learning environment such Blackboard/Moodle with discussion boards may also be an option. The supervisor can organise virtual peer meetings and an annual local web based research conference is another option. International conferences are also occasions where face-to-face meetings can occur and they also provide the student with effective opportunity to acquire international contacts and collaborations thus reducing the reliance on the supervisor sides (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967). The supervisor can also identify quality research groups or labs at local university or research institutions so that the student will have the opportunity to gain additional peer feedback (Wisker, 2007).
- To address the lack of in-house training opportunities, dedicated pages should be created on the universities website or virtual learning environment(Moodle, Blackboard). It should induction, resource material, recorder seminars and training sessions. A dedicated virtual induction is recommended for distance students (Unwin 2007; Wisker 2007). It should include a web-link, liver streaming seminar introducing the postgraduate research programme requirements, advice for students on any mandatory online courses to take (i.e. research ethics and integrity, intellection property management), IT resources, library resources, student support services, student (remote) counselling services. Separate formal sessions can be

organised to discuss issues such as research methods, diversity and cultural issues. (Nasri and Mafakheri, 2015, p. 1967).

- Finally, it is also recommended that course leader or tutor should be appointed to support the postgraduate distance learning programme in order to provide pastoral and administrative support to students, thus easing the administrative burden on supervisors (Paran et al. 2020)

2.4 Analytic Conclusions

In general we make the following observation with respect to research gaps concerning the literature and scholarship surrounding research supervision and remote research supervision:

- The modules of supervision analysed in Section 2.2 in general do not appear to have been developed with distance/remote supervision in mind. Moreover they have not been applied to remote distance supervision so there is open question with respect to their robustness and fitness for purpose. In short this how do this models translate to online/distance learning space?
- Another question how “digitally aware” are these models? For instance what learning and communication technologies, asynchronous and synchronous teaching online activities map to Lee’s (2019) framework concepts of supervision and where? Hence a worthwhile exercise would involve conducting research into developing a *digitally annotated* model for research supervision.
- Another interesting research question is how well Lee’s (2019) concepts of supervision translate to the science, technology and engineering discipline. The model is general and rightly so and it may be worthwhile exercise to explore a methodology on how to instantiate a framework for specific disciplines thus ensuring better adoption.
- Supervision models and supervisor pedagogy in general tend to focus on a one-to-one ,face-to-face relationship between the supervisor and supervisee i.e. the full time campus based student pursuing a four year PhD Degree. The scholarship on supervision does not appear to differentiate between the PhD and the MSc by Research/MPhil degree and there appears to be an *implicit assumption* in the literature that the models,

which apply to the PhD, apply also to the research masters. This also appears to be case for the **professional doctorate** (DPsych, EdD, EngD), which although they consist of a significant taught often contain group research projects/practica.

- Likewise the literature is lacking around the application of existing supervision models to **cohort/group supervision** of PhDs either face to face or remotely. This is particular the case with respect to the professional doctorates.
- There is less of focus in the literature at taught masters (Anderson et al., 2007, 2008) or undergraduate levels (Brew, 2010; Cullen, 2009)
- More research is required to explore the negative effect of distance learning in the context of remote supervision on the supervision process and the student with respect to Lee's (2019) concepts of **critical skills** and **emancipation** (student independence).
- Remote supervision is under in general researched and given the current Covid-19 pandemic this research is timely.
- Hierarchical feedback systems (Unwin, 2007) require more detailed exploration and empirical validation i.e. what processes/technologies work best, when and for which type of postgraduate student?

I have conducted detailed literature review of Research Supervision Pedagogy and Remote Supervision having compared and contrasted key models of research supervision (Section 2.2) and analysed what the scarce literature surrounding remote supervision, including the challenges and potential strategies to address (Section 2.3). Finally, I provided analytic conclusions and identified research gaps in the field which field directly into research questions. Lee's (2019) framework for research supervision is arguably the richest and well researched, however it is perhaps less accessible to the novice than Gatfield's (2005) supervisory grid which is more agile but perhaps less generalizable. Regardless both models are well aligned (Lee, 2019, p. 19) and more structured and suitable and better suited to support reflective thematic analysis and our research methodology, which I move now to discuss in the next Chapter.

Appendix G: Extended Descriptive Analysis of Themes

G2.1 Theme: Concepts of Remote Supervision

Theme Name: Concepts of Remote Supervision

Description: This theme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concepts of Supervision (2019) (Section 2.1 and how they translated to remote research supervision.

SubThemes: Research Enculturation, Critical Skills, Student-Supervisor Relationship, Structured-Functional, Emancipation

SubTheme Name: Research Enculturation

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of research **Enculturation** (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision.

Codes: *serendipity-spontaneity, conference-attendance-networking, research-placement-internship, online-group-meetings, physical-lab-experience, peer-support/peer-le, career-development*

Code: : serendipity-spontaneity

This code is concerned with what supervisors experience as the absences of chance (office door, water cooler), serendipitous or spontaneous meetings with students and which are common when conducting campus based research and supervision. Examples from participants include:

"often **rely on kind of chance you know chance ad hoc interactions**"

"students knew they had to **give a quick update** on **what they've been doing**"

"**a chance for them to grab me if they had those quick questions**"

students were able to reach "**out for whatever problem**",

"**spontaneous chats like** in the hallwayI find would more important for like the building up a rapport with the student"

"you **would have been sparking ideas**, and I would have pulled that pieces of paper and coloured pens,"

"**maybe just discuss** about some **new technique**"

However, working online means according for one supervisor that they would

“think twice before sending email because I don't want to spamand I think that there is less” spontaneity.

The same applies to the loss of chance meetings between academics which lead to collaborations:

“I don't have the chance meetings with other academics anymore, that lead to ideas like when's the last time any of you here have been doorstopped by Professor John Doe”

I call it the John Doe effect , you're in your office and eating your sandwich right and bang bangthat's gone now I haven't had John Doe effect moment in about 18 months.

Code: conference-attendance-networking

This code is concerned with the loss of physical conference attendance (as a result of Covid) and networking as part of research enculturation of research students.

One supervisor mentioned that as a result of Covid-19 restrictions “conference travel” is not happening at the moment and I think that is affecting PhD students, especially those who are just finishing up”

Although students can attend conference online the supervisor argues that they are not the equivalent.

“they're going to conferences online and the networking opportunities just aren't the same there”.

Some conferences have provide digital avatars and students can the supervisor is not convinced “you can go around and talk to people but sounds awful”

With respect to the physical conference it provides a mechanism for the supervisor to enculturate the student

“you know you can introduce them to people that you know, on the field.

in other cases is more valuable....., because a lot of time to be with students want to move on, andspread their wings and so and that's a big thing that's missing.

Regardless of Covid-19 for the remote student to be properly enculturated he/she would benefit from attending conferences physically at the same time as their supervisor to avail of introductions and networking opportunities.

Code: group-meetings.

This code is concerned with the discussions arising about how to organise online video conference group with research students in order to facilitate research enculturation. Negative experiences of supervisors include:

“the group meeting is moved to fortnightly because we found people just finding it to much in the group meeting”

and

“we've got it online we've had to move it to be fairly structured because we just found people weren't coming and you can't do that ourselves and kind of grabbing free at the door, we lost that.”

With respect conducting group meetings to practice presentation talks and discuss the methodologies and technologies, the same supervisor found that:

“attendance really dropped off, so we said it's too hard to keep up with everybody else's stuff and they found it really annoying and boring”

Another supervisor modified their group meeting structure in response to a student's feedback Which i.e. “one of my students and I really appreciate itYou know that it was just too hard to concentrate for that long, and we should just do status updatesthen leave the discussion to the end,which is something that we never did in the face to face”.

“they were kind of waiting for their turn,they ended up just not like it wasn't very pleasant experience.... having to wait like an hour”.

Another supervisor agreed i.e. I think you're right ...there is a bit of a i'm waiting for my turn that's the only time I have to be doing stuff and then the camera goes off.....”

However, the previous supervisor indicated that the camera being turned off likely because the group knew each other prior to moving online. So this was not an issue however it was likely that keeping the camera on did impact on concentration.

“in that group meeting people don't turn the camera off because I think they know each other quite well and I would kind of be strange thing to do, but I think that made it harder for them to concentrate,

The supervisor's experience of online group meetings was positive for managing research student cohorts online i.e. “I have seven students and some of them are supervised and they still attend the meetings actually” The supervisor also indicated that the group meeting fostered collaboration between students i.e. one to one meetings between my students and that might not have happened if it wasn't for that:

Another senior academic described how they “have a weekly group meeting which is far more

relaxed, we can have a journal club , more often than not breaks downthings go different directions right and everyone has a cup of tea”.

The supervisor does not attend the group meeting every second week as this meeting is facilitated by a senior PhD who is a mature student and is “brilliant ... she's just really organized very social very smart and she's kind of created the energy in that group”.

The outcome of this discussion is that enculturation of research students could be facilitated well by allowing senior researcher students/postdoctoral research to organise a less formal research group (See theme: Modalities of Supervision under *online-interaction* for a related discussion).

The academics in the group recognised the value of this i.e. it's a good idea, I think I might try something similar...” but that it was “critical is, as you say you can really switched on senior PhD or a postdoc who can help who's not the professor.

Group dynamics play a role and/gender may perhaps play a role but this is speculative

“you know it just depends on the group this group happens to be I noticed the guysaren't very good at doing it” while one online group consisting of five females “very good at it” with respect to self facilitation of their bi-weekly research group meeting.

Another supervisor also compares their negative experience with another supervisor who had a positive experience with online group supervision i.e. “you and I kind of had the opposite responses”

Finally one supervisor argued that online group meetings are easier to organise i.e.

“Its kinda harder to not be there because they all have it in their calendar it's a zoom in their calendar, the barrier to entry is so flipping low you are at home, what else you're going to do, you know”

Code: lab-experience-physical-lab-placement

The code is concerned with the overall importance of the physical lab experience and its role in the research enculturation of the postgraduate student and how is this is missing in remote supervision. It links closely the theme of **Research Infrastructure** (access-to-lab).

One supervisor felt “ he lab experience is too ...important to be removed, out of the PhD and it can be feasible for some short period, but it shouldn't be the normal way”

Another agreed the stating the loss of the ability of the research student being able to observe and model off the supervisor as well as senior colleagues/PhDs and socialise with colleagues as a result of distance learning at the postgraduate research level.

I'd agree with that, I think we've talked about the lack of spontaneity and that kind of serendipitous discoveries at the coffee machine or over lunch or then that's where that enculturation stuff, I think, not just from observing your supervisor, but also from discussing stuff with your peers or gaining experience from ones who are.., a year or two ahead of you....if we were to move to solely remote supervision, apprenticeship/enculturation would be more difficult,

One supervisor felt that enculturation was not possible online:

I think the enculturation point is totally missing in zoom , like, I cannot see any way that you can do this kind of role modelling apprenticeship.

While another stated the distance learning impacted on the students ability to mix and learn from each other as stated earlier and this would have significant impact on the research.

I personally think ignoring a massive elephant ...in the roomthey're not getting that experience of mixing as much as they would have right... I don't think the learning off each other.... how do we get them together again get students to get to start talking together

An interesting discussion emerged with respect to the supervisors perceptions of the lab experience which is generational. In other words there is not much difference between a physical lab experience and distance learning in that younger student may well enculturate online

One senior supervisors experience of the lab environment was:

“10 years ago now, it used to be crazy hectic high energy people jumping around playing football, even in the lab and playing music... very high energy place”

Nowadays however the same supervisor perceives that lab differently:

“you're going to lab all the students have their headphones in and they're living there actually just talking to their friends online, you know they're not interested in that mode so maybe it depends on the lab”

Supervisors agreed despite the capacity to interact online that there was some face-to-face interaction happening in the lab:

“I kind of agree with you, about that.... I don't actually see them talking that much to each other, but I do think that they are having lunch together and going for coffee together”

“They can are aware of each other's presence”

“there's definitely some level of interaction there”

Supervisors reported that students miss the social contact in lab but their social contact maybe online, perhaps this is not an issue:

“others will just say, miss social contact right, but you know if their social contact is online”,

As a workaround some supervisors place the remote student in a laboratory (and even earn credits) where they have existing collaborations, which appears to be a useful solution to fostering enculturation :

“any of my students that are abroad... I've put them in other universities labs abroad..”

“just find some university advisor right, ... an internship there....get some credits”

“just stick her in some lab nearby”

Supervisors commented that the university bureaucracy surrounding how to facilitate a research placement which was credit bearing was barrier. They describes the form to complete the process as

“its a really long one...”

“no it's torture trying to fill it out...”

There is also the risk however that a student may not wish to return to the university campus where the PhD is hosted, as one supervisor described:

“And she's doing fine like it's not a problem that's partly why we haven't panicked but she's great and, as she says to me her Internet access is far better and her place ...where she is living is far more comfortable than what she has in Ireland so she's not real keen to come back and finish off”

Code: peer-support-peer-led

This code captures supervisors' discussions around the impact of conducting postgraduate research students remotely on peer support in the context of research enculturation.

One supervisor comments how the benefits of a face to face research group meeting and how it fostered peer support.

The supervisor “...set up the group meeting because one of my other students will be able to answer their questions, better than I could, because there will be ...something related to an experimental detail that I just couldn't I couldn't help them

The supervisor described the benefits of continuing group supervision online because:

“for the students... to help each other, and I think that's particularly important am at the moment because we're not seeing each other..... that's been really helpful so used to be obviously face to face but and we kept it going and i'm really glad that we that we just”

One supervisor agreed in the context of online research group that was peer-led and or led by a senior PhD Researcher and has not generated peer support activities:

“So that seems to work and then I also encourage them now to meet in pairs and I don't force it I just have encouraged thattry and take away from spoke model, so you don't need to come to me to talk to her.

As well as encouraging students to

“just set up your own meetings”

The same supervisor commented that “they kind off become friends kind of like subsets of them, you know and they enjoy just doing that”

Another supervisor commented that peer support was a key by product of the physical lab experience and was not convinced that this was being replicated on line.

“when a student goes to the lab is not just the lab its the fact that they can talk with so many other people about their PhD and sometimes you know the Supervisor is just the last resort for solving some problems. Because they can check with other PhD student postdoc and so and i'm not so sure that, right now, they are having that kind of support from other peers.

The supervisor made an interesting comment in that they are hesitant to “bother” a student spontaneously online and would assume the same is among their peers:

“I think about myself my I’m doing the same like before bothering someone else with emails and slack I think twice...” See (**Supervision Modalities**: online-interaction)

“ probably they're (the students) doing the same so they're lacking also this kind of experience “so they are lacking, you know basically lots of interaction”

SubTheme Name: Student-Supervisor Relationship

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleamed from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee’s Concept of Relationship (2019) ((See Section 2.2.1))and how it translates to remote research supervision. The subtheme is with the challenges surrounding boundaries and the rapport between student and supervisor and the effect of the lack-of physical context on their student supervisor relationship

Codes: *rapport-relationship, boundaries-of-supervision, lack-of--physical-context*

Code: rapport-relationship

Description: This code is captures the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to the impact of remote supervision on their relationship or rapport with students.

Supervisors in general feel something is missing:

“because you don't have that personal interaction that feels like and everything has to be very formally done and discussed in the meeting it's just lacking”

“I feel a little bit disconnected”

“but I feel like there's something missing out”

They also find it strange that there are some students that they have never met and do not have “some level of personal knowledge about the student”. They find it a

"It can be a bit strange."

"....that I never met so it's weird."

One supervisor misses not being "able to have a few minutes, with a student" each day" as was the case with campus based supervision.

Another supervisor felt that the relationship had become directorial and task orientated:

"ess of a conversation like you'd have one, you know you're walking over to coffee and a lot more about here, where the tasks last week"

One supervisor states that remote supervision demands being more involved in the supervisee's issues regardless of whether the supervisor is comfortable or not with the situation.

"You know that may mean that you have to listen to them for a bit talking about whatever problem they may have"

"I think that's part and parcel of where we are now it's it's it's something I would prefer not to get involved in..."

This links into the code *boundaries-of-supervision* .

One supervisor is able to compensate for this by sharing mobile contact details with students which helps to foster *sponteniety-serenditpy* in the relationship.

"They ring me anytime and that's how we've kind of evolved to working but, and that gives us that spontaneity "

Another supervisor comments sharing numbers is symbol of trust between supervisor and supervisee

"the phone number part it's almost like a - if you build up the rapport to get to that point where it's almost like the rite of passage, I know you - here is the number to contact me kind of thing."

Another supervisor comments that there is less of an issues in relationship building with fourth year students that they had a previous face-to-face relationship with.

"For the other students, I know that because she's in the fourth year there was this long term relationship going on, and she she she's very open with me, so I don't have that type of problem but."

With other students at early stages the same supervisor felt that"

“It could be like a **problem for the others,**”

“I don't know **really what are they struggling**...like if they have some some some family problems at home, for example, that prevent them from working.”

Furthermore the supervisor felt that distance online learning prevented students from confiding in the supervisor:

“In addition like many of the students actually going through a lot of struggle, **but they may feel not comfortable in talking with you** about that”.

Code: boundaries –of-supervision

Description: This code captures the uncertainty created for supervisors by remote supervision in relation to the what are the appropriate boundaries of supervision. Supervisors are for example unsure how to manage the blurring of boundaries in the supervision relationship as result of supervising online and demanded to act as institutional gatekeepers for student wellbeing and moving what they feel is beyond their role of academic supervisor:

“The the level of **separation between you,** as a supervisor and the **students has changed** I know there's there's discussions about how much a supervisor should be you know ..be knowledgeable or be invested **or involved in your your students life outside of the PhD**”

“Others say that you, you should be **on kind of dinner conversation level** with your students”

“I've had to **deal with stuff over** the last year, which **has really been quite personal knowledge** for some of my students**bereavements to deal with Covidwho've had all this stuff**

One supervisor expressed concern as to being unsure as to what was expected of them formally

“**this wasn't my role, I was just meant to be helping you** get through this (PhD Programme)

“Should **it be should not be?**”

Another supervisor commented that taking on such a pastoral or involved role very depends on the student's context:

“....it sort of **depends on the students like** with some of my studentsthey **have a lot of support** outside.... of their study and and they might be **living with their parents**might have their own **family.**

However the same supervisor made valid point the in some situations regardless of the supervisor preference that some involvement in non-PhD issues are unavoidable:

“I don't **really know... have an answer** to what like **how much you should get involved** in that or whether we **you find out these things and kind of ARE involved**”.

Code: loss-of-physical-context

Description

This code captures supervisors' explicit frustrations caused by the lack of physical contextual information as a result of remote supervision and how this impacts the supervision relationship. For example, many supervisors discussed their concerns for student health and their inability to assess the situation remotely.

"I have **no other insights other than seeing an email in the morning** to judgment call on their sleeping patterns"

when you're **working remotely you don't have the usual physical cues**

While with campus based supervision:

"You can **just get a sense of what's going on from the everyday**" interactions in the lab.

"all **those cues are gone**the ecological.... **the context for your everyday is gone**"

"and just as a lot, **I can't see if I only have zoom** and"

"you know what it'd be **expecting to see** (the student) **every day and just be able to monitor the situation** in some way, "

y"ou notice there's a few days(the student) **not turning up at their desk.**"

One supervisor felt disconnected from their students and not seeing them as real and not being able to assess their facial cues through a camera:

"like you know **I don't see you as a person it's very hard to you know, look at your face through**a camera and **pick up on all the on the dozens of things like** whether or not this is working .."

SubTheme Name: Critical Skills

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors' understanding of Lee's Concept of Critical Skills (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision.

Codes: *discussion-feedback, brainstorming-critical-thinking*

Code: *discussion-feedback*

Description: This code is with the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to providing feedback for example:

“tried to do is to have them, for example, to write down things, because then I can keep on that some **feedback but it's much more limited**”

Another supervisor commented:

“i've **given my answer back and then the following week** you find that they've **completely misunderstood you....** i'm **finding this a lot projects**”

This was supported by another supervisor:

there's there's this this issue **of not being sure the students have understood us and not being sure that we've understood the students.**

And another supervisor also supported how they are unsure if they are being understood:

“thinking **that i've got the point across to the students that they they've asked the question I think i've understood what they wanted**”

In relation to sharing information online between supervisor and student one supervisor commented negatively that there is

“**less opportunity I think for sharing really** idea so normally if I was in a lab and I was reading some interesting paper...”

There was a general consensus that is was difficult to have discussions with students online i.e.

“think everyone's exactly right **it's it's just really hard to to have discussions on zoom** as as we're discovering it in this focus group right”

“there is less opportunity for talking actually out new things”

“Just that **doesn't happen,** **it becomes very much I can what have you done last week, what are you gonna do next week, so the critical discussion and critical issues is just not prioritized** in in that kind of a time slot that we have so **that's that's particularly tough**”

Code: brainstorming-critical-thinking

Description: This code captures the frustration experienced by supervisors in relation to effectively conceptualising and brainstorming about a research problem with a student online (as form of critical thinking) contrast to face to face supervision. For example “**is more critical thinking like brainstorming and find zoom terrible like I am struggling so much**”

“**I would love to have a whiteboard I know there is a (virtual) whiteboard but it's just brutal like it doesn't work**, I found the same thing with my masters students sometimes they lack some knowledge, so I tried to explain it **and just doesn't work like** you need some support That is just frustrating.

Another supervisor mentioned in relation to trying different devices for brainstorming with little success:

i've tried, a **number of different devices have a one of these pen things** that goes on a pad but again it's : clunky difficult to write with and frustrating actually

One supervisor commented how critical discussion around research problems can not go a deep as result of the absence of face to face supervision (the whiteboard) i.e.

“what we were just talking about the lack of the **whiteboards means sometimes we don't go as deep as we should.... that are more easily done using whiteboards, which is a shame.**”

Again this was supported by the supervisor who commented at the beginning above in that they felt unable to “**to helpstudents to scope out things like you know, to have them reasoning like** when when **they're hitting a wall it's very hard to have them navigate possible solutions**, soeverything must go through some sort of (online) structure.

This was supported by other participants in the supervisors are unable to “intervene” with a students critical thinking if it needs adjusting when a student has hit a “**cul de sac or in some type of a mental loop and frustrated with something**” and being unable to “intervene and **knock them out or just give them a different perspective**”

Another example of this is when other supervisors felt that they were unable to “**....analyze something with the students, particularly early** on, where you're trying to get into

explore ideas and to come up with suggestions”
as well as being unable to come up with list of issues and problems to discuss and think about critically when working online compared to interacting face to face i.e.
“some kind of just a list of things to do you want me to probe you and really flesh out your thinking
.....it is very difficult when they're not there in the room”

SubTheme Name: *Functional-Structured*

Description: This subtheme refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee’s Concept of Functional supervision (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision. The subtheme is concerned with the experiences of supervisors with having to apply more structures to their supervision style as result of the move to online/remote supervision.

Codes: structured-planning, meeting-minutes-note-taking

Code: *structured-planning*

Description: This code captures supervisors experience of applying more structures and project planning to their supervision style as result of move to remote supervision.
Supervisors discussed how they had been applying more structures and using synchronous online collaborative documents(Google Docs), project dashboards to track progress, and scheduled Zoom (video conferencing meeting)

“I think it sounds like we're all doing someGoogle Doc..”

For some supervisors, research activities are broken down into tasks.

“like a task that might be something likelook into approaches for this or find.....very much as tasks, you know, read the paper least, learn these technologies”

One supervisor maintained that more structure was a side effect of remote supervision:

“So if they're not actually seeing them on a day to day basismeans that you have to have ...more slight more hands on approach when it comes to actually supervising”

“would they be better with some form of project dashboard which kept track of what they were doing like we do with the taught masters students i'm not sure I just throw it out there.”

It raised the question on the future of the Phd and if a remote Phd should be more structured similar to a professional doctorate.

“that's just a sort of a general kind of question about where it's (remote supervision) going”

One supervisor commented on how the organic experience of the PhD was not becoming too project managed as a result of supervision and so this a negative:

....like an organic spread them where they come back to you with their own ideas to do their own research, now I feel like having that as like an itemized task - it feels like it's lending more towards project manager, even the students' research and getting up to speed or reading the papers".

Many supervisors might start out with functional approach but then become move to an apprenticeship model:

"looking at that model you shared I kind of feel almost like I would start at the functional and move my way through...." the other models of supervision.

One supervisor felt the additional structure was beneficial:

"the regularity of having these one to one even over zoom meetings as probably in quite beneficial in most cases."

The supervisor also indicated that they have become more scheduled orientated and protective of this time:

"I'm far more disciplined about my time as a result of all these zooms and everything i'm so calendar drivenschedule driven but i'm like a battery chicken right, but you know I can lay an egg on command!"

"you know I'm far more far more careful about that time"

Furthermore, some supervisors had become more regimented. Two supervisors were

"supervising student together but it's like religiously every Tuesday evening we meet up and and it's the same most of the other students that i've got".

Many supervisors commented that the move to distance/online learning and caused a shift from low structure to high structure in supervision style:

"way we're living on zoom now we've gone from low structure to high structure so everybody's been shifted"

The shift was considered beneficial by the same supervisor:

it looks to be a good thing right..... OK, for me personally it's been a good thing

what zoom has definitely made me more disciplined on regard meetings and ensuring that we do meet them every week because it has reduced my stress a wee bit actually

The supervisor also felt that the shift provided students with structure which they perhaps "craved"

(similar to a parent- child relationship)when studying by distance/online for instance “It might give them know predictability or consistency”I’m thinking of parenting right now it’s a consistency”

Finally, one supervisor commented that although supervisors could be more structured it did not automatically mean that they need to be directorial or task orientated. Hence the creation of this code in contrast to *deliberate-directorial* under the theme of **Supervision-Styles** i.e.

“Moving to that high structure in terms of meetings doesn’t change or necessarily change your style of supervision”

Another supervisor confirmed this:

“It shouldn’t affect my it doesn’t change my personality now for sure yeah. “

Code: meeting-minutes-note-taking

Description: This code captures supervisors’ experience of encouraging students to take efficient notes in order to reduce cognitive overload. Students are often asked by supervisors to use a collaborative document editor such as Google docs to:

“leave a comment...., but I make a point that they shouldn’t be long,

“wrap it up a...100 words it’s a quick stream of consciousness, just that we have some continuity as we’re going along “

“so I’m trying to encourage them to even if it’s just three points that we discussed actions they are going to take”

Another supervisor mentioned that this approach

“is a lifesaver to know what we discussed last time just even to jog our memories and bring us back on to the same points”

Other tools are discussed such as used software code repositories (gitlab) or hyperlinks to Google Slides i.e.

“I have this co student and she’s using git lab and doing a magnificent job of having this wonderful rolling set of notes”

“use Google slides so that means that I’ve got a link that I go to for meetings, I can see, they put their results in they’ve got bullet points as to what they’re working on”.

"Good note taking was raised by one supervisor as beneficial for managing supervision workload: I personally find it easier, where I’ve got students that take good notes”

Code: Emancipation

Description: This code refers to the insights gleaned from the data which related to supervisors understanding of Lee's Concept of Emancipation (2019) (See Section 2.2.1) and how it translates to remote research supervision. There is little data on this concept hence it does not warrant the level of a subtheme.

Supervisors are not too concerned with the emancipation would supported by the distance but also supported by being part of an online research group (enculturation):

"I mean it could be easier to be emancipated if it's all remote"

"I'd say the emancipation, supported by the enculturation and being being part of a group"

Another supervisor demonstrated concerns that current students may not fully understand the nature of the PhD in that it requires research independence and the ability to think creatively i.e:

The supervisor felt that the existing group was a "cohort of students who have not really learned in my view, what the doctorate is"

The supervisor felt that "students should have that sort of imagination side of things I'm a little bit concerned might be stifling that a little"

G2.2 Theme: Student-Wellbeing-performance

Theme Name: Student-Wellbeing-performance

Description: This theme refers to impact of conducting remote research and learning on student wellbeing in terms of mental health (isolation experienced by students), the progress of students in relation to their studies and their overall experience.

Codes: *student-mental-health, student-progress, student-isolation*

Code: : student-mental-health,

Description: This code captures the effect of distance learning on student mental health *from the perspective of the supervisor*. For instance one supervisors states in relation to students in the final year of their research degree i.e. one or two of them are writing up they've just shut themselves off, and you can see the the the impact on their mental health. The supervisor wonders if there is "psychological damage to overdoing the online presence". However as the same time the participant commented that perhaps "we over estimating the impact on students who are more savvy on social media or far more used to that as a way of communicating - are far more used to the principle of connecting online" and "this a terrible situation are we just making something a little

worse than it actually is, "... So there may be a different perceptions across different generations (See *code:online-interaction*).

Another supervisor describes the concerns raised by a student's parents i.e. his parents were **actually quite worried about** him and they wanted him to leave Ireland". On a positive note the student organised an internship in the home country which the supervisor felt **"was a really good idea"** and "when that happened like **there's just no question that and I wasn't going to dissuade him from going"**

"he's still in COUNTRY and meeting him once a fortnight and it's **going fine and i'm really, really glad** that he left"

Many of the participants raised the problem of being unable to assess the mental health of the postgraduate within a remote context which would not be in issue in physical context and cues (links to *code: to loss-of-physical-context*) i.e.

With campus based research and study:

"You know by their **posture you know, by the way, that they're hitting the keyboard that they're agitated and you might see it**, a few times throughout the day that **you could pick up on"**

"just naturally **came to our senses** of being around people and **don't have to reach people**, and"

while with remote supervision:

"I find that this **disconnect makes it very difficult** like I don't know when I land into a zoom meeting and I **haven't seen the students in the week I don't have any context** about their **their mental state**, things **I would have noticed as well in the past**, like if you notice that the studentvery consistently turning off at their desk at nine o'clock.....and I also **don't know in** the way that to present themselves, maybe **they're putting on their and happy SMILEY face"**

It is also difficult for supervisors to know or assess when "you **should be intervening or not**, when all you have is" the student **"putting on a good face"**.

Some supervisors feel compelled to take on a parental role (links to subtheme of **Student-Supervisor-Relationship**) in order to assess the mental health of the student and being quite directorial by running through a mental health checklist i.e. you're almost **you feel like a parent** and "the student come in, and you know you might ask them questions like **you went to bed early yeah**

eight you got outside yeah yes, you know, like you're doing the mental health checklist like" and "you're running through these things as well just even like to get a base idea of mental health for the student"

This would not be the case with on campus supervision where the supervisor "wouldn't have to do that, you'd see they are in at nine And you can see them at lunch.... they're eating"

Code: : *student-performance*

Description: This code captures the effect of distance learning on student performance from the perspective of the supervisor. There was some concern on the progress of students raised for instance one supervisor felt "I suppose it's slowing things up a little bit....you're concerned about the progress" and that students have a "tendency if they don't see you in the office to actually forget that they have to try and push themselves a little further forward. The supervisor argued with on campus supervision "if they if they see you every day they feel they should do something" while with remote supervision the supervisor felt "if you don't meet them regularly.... that can be that gap between the supervision and their response". In addition the supervisor mentioned that in one case that it was stressful for one student to make progress "persevere we're trying to get his work done and get across the line, so you can get back to back home to see his family... its tough ...spent a month in isolation in a small apartment.

Another supervisor commented how it very difficult assess the students progress when supervising remotely on the students may "go through the motions but Im not sure what's going on it on in between, and I suspect there's problems"

Code: : *student-supervisor-isolation*

Description: This code capture the experience of isolation from result research postgraduates (and in some cases supervisors) engaged in distance learning *from the perspective of the supervisor*. Although it links heavily with *student-mental-health*, we assign the topic a separate code as it is quite prominent.

One supervisor's perspective on student isolation was that students are" really suffering" and "that student earlierwas really suffering right loneliness was the big issue right...."

"the loneliness thing I fully agree" as confirmed

With respect to the supervisor's experience of supervision one supervisor felt "there's a bit more of a disconnect" and in some cases that there is "incredibly low support and (we are) not meeting them at all"

Many supervisors found it strange that they have not physically ever met some of their supervisees "one i've never ever met in person he moved to Dublin"

"other (supervisors) got students they've they've never actually met."

This is less of a concern about students with whom the supervisor has had an existing campus based supervisor-supervisee relationship, whereby remote supervision in this context has had less of a negative effect i.e.

"the others are ones that i've had two or three years for them to get to know my style ...do people feel that's made a difference"

G2.3 Theme: Supervisor Wellbeing

Theme Name: *Supervisor Wellbeing*

Description: This theme refers to impact of remote supervision on supervisor wellbeing in terms of general confidence, the effect of workload on wellbeing. It also attempts to capture burdens on the supervisor as a result of remote supervision.

Codes: *supervisor-confidence-motivation, supervisor workload-burden,*

Code: *supervisor- confidence-motivation*

Description: This code captures the effect of remote supervision on supervisor confidence and motivation. For instance one supervisor felt uncomfortable and unsure with having to advice students and whether or not to travel to Ireland or on topic, which they felt, was outside their remit. Although this was a direct result of Covid this could have broader implications with respect to remote supervision and expectations from supervisors i.e. "I found weird I am having to give students advice on stuff like this and I am like I don't know. Should I shouldn't come to Ireland and,I don't want to encourage you to travel when maybe it's going to be a problem and, but if I don't encourage you to travel now, you might have to pay for me to quarantine in three weeks time"

The same supervisor expressed concerns about whether remote supervision would become more mainstream i.e. is it the new norm, which we are going to have PhDs and master's students online.

As results for the move to online/remote supervision the supervisor “made a conscious effort to say I’m backing off with the number of students are going to have during this whole (online) process” and also “could have taken on more students” but had felt unsure i.e. “because I’m a little bit nervous”

Another supervisor raises the issue of how “nobody teaches had to be a PhD supervisor right so from observing your own advisor and observing other other advisors right, and then we don't get to do that anymore so there's definitely an issue”. This implies that with out the face to face contact from other supervisors from which to model off, supervisor working remotely may feel they are on their own and that their be a need for the provision of explicit helping skills training to academics engaged in remote supervision.

Code: *supervisor workload-burden*

Description: In this context, refers to discussions around the challenges related to postgraduate supervision workload i.e. the number of postgraduate (taught and research) students they are required to manage i.e. “you have so many projects going on” ... “20 people I mean every day and I don't know what I’ve said to”.

In addition this code captures the burden on supervisors’ wellbeing created by both existing workload and the impact of remote supervision with respect to i) no having enough time i.e. haven't got time to meet all seven of them in the week, which does happen” ii) meeting students at unusual times i.e. one supervision mentions meetings in weird times which I wouldn't normally not do...Like very late, maybe quite early” and another supervisor “when I was meeting her(the student) at that point, it was it was late in the day for me”, which is a result of time zone differences.

On supervisor raises concerns around their own wellbeing in relation to workload i.e. “I’m finding all of it bit of a struggle” and another raising the negative effects on all parties of continuous video conferencing for conducting remote supervision i.e. kind of given them ...open ended zoom slots.just really conscious of zoom's tiring”

F2.4 Theme: Modalities of Supervision (Pros and Cons)

Theme Name: Modalities of Supervision (Pros and Cons)

Description: This theme refers to the observations arising in the data in relation to the various

modalities and types of research supervision i.e. face to face of campus based supervision, remote and or distance supervision typically 100% online as well as a mix of both (blended). It also includes co-supervision as form of remote supervision which maybe cross-institutional and supervision of part-time students.

Codes: *blended delivery, online- interaction, face-to-face, remote-co-supervision, part-time-phd*

Code: *online-interaction.*

Description and Analysis:

The discussions associated with this code centred around online interaction as a form of supervision. There have been positive experiences with respect to synchronously communicating with students via chat often using a tool call Slack i.e. “ I love the fact that some of your having you know conversations between students and slack” and “they just chat with each other and they used to it and that for them is the same as meeting at the water cooler”. This is usually in the context of research group interaction or supervision of research groups remotely. Other experiences have been negative where a supervisor offers students to “contact me on Skype we have a slack but sometimes you just don't seem to bring up issues until the next meeting” and the students will “drop things into the slack but one or two PhDs I co supervise they wont are waiting” until the next video meeting. Other supervisor also agreed the students may be “scared” to reach out online resulting in little interaction i.e. “we didn't have that much interaction”. The Slack tool appear to counter act in part the absence of spontaneity(*Subtheme: Research Enculturation*) experienced due to the absence of on campus contact i.e. “every communication is intentional and deliberate and we've lost that spontaneous we also have slack which has been good”. A positive advantage of organising online group meetings for supervising research students is that the ease of access and organisation as a result of tools like Zoom allows the supervisor to delegate management of research meetings thus fostering enculturation for example one Professor has a weekly one-to-one online supervision with each student but also host a group supervision biweekly. Every second week this is hosted by a senior PhD i.e. i.e. every second meeting I don't turn up I tell me and I let them just meet themselves” and “it's been fantastic, because...they let their hair down a bit, because even though I think I'm relaxed, I may talk too much... they've got their own dynamic going on, so every second meeting is their meeting”. Supervisors also mentioned the impact of different time zones and technical difficulties encountered when interacting online. Examples included “connection is not working....terrible” and the output on the screen “hanging heavy over the keyboard having some technical difficulty:

Another supervisor described the difficulties of trying to organise social activities with online board games in a Zoom meeting for an induction meeting with doctoral students so that students could “trash talk and then we're playing the game - look it kind of worked, but the whole thing was really, weird because I didn't get to know the students, particularly well.

A common negative experience of supervisors communicating online in the context of video conferencing is *loss-of-physical-context* when interacting with students but this address under the subtheme *Student-Supervisor-Relationship*.

Finally some supervisors indicated the issue may be with them and for “Digitally native” younger students socialising and working online may be quite normal in that “ they are attracted - that's how that is increasingly how they interact in the way, independent of covid” and “ for digital natives” remote supervision and online interaction “is nothing that unusual”. Supervisors agreed that it may be the case that they are “seeing the world through the lens” of their “own (online) experiences “ and that they should not “overplay ...the role of Zoom”

Code: *blended-delivery*.

Description and Analysis:

The justification for this code as it does highly the issue of attempting to replicate the conditions the research environment (particular in the context of Covid) where the university wishes to have research students partly based on campus (blended) and remotely. However this naturally could generalise to blended postgraduate research programmes (post-Covid) The universities “week on week off traffic light system” presents challenges in that you “can't then have the same setup in both places, because you can't move stuff back and forth”. For example one supervisor described how one student “took his (computer) tower home on the bus last March, because he knew that there was going to be issues withtrying to ...manage it remotely. But that means if he wants to be week on week off what's he supposed to do..... carries his kit (desktop computer) back and forth every other week”. Hence a blended research programme would need to factor in

Code: *face-to-face interaction*.

Description and Analysis:

This code captures some of the practical difficulties supervisors are experiencing as result of the

absence face-to-face interaction as a by-product of remote supervision. For example “problems that they have at the end of the week.... could have been resolved throughout the week” if a student had dropped into to their supervisor’s office briefly. “You gotta be at the door and quickly solve the problem, so we lost that completely” Online interaction appears to inhibit the approachability of the supervision and supervisors experience this as a loss i.e. missing that type of... day to day interaction just a three four or five minute conversation, how are you getting on?” One supervisor indicated that face to face meetings despite their length were “absolutely fine” and “energizing”.

Code: *remote-co-supervision*

Description and Analysis:

Although mentioned briefly, this code is included provides interesting insights into the benefits of remote cross site co-supervision whereby it is “actually a really great foundation for our future supervisions, because we've got this understanding of how to supervise remotely”. Another supervisor mentions that in their co-supervision arrangement that they “have the same experience actually” and “it makes no difference at all, like I have kind of forgotten that the supervisor is in another university”. The first supervisor mentions some minor concern about how the dynamic may change once on-campus study resumes i.e. “because we're all interacting in the same way, so it's going to be interesting to see when we hopefully return to regularly scheduled programming” and “where potentially there'll be one dialled in to a weekly meeting or I'll be the one dialling into a weekly meeting and we won't be equal anymore will it change?” There is a hint here from the supervisor that the power dynamic may be change in perhaps a negative way but this is speculative, requiring more research.

Code: *part-time-phd*

Description and Analysis:

Although mentioned briefly, this code is included provides interesting insights into the quite strong negative perceptions of two supervisors of part time doctoral supervision (face-to-face or remotely) i.e. I feel a little bit like part time PhDs in computinghugely risky... even in four years, some of the stuff that my (full-time) guys are doing is out of date”. Another supervisor strongly agreed in that “part time PHDs are a nightmare!I don't entertain them at all, so I kind of zoned out to everybody, part time PHD and I don't know I've done it before I took nine years - never fuckin again not me”. Both supervisors agreed the a part time PhD was manageable if the research topic was fundamental .i.e. “the only way to do it is you have to pick a topic that's absolutely fundamental....

no way you'll do can have any applied computing science right or AIsomething deeply mathematical”

G2.5 Theme: Supervision Styles

Theme Name: Supervision Styles

Description: This theme refers to impact of remote supervision with respect to different supervision management styles. The codes are in part influenced by Gatfield’s (2005) supervision management grid. Management styles include i) a deliberate or directorial style ii) a more apprenticeship/pastoral style. In addition, this theme explores the impact of remote supervision on the flexibility of supervision delivery and on supervisor capacity to switch supervision styles (Gatfield ,2005) dynamically throughout the course of the student’s PhD.

Codes: *apprenticeship-style, directorial-deliberate, dynamic-flexible-supervision*

Code: *apprenticeship-style*

Description and Analysis:

This code captures the concept of an apprenticeship/mentor/coach/pastoral style model to supervision. I also subsumes under it the *laisser-faire and pastoral styles or low structure and low direction* forms of research supervision (Gatfield ,2005). The code is mentioned typically when supervisors are discussing the supervision style prior to the emergency move to online/remote supervision. Typically with respect to traditional face to face supervision, academics were sometimes *laisser-faire* “relying on **ad hoc** relying on all these (face to face) interactions for just figuring stuff out, which is life, you know that's **improvisational** thing” “or a lot on kind of **winging it**”:

. Prior to the move to remote supervision the some supervisors’ expectations of the postgraduate researcher “was to go from undergrad to completely **...sink or swim - you know Sparta**you know surviving is - it can be shocking”. So students were expected to adhere to the traditional apprenticeship style model be highly motivated, take initiative and work independently. Supervisors do not view themselves as line managers or directorial but a mentor/coach i.e. “we'll call it a **pastoral model** to some degree right,” and “you've signed up to do a marathonand I’m **your coach not your boss** right”.

Other examples are of the mentor/apprenticeship style” I’m **not your boss you don't work for me to ... don't' come in and expect** ...I’m going **to tell you what to do.** as well “**don't expect me** to tell you

get your working hours or your holidays it's **you've set yourself this challenge** of a PhD" or "I'm going **to coach you through it** I'm your **advisor like in the US style of a PhD advisor**" or we're **just mentors not actually bosses**.

Other examples include applying this style to face-to-face supervision during the early stages of the PhD student's degree and although it may involve providing high-level tasks it is not directive – the student is left to accomplish them over six months. i.e. more alight **standoffish here are the the concrete tasks, you need to accomplish in the first six months** kind of thing and then hopefully by the end **it's much more of a sharing of my experiences**". There is an acknowledgement however that the move to remote supervision has required placing more structures in place and this maybe a positive learning experience for the supervisor i.e. " so maybe **it's good that.....there's some structure** there"

Codes: *directorial-deliberate*

Description and Analysis:

This code captures the experience that supervisors are becoming more deliberate and even directorial in the communications and tasks setting since the move to remote supervising . For instance one supervisor will now " **cut to the chase** I had to be **way more deliberate** and ain't that if I just say it" and while another commented "I do find that, as I said, it is 100% **more deliberate**". Another example of the change in student-supervisor interaction with respect to verbal communication "like I'd probably change up the way I speak a little better.....might start asking them probing questions. Another example is the need to be deliberate with respect to the time allotted for a supervision meeting i.e. even the conversation that we have now is **very much project and a targeted thing** because, unfortunately, what I can see it's very much that that is **my hour**, so we need **to get as much into that** as possible".

Another example of directorial where a supervisor tries to enforce structure on remote working hours with research students i.e. like I've **given out to** one or two students before when I'd see like you know they send an email at two in the morning and giving them a **good bit of a talk on** burnout and how **you need to get off** that now.

In addition, supervisors express unhappiness with the move to more deliberate forms of supervision and communication i.e. "I do find out now things are a **lot more deliberate** I feel like everything's moving more towards the idea like it's a project, and **there are tasks to be completed**, and in the

meeting, did you complete those tasks...?...like the (taught) Masters projects or the final your projects for the undergraduate degrees, I find the PhDs moving on that way and its a shame". However another supervisor commented on the positives about being more directorial/deliberate in that the approach in that it reduces their stress and cognitive load as being directorial " makes life so much easier, it does probably pushes more into the managerial style, as opposed to the pastoral, but it really makes my brain relax because I'm not having to try and remember who you (the student) are what are you doing again".

Codes: *dynamic-flexible-supervision*

Description and Analysis:

This code describes the overall impact on the flexibility expected from supervisors as well any barriers raised by remote supervision to the supervisor's ability to adapt supervision management styles to the student's needs. In the context remote supervision can mean an increase in flexibility for both the supervisor and student. Working online does offer advantages to the supervisor with respect to an increase of communication options i.e. I think there is much more flexibility" and " I have a student, for example, that has children so for her it's actually easier, sometimes to zoom to organize a quick meeting ...just out of the blue. However, this may depend at what stage the student is in their PhD "but she's also a fourth year student. ...assume she's more willing, you know, to reach out to me at every time Like she she reached out via whatsapp whatsoever, I think, for first year student will be much different".

However this may mean the supervisor is required to organise a supervision session outside regular hours if a student has to "set up a shift with her husband" "is working a night" , the supervisor will need to fix" a particular supervision late night slot. Experiences vary from supervisor, for example one supervisor found it "next to impossible to arrange on a week by week basis of a rolling dynamic time, so ... if you want to meet your students, you are kind of almost forced the very high structured environment".

Regardless of their experiences either (positive or negative) supervisors also feel strongly that remote supervision should not be "the standard ...the normal way of operating... not for a PhD.

With respect to supervision management styles and being dynamically able to adapt to the needs and stages of the PhD student, one supervisors expressed concern in that they felt "straight jacketed by zoom in terms of how what style" they could adapt to. Another supervisor commented on whether supervising online allows supervisors "the freedom to change gears and whether they can "shift gears on zoom" with respect to PhD management styles.

Interestingly, however another supervisor felt that imposing structures did not necessarily lead to a more deliberate or directorial supervision style in that “the (supervision) meeting that the nature ...hasn't changed in that way” . A supervisor “can have this meeting that happens regularly but within the meeting you don't have to become like hardcore project manager”. The supervisor is “not really straight jacketed” by Zoom and that it that it does “not necessarily change your supervisory style” and that it was “still very possible to have that sort of pastoral approach” with a series of structured meeting.

A clear example i a doctoral student who is in thesis write up whereby although the supervisor has regular meetings, the management style is *laisser-faire* within the meeting i.e.” I haven't met him for a few weeks at the last time we had a meeting that was really pointless,he was sort of in the zone and we've didn't really have anything to discuss and i've left it”

This above also resulted in the need to distinguish between the *deliberate*-directorial supervision style and the concept of *functional-structured* (Theme: Concepts of Supervision) supervision which was not necessarily directive when generating codes.

G2.6 Theme: Research Environment

Theme Name: Research Environment

Description: This theme refers to challenges, which arise in remote research supervision within the context of accessing the research environment – physical and/or virtual. It may be the campus access to the research centre/university environment including, the research lab space, desk space, learning space, seminar rooms as well as equipment ain computer labs, labs for electronic engineering, science lab for experiments. It may include remote access to servers and datasets or take home access to hardware or materials, data or equipment that would otherwise normally reside on (in) campus. This theme also refers to challenges and issues surrounding institutional support for supervisors and research students as well as legal-finance challenges that may be inadvertently caused by the move remote supervision/research study.

Codes: *access-to-materials-data, access-to-lab-equipment, home-access-to-equipment, legal-financial-issues, student-learning-space*

Code: access-to-materials-data

Description and Analysis: This code concerned with the challenges surrounding access large

datasets and or data critical for experiments. It may apply to other research materials i.e chemicals. Some students /supervisors going to “enormous negotiations” with a third party collaborator and are required to sign a non disclosure agreement and evidence that the data stored securely off campus “we could sign a contract saying that we made every effort to ensure not only was this dataset not stored on Internet cable computer, but it was physically prevented from being accessed”. “ we ended up actually purchasing this guy's safe, which is presumably under his bed”. Sensitive third party data access would not be an issue with campus based research and supervision the data would under physically restricted access” and it “wouldn't be a problem”.

Code: access-to-lab-equipment

Description and Analysis:

This code concerned with the challenges surrounding research students gaining access to the research lab on campus. This is usually in the context of gaining access to high performing hardware such machines with graphic processing unit(GPU) needed for building complex learning models and this negative impacts this has on the students research i.e. “whole sway the PhDs that just can't happen without physical access to your expensive infrastructure and even for ours that the gpu's”. Although remote access to servers with GPUs was made available to research students and work progressed “and the remote access - look it works”, there is the sense that this suboptimal and “we're trying to muddle through and figure out ways to rearrange their plans and put stuff off, but at certain points, they need to be in there” Although in the context of this research study the focus in students of computer science, the doctoral thesis are interdisciplinary such as combining data science and chemistry or mechanical engineering i.e. “mixing chemicals and then using the bio printer and you know building devices to desalinate water”. These students require laboratory access to complete their experiments which is challenging for both student and supervisor i.e. “two of my co supervision are in Mech Eng and they need physical access to a lab”

As mentioned by one participant “if you're looking at this beyond just computing then that raises a whole bunch of totally separate questions about remote supervision”. In addition in order set up the same lab conditions at “home”, supervisors in some case purchase new equipment for instalment at the student's home i.e. “doing air quality and they had to buy all this stuff “.

Code: home-access-to-equipment

Description and Analysis:

This code concerned with the challenges surrounding research students having or retaining access to campus equipment for remote work i.e. laptops and computer hardware, monitors and graphic

processing unit(GPU)s at home and the challenges surrounding this. In particular one participant highlighted the impressive response by department " I was so impressed at how well the school and university in general responded last March, when they basically said take your computer home take your screen home if you need to take a taxi just do what you need to do, which I was so impressed they did that". However, on the negative side it adds additional burden on the supervisor " had to drop piece of equipment off to the student's housethe student was also not been able to come and have a place at the university". In addition there are issues for students concerning the heat electricity generated from powerful hardware that is being housed in a small unventilated space and the potential negative impact on the health of the student and the maintenance of specialist university hardware in improper conditions i.e. we've sent them home with the gpu machines - that's noisy , heat electricitysomeone who's in what a three by three room and eating, sleeping, working" and "the room isn't properly controlled for temperature and stuff like that

Code: legal-financial-issues,

Description and Analysis:

This code captures any legal and financial complexities surrounding research students residing outside of the country while also being registered for full time campus based attendance and in receipt of scholarship. In addition supervisors raise concerns i.e." it's such a complicated question because the University has certain things it wants to try and do, but there are others that are related to tax issues visa issues". In some cases supervisors are critical of the university expectation that off-campus students should reside in the country i.e. "It's been a little bit short sighted" . PhDs students in receipt of a tax-free fellowship in Ireland must reside in the country in order "get a social security number you have to be here and have a bank accounts to get a bank account, you have to have a residential address in Ireland". Supervisors are faced with the conundrum of paying a stipend to a student who is not yet resident which not part of the regular procedure i.e. "technically, we can probably pay them, but do we really want to start paying them when they haven't come, yet what if they drop out". One supervisor hints that the university is applying some pressure (by whom is unclear) to have full time postgraduate students who are studying remotely to be resident within the country i.e." is a sort of a little arm twisting going on to try and get them back. It should be noted that although these issue may not be limited to the campus based restrictions COVID-19 and it has broader impact on the potential for any future plans to have full time registered students studying remotely (non resident) who are receipt of a tax free scholarship and the challenges this raises legally and financially for the university and supervisor.

Code student-learning-space

Description and Analysis:

This code describes the challenges surrounding whether research students have optimal or suboptimal learning spaces in which to conduct their research and studies. In some positive cases the student may “actually have their own space and maybe they have a desk” while for other students it is negative whereby, “you can very clearly hear that they are living in a very noisy household and there is a lot of distraction, and things going on” and that his has “definitely proven difficult for some students”. Another example highlights this clearly that “some students may be in a situation where they have a space in their house where they can work ...the ones that could be living with family in a very disruptive environment”. The same participant notes that with campus based study that “all of those problems didn't exist because you had your space where you were you had your work, and that was kind of it, so the muddying of those waters.”. Here the blurring of work life boundaries is also hinted. In addition, a submit optimal learning space may have a negative impact on student health i.e. “have physical issues because of having to work in a non optimum bedroom”

Appendix H: Extended Discussion on Reflexive Thematic Analysis

3.4 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

As mentioned earlier Thematic Analysis (TA) is a collection of approaches for analysing qualitative data which focus on identifying patterns of meaning or *themes* in qualitative data. As stated by (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2012b) while there are different versions of TA which share some degree of theoretical flexibility, they can differ enormously in terms of both underlying philosophy and procedures for producing themes. For instance other analytic methods such as thematic Decomposition Analysis(DA) and Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis(IPA) (Smith and Osborn, 2003) , Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2002). Similar to TA, IPA and Grounded Theory look for patterns in the data but are “theory bounded” (Braun and Clarke, 2021b). IPA is connected to phenomenological epistemology, which is about understanding people’s everyday experience in great detail. Also as well patterning of meaning across participants, it focuses on the unique characteristics of individual participants. Also, I am less concerned with different and divergent data (Braun and Clarke, 2021b) Grounded Theory on the other hand comes in many flavours and there is a lot of debate on its correct usage in the literature (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Furthermore, it is concerned with inducing and developing a theory from the data, which is not our goal here. Grounded theory is suitable for large projects which is not the case and it is argued in the literature that it is rarely used fully even when grounded theory is claimed as the analysis method (Pidgeon and Henwood, 1997). Finally thematic Decomposition Analysis(DA) is concerned with identifying shared patterns (stories and/or themes) which are produced via social interactions as it is bound to social constructivist epistemology (Braun and Clarke, 2021a, 2021b). A detailed comparison of reflective thematic analysis with other forms of TA is outside the scope of this thesis and we refer the reader to Braun and Clarke, (2021a, 2021b) for a detailed discussion. While many forms of TA tend to share some degree of theoretical flexibility, they can differ enormously in terms of both underlying philosophy and procedures for producing themes.

One of the advantages of the reflexive TA method outlined by is that it is theoretically-flexible; it can be used within different theoretical frameworks for quite different types of research questions. Furthermore, what is key in reflexive TA is that the theoretical position is made clear and that the researcher “acknowledge these decisions and recognise them as decisions” (Braun and Clarke, 2021). .